

Lectures on Some Types of algebras

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CHAPTER ONE

SECTION ONE

- **Introduction to BCK-algebras**

The notion of BCK-algebras was formulated first in 1966 by K. Iseki, Japanese mathematician. This notion is originated from two different ways.

One of the motivations is based on set theory. In set theory, there are three most elementary and fundamental operations including the general analytical operations introduced by L. Cantorovic and E. Livenson to make a new set from old sets. These fundamental operations are to make the union, the intersection and the set difference, then as a generalization of those three operations and properties, we have the notion of Boolean algebras. If we take both of the union and the intersection, then as a general algebra, the notion of distributive lattices is obtained. As a generalization of this notion, for example, there is the notion of semi rings. Moreover, if we consider the notion of the union or the intersection, we have the notion of an upper semi lattice or a lower semi lattice. But the notion of set difference was not considered systematically before K. Iseki. Another motivation is from classical and non-classical propositional calculus. There are some systems which contain the only implication functor among the logical functions. These examples are the system of positive implicational calculus, weak positive implicational calculus by Church, and BCI/BCK-systems by C. A. Meredith (see A.N. Prior). From these relationships, K. Iseki introduced a new notion called a BCK-algebra.

Definitions and elementary properties of BCK-algebras are studied.

DEFINITION 1.1.1.

Let X be a set with a binary operation $*$ and constant 0 . Then $(X; *, 0)$ is called a BCK-algebra if it satisfies the following conditions: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

$$\text{BCI-1} \quad ((x * y) * (x * z)) * (z * y) = 0,$$

$$\text{BCI-2} \quad (x * (x * y)) * y = 0,$$

$$\text{BCI-3} \quad x * x = 0,$$

$$\text{BCI-4} \quad x * y = 0 \text{ and } y * x = 0 \text{ imply } x = y,$$

If a BCI-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ satisfies

$$\text{BCI-5} \quad 0 * x = 0, \text{ for all } x \in X, \text{ then we say that } X \text{ is a BCK-algebra.}$$

REMARK 1.1.2.

For brevity we also call $(X; *, 0)$ a BCK-algebra. In X we can define a binary relation (\leq) by $x \leq y$ if and only if, $x * y = 0$.

DEFINITION 1.1.3.

Let X be a set with a binary operation $*$ and constant 0 . Then $(X;*, 0)$ is called a BCK-algebra if and only if, it satisfies that : for all $x, y, z \in X$,

BCI-1' $(x * y) * (x * z) \leq z * y$,

BCI-2' $x * (x * y) \leq y$,

BCI-3' $x \leq x$,

BCI-4 $x \leq y$ and $y \leq x$ imply $x = y$,

BCK-5' $0 \leq x$,

BCI-6' $x \leq y$ if and only if, $x * y = 0$.

REMARK 1.1.4.

Now, for any BCK-algebra $(X;*, 0)$, $*$ is called a BCK-operation and \leq is called a BCK-ordering on X respectively.

Next, we consider the independence of the axiomatically system of BCK- algebras.

EXAMPLE 1.1.5.

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3, ..\}$ and the operation $*$ be defined as follows:

$$x * y = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x \leq y \\ 1 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Then $(X;*, 0)$ satisfies BCI-1, BCI-3, BCI-4 and BCK-5, but it does not satisfy BCI- 2.

EXAMPLE 1.1.6.

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, ..., w\}$ in which $(*)$ is defined by

$$x * y = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x \leq y \\ y & \text{if } y < x \text{ and } y \neq 0, \\ x & \text{if } y < x \text{ and } y = 0. \end{cases}$$

where \leq is the natural ordering on X and $x < y$ denotes that $x \leq y$ and $x \neq y$.

Then $((X;*, 0)$ satisfies BCI-2 ,BCI-3, BCI-4 and BCK-5 , but does not satisfy BCI-1.

EXAMPLE 1.1.7.

Let $X = \{0,1\}$ in which $*$ is defined by the following table:

*	0	1
0	0	0
1	0	0

Then $(X;*, 0)$ satisfies BCI-1, BCI-2, BCI-3 and BCK-5, but it does not satisfy BCI-4.

EXAMPLE 1.1.8.

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2\}$ in which $(*)$ is defined by the following table:

*	0	1	2
0	0	0	0
1	2	2	0
2	2	2	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ satisfies BCI-1, BCI-2, BCI-4 and BCK-5, but it does not satisfy BCI-3.

EXAMPLE 1.1.9.

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2\}$ in which the operation $(*)$ is given by the table

*	0	1	2
0	0	0	0
1	2	2	0
2	2	2	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ satisfies BCI-1- BCI-4, but it does not satisfy BCK-2.

The above examples show that BCI-1, BCI-2, BCI-3, BCI-4 and BCK-5 are independent each other.

Now, we give some elementary and fundamental properties of BCK-algebras.

THEOREM 1.1.10.

In a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, we have the following properties : for all $x, y, z \in X$,

- (a) $x \leq y$ implies $z * y \leq z * x$.
- (b) $x \leq y$ and $y \leq z$ imply $x \leq z$.

Proof.

Let $x \leq y$. Then by BCI-1, we have $(z * y) * (z * x) \leq x * y$. Since $x \leq y$ implies $x * y = 0$, we obtain $(z * y) * (z * x) \leq 0$. Combining BCK-5' and BCI-4' we have $(z * y) * (z * x) = 0$, that is, $z * y \leq z * x$, and hence (a) holds.

By (a), $y \leq z$ implies $x * z \leq x * y$. If $x \leq y$ then $x * y = 0$. Hence $x * z \leq 0$, and so $x \leq z$. Therefore, we have (b). ■

Putting BCI-3', BCI-4' and (b) together we know that (X, \leq) is a partially ordered set.

THEOREM 1.1.11.

In a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, we have $(x * y) * z = (x * z) * y$ for all $x, y, z \in X$.

Proof.

By BCI-2', we have $x * (x * z) \leq z$. Making use of (a) and BCI-1', we get $(x * y) * z \leq (x * y) * (x * (x * z)) \leq (x * z) * y$.

Since x, y and z are arbitrary, interchanging y and z in the above inequality we obtain $(x * z) * y \leq (x * z) * (x * (x * y)) \leq (x * y) * z$. By BCI-4', we have $(x * y) * z = (x * z) * y$. ■

THEOREM 1.1.12.

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCK-algebra. Then the following hold: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

- (a) $x * y \leq z$ implies $x * z \leq y$,
- (b) $(x * z) * (y * z) \leq x * y$,
- (c) $x \leq y$ implies $x * z \leq y * z$,
- (d) $x * y \leq x$,
- (e) $x * 0 = x$.

Proof.

(a) is a directly consequence of Theorem (1.1.11).

(b) follows from BCI-1' and (a) without any difficulty.

(c) Let $x \leq y$, then $x * y = 0$, and hence by (b), $(x * z) * (y * z) \leq x * y = 0$.

Hence $x * z \leq y * z$, and (c) holds.

(d) By virtue of (a), BCI-3 and BCK-5, we have $(x * y) * x = (x * x) * y = 0 * y = 0$.

Consequently $x * y \leq x$, proving (d).

(e) By BCI-2', we have $x * (x * 0) \leq 0$, that is, $x \leq x * 0$.

Moreover by (d), we get $x * 0 \leq x$. Hence by BCI 4', (e) holds. ■

REMARK 1.1.13.

For any $x, y \in X$ denote $x \wedge y = y * (y * x)$. Obviously, $x \wedge y$ is a lower bound of x and y , and $x \wedge x = x, x \wedge 0 = 0 \wedge x = 0$. But in general, $x \wedge y \neq y \wedge x$.

THEOREM 1.1.14

In any BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, we have $x * (y \wedge x) = x * y$, for all $x, y \in X$.

Proof.

For any $x, y \in X$, since $y \wedge x \leq y$, by Theorem (1.1.12(a)) we get $x * y \leq x * (y \wedge x)$

On the other hand, by BCK-2' we have $x * (y \wedge x) = x * (x * (x * y)) \leq x * y$.

This means $x * y = x * (y \wedge x)$. ■

In the following, we give two equivalent definitions for BCI- algebras.

THEOREM 1.1.15.

An algebra $(X;*, 0)$ of type $(2, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra if and only if, it satisfies the following conditions:

BCI-1 $((x * y) * (x * z)) * (z * y) = 0,$

1. $x * (0 * y) = x,$

BCI-4 $x * y = 0$ and $y * x = 0$ imply $x = y$.

Proof.

The part "only if " is obvious and omitted. We give the proof the part "if" as follows.

Putting $x = z = 0$ and using (BCI-1) we have $((0 * y) * (0 * 0)) * (0 * y) = 0,$
 $(0 * y) * (0 * 0) = 0, \Rightarrow 0 * y = 0,$ thus BCK-5 holds.

Combining (a) and BCK-5 we get (1) $x * 0 = x$. Substituting 0 for y and z in BCI-1 and using (1) we easily obtain BCI-3 $x * x = 0$.

Replacing y by 0 in BCI-1 and applying (1) it follows that BCI-2 $(x * (x * y)) * y = 0$
 . Summarizing the above results we have proved that $(X;*, 0)$ is a BCK- algebra. ■

REMARK 1.1.16.

In combinatory logic, there are various combinators. The names of combinators are attached to formulas of the algebra in the following way :

If a combinator U has functionality V the corresponding formula is obtained by replacing F Z W in V by $W * Z$ and equating the result with 0. (If a logical system is to be represented each F Z W becomes $Z \supset W$ and the results is preceded by \vdash ; for more details on the combinators, their functionality and their corresponding tautologies, see H. B. Curry and R.

The functionality of the combinators K, B, C, I and W are given by

- $\vdash Fx (Fyx) .$ K
- $\vdash F(Fxy)(F(Fzx)(Fzy)) .$ B
- $\vdash F(Fx(Fyz))(Fy(Fxz)) .$ C
- $\vdash Fxx .$ I
- $\vdash F (Fx (Fxy)) (Fxy) .$ W.

Thus according to the above procedure the corresponding formulas are :

- K $(x * y) * x = 0$,
 B $((y * z) * (x * z)) * (y * x) = 0$,
 C $((z * x) * y) * ((z * y) * x) = 0$,
 I $x * x = 0$,
 W $(y * x) * ((y * x) * x) = 0$.

In 1981, M. W. Bunder, gave the following theorem.

THEOREM 1.1.17.

An algebra $(X;*,0)$ of type $(2, 0)$ is a BCK- algebra if and only if, it satisfies the axioms B, C and K and the rule BCI-4 .

Proof.

The part "only if" has been proved in Theorems (1.1.12 and 1.1.13). For the part "if", interchanging x and $y \in C$ gives $((z * y) * x) * ((z * x) * y) = 0$.

Applying the rule BCI-4 we have (1) $(z * y) * x = (z * x) * y$. By (1) and B it follows that $((x * y) * (x * z)) * (z * y) = ((x * y) * (z * y)) * (x * z) = 0$, which says that BCL-1 holds. (1) and K give

(2) $(x * x) * 0 = (x * 0) * x = 0$.

Using (2) and K we get $0 * (x * x) = ((x * x) * 0) * (x * x) = 0$.

The two identities above and the rule BCI-4 give BCI-3. By BCI-3 and K we obtain

$0 * x = (x * x) * x = 0$, which is BCK-2.. From (1) and BCI-3 it follows that

$(x * (x * y)) * y = (x * y) * (x * y) = 0$, namely, BCI-2 holds.

Therefore, $(X;*,0)$ is a BCK-algebra.

This theorem exhibits a closed relationship between BCK-algebras and combinatory logic, and the name of BCK-algebras is also taken from the BCK-systems of C. A. Meredith.

The following examples are interesting for development of BCK-algebras.

EXAMPLE 1.1.18.

Let A be an arbitrary nonempty set and let X be the set of all real valued functions defined on

A. For $f, g \in X$, we define $f * g$ by $:(f * g)(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{iff } f(x) \leq g(x) \\ f(x) - g(x) & \text{if } g(x) < f(x) \end{cases}$.

By the definition of $(X;*,0)$ is a BCK-algebra.

EXAMPLE 1.1.19.

Let M be the set of all non-negative integers. For any x, y in M , we put

$$x * y = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x \leq y \\ x - y & \text{if } y < x \end{cases} . \text{ Then } M \text{ is a BCK-algebra.}$$

EXAMPLE 1.1.20.

Let M be a partially ordered set with the least element (0) . The operation $(*)$ on M is defined by:

$$x * y = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x \leq y \\ x & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$$

Then $(M ; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra. Hence any partially ordered set is regarded as a BCK-algebra.

As a special case of this example, we have

EXAMPLE 1.1.21.

Let X be a nonempty set. The power set is denoted by $P(X)$, and \emptyset the empty set, the binary operation $(*)$ on $P(X)$ is given by, for any A, B in $P(X)$,

$$A * B = \begin{cases} \emptyset & \text{if } A \subseteq B \\ A - B & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} . \text{ Then } (P(X); *, \emptyset) \text{ is a BCK-algebra.}$$

EXAMPLE 1.1.22.

Let X be a partially ordered set with the least element 0 and a distinguished element a such that

$0 \leq x$ for all x in X and $a \leq x$ for all nonzero x in X . The operation $*$ is defined as follows:

$$x * y = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x \leq y \\ x & \text{if } y = 0 \\ a & \text{otherwise} \end{cases} . \text{ Then } (X ; *, 0) \text{ is a BCK-algebra.}$$

This example is due to Y. Seto (see K. Iséki) .

The main materials in this section are from Professor K. Iséki and S. Tanaka. The examples (1-4) were given by H. Jiang and Z.P. Tian.

CHAPTER ONE

SECTION TWO

1.2 Subalgebras of BCI/BCK-algebras

In this section, we shall discuss the number of subalgebras in a finite BCK-algebra.

DEFINITION 1.2.1.

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCK-algebra and let X_0 be a nonempty subset of X . Then X_0 is called to be a subalgebra of X if, for any x, y in X_0 ; $x * y \in X_0$.

i.e., X_0 is closed under the binary operation $*$ of X .

THEOREM 1.2.2.

Suppose that $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra and let X_0 be a subalgebra of X . Then

- (a) $0 \in X_0$,
- (b) $(X_0; *, 0)$ is also a BCK-algebra,
- (c) X_0 is a subalgebra of X ,
- (d) $\{0\}$ is a subalgebra of X .

Proof.

This is immediate from Definition (1.2.1). ■

Routine calculation now leads to the following.

THEOREM 1.2.3.

If we are given a nonzero element x_0 of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, then $(\{0, x_0\}; *, 0)$ is a subalgebra of X .

LEMMA 1.2.4.

In a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, for all $x, y, z \in X$,

- (a) If $x \neq y$, then $y * x \neq 0$, whenever $x * y = 0$,
- (b) $x * y = z$ implies $z * x = 0$.

Proof: Suppose that $x \neq y$ and $x * y = 0$.

If $y * x = 0$, by BCI-4 we obtain $x = y$, which contradicts to $x \neq y$. Hence (a) holds.

If $x * y = z$, it follows from Theorem (1.1.13(d)) that

$z * x = (x * y) * x = (x * x) * y = 0 * y = 0$. This shows that (b) is true. ■

DEFINITION 1.2.5.

For a n -sequence a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ the $(n - 1) \times n$ matrix

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 * a_2 & a_2 * a_1 & \dots & a_n * a_1 \\ a_1 * a_3 & a_2 * a_3 & \dots & a_n * a_2 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_1 * a_n & a_2 * a_n & \dots & a_n * a_{n-1} \end{pmatrix}$$

is called **the adjoint matrix relative to the n-sequence** a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n .

THEOREM 1.2.6.

Given a n-sequence a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n ($n \geq 2$) of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, if $a_i \neq a_j$, whenever $i \neq j$, ($1 \leq i, j \leq n$), then there exists at least a column in the adjoint matrix A which consists of nonzero elements.

Proof.

We proceed by induction on n . If $n = 2$ then $A = (a_1 * a_2, a_2 * a_1)$.

Suppose $a_1 * a_2 = a_2 * a_1 = 0$. Then we have $a_1 = a_2$ by BCI-4, a contradiction. Hence the assertion holds for $n = 2$.

Now suppose that the assertion holds for $n = k$. For a $k+1$ -sequence $a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k, a_{k+1}$ of X , let $a_i \neq a_j$ whenever $i \neq j$ ($1 \leq i, j \leq k+1$) and adjoint matrix

$$A_{k+1} = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 * a_2 & a_2 * a_1 & \dots & a_k * a_1 & a_{k+1} * a_1 \\ a_1 * a_3 & a_2 * a_3 & \dots & a_k * a_2 & a_{k+1} * a_2 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots & \vdots \\ a_1 * a_k & a_2 * a_k & \dots & a_k * a_{k-1} & a_{k+1} * a_{k-1} \\ a_1 * a_{k+1} & a_2 * a_{k+1} & \dots & a_k * a_{k+1} & a_{k+1} * a_k \end{pmatrix}$$

Denote

$$A_k = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 * a_2 & a_2 * a_1 & \dots & a_k * a_1 \\ a_1 * a_3 & a_2 * a_3 & \dots & a_k * a_2 \\ \vdots & \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ a_1 * a_k & a_2 * a_k & \dots & a_k * a_{k-1} \end{pmatrix}$$

Obviously A_k is the adjoint matrix of the k -sequence a_1, a_2, \dots, a_k . By the hypothesis of induction, we know that there is at least a column in A_k , which consists of nonzero elements, without loss of any generality suppose that it is the first column, thus

$$\begin{cases} a_1 * a_2 \neq 0, \\ a_1 * a_3 \neq 0, \\ \vdots \\ a_1 * a_k \neq 0. \end{cases}$$

Now it suffices to discuss the following cases:

If $a_1 * a_{k+1} \neq 0$ then each element in the first column of A_{k+1} is not equal to 0, and consequently the assertion holds for $n = k + 1$.

If $a_1 * a_{k+1} = 0$, then by Lemma (1.2.4), we obtain $a_{k+1} * a_1 \neq 0$ as $a_1 \neq a_{k+1}$.

We can verify $a_{k+1} * a_i \neq 0$ for $2 \leq i \leq k$. In fact, if there is i_0 ($2 \leq i_0 \leq k$) such that $a_{k+1} * a_{i_0} = 0$, in view of Theorem (1.1.12(b)) we get $a_1 * a_{i_0} = 0$ as $a_1 * a_{k+1} = 0$. This is impossible.

This shows that each element in the first column of A_{k+1} is not equal to 0, and so the assertion holds for $n = k + 1$. ■

REMARK 1.2.7.

For a set A denote the cardinal of A by $|A|$. For a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, $|X|$ is called to be the order of this algebra.

If $|X| < \infty$, then X is called to be of finite order.

If $|X| = n$, then X is said to be of order n .

If $|X| = \infty$, then X is said to be of infinite order.

THEOREM 1.2.8.

Any BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ with order $n + 1$ must contain a subalgebra with order n ($n \geq 1$).

Proof.

Suppose $X = \{0, a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n\}$ is a BCK-algebra with order $n + 1$, in which $a_i \neq a_j$ whenever $i \neq j$ and let

$$A = \begin{pmatrix} a_1 * a_2 & a_2 * a_1 & \dots & a_n * a_1 \\ a_1 * a_3 & a_2 * a_3 & \dots & a_n * a_2 \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ \cdot & \cdot & \cdot & \cdot \\ a_1 * a_n & a_2 * a_n & \dots & a_n * a_{n-1} \end{pmatrix}$$

be the adjoint matrix of the n -sequence a_1, a_2, \dots, a_n . By Theorem (1.2.6) there exists at least a column in A which consists of nonzero elements, without loss of generality, we can suppose it is the n -th column of A that is, $a_n * a^i \neq 0, i = 1, 2, \dots, n-1$.

We now show that $X_0 = \{0, a_1, \dots, a_{n-1}\}$ is a subalgebra of X . In fact, if not, then there are i and $j (1 \leq i, j \leq n-1)$ such that $i \neq j$ and $a_i * a_j = a_n$. By means of Lemma (1.2.4(a)), we have $a_n * a_i = 0, i = 1, 2, \dots, n-1$, which contradicts to $a_n * a_i \neq 0 (1 \leq i \leq n-1)$. ■

Next we give a theorem of estimating the number of subalgebras in a finite BCK-algebra.

THEOREM 1.2.9.

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCK-algebra with order $n (\geq 1)$. Then $1 \leq N(i) \leq C_{n-1}^{i-1}, i = 1, 2, \dots, n$, where $N(i)$ denotes the number of subalgebras with order i in X .

Proof.

We know that any subalgebra with order $i (1 \leq i \leq n)$ consists of 0 and $i-1$ nonzero elements. Since X contain only $n-1$ nonzero elements, it follows that $N(i) \leq C_{n-1}^{i-1}$.

On the other hand, by Theorem (1.2.8), X at least contains a subalgebra X_{n-1} with order $n-1$, X_{n-1} contains a subalgebra X_{n-2} with order $n-2$, repeating this argument we get that $1 \leq N(i)$ for all $i (1 \leq i \leq n)$. This completes the proof.

EXAMPLE 1.2.10. Let $X = \{0, a, b, c\}$ in which $*$ is given by the table

$*$	0	a	b	c
0	0	0	0	0
a	a	0	0	a
b	b	a	0	b
c	c	c	c	0

Simple calculations show algebra and the lattice of subalgebras in X is as follows:

that $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCK-

It is not difficult to see that $N(i) = C_{4-1}^{i-1}$, $i=1, 2, 3, 2, 1$. This example shows that in Theorem (1.2.9), $N(i) = C_{n-1}^{i-1}$ may hold.

EXAMPLE 1.2.11.

Let $X = \{0, 1\}$ in which $*$ is defined by $0 * 0 = 0 * 1 = 1 * 1 = 0$ and $1 * 0 = 1$.

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is BCK-algebra and $1 = N(i) = C_{2-1}^{i-1}$ $i=1, 2$.

This example shows that in Theorem (1.2.8), $1 = N(i)$ may hold.

EXAMPLE 1.2.12.

Let $X = \{0, a, b, c, d\}$ with $*$ table be as follows:

*	0	a	b	c	d
0	0	0	0	0	0
a	a	0	a	0	a
b	b	b	0	0	0
c	c	c	c	0	c
d	d	d	b	b	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra, and in X $1 < N(3) < C_{5-1}^{3-1}$.

This example shows that in Theorem (1.2.9), $1 < N(i)$ and $N(i) < C_{n-1}^{i-1}$.

CHAPTER ONE

SECTION THREE

1.3 Bounded BCI/BCK-algebras

In this section, we study bounded of a BCK-algebra.

DEFINITION 1.3.1.

If there is an element e of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ satisfying $x \leq e$, for all x in X , that mean $(x * e = 0)$ the element e is called **unit of X** . a BCK-algebra with unit is called to be a **bounded**.

In a bounded BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, we denote $e * x$ by N_x or x^* .

EXAMPLE 1.3.2.

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ and $*$ operation be given by the table:

$*$	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0	0
2	2	1	0	1	0
3	3	3	3	0	0
4	4	4	4	4	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a bounded BCK-algebra with unit 4.

EXAMPLE 1.3.3.

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, w\}$ with $*$ operation be defined by: for all $x, y, w \in X$

$$x * y = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x \leq y \leq w \\ 1 & \text{if } y < x < w \text{ and } y \neq 0 \\ w & \text{if } y < x = w \text{ and } y \neq 0 \\ x & \text{if } y < x \leq w \text{ and } y = 0 \end{cases}$$

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a bounded BCK-algebra with unit w .

EXAMPLE 1.3.4.

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, \dots\}$ with the natural order. Then we define

$$x * y = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x \leq y, \\ 1 & \text{if } y < x \text{ and } y \neq 0, \\ x & \text{if } y < x \text{ and } y = 0. \end{cases}$$

Under the definition of $*$, $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra, but this is not bounded.

This shows that the class of bounded BCK-algebras is a proper subclass of the class of BCK-algebras.

Next, we give some properties about N_x or x^* .

THEOREM 1.3.5.

In a bounded BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, we have, for all $x, y \in X$

- (a) $e^* = 0, 0^* = e$,
- (b) $x^{**} = x$,
- (c) $x^* * y^* \leq y * x$,
- (d) $y \leq z$ implies $x^* \leq y^*$,
- (e) $(x * y)^* = (y * x)^*$,
- (f) $e \wedge x = x$,
- (g) $x \wedge e = x^{**}$,
- (h) $x^{***} = x^*$.

DEFINITION 1.3.6.

For a bounded BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, if an element x satisfies $x^{**} = x$, then x is called an **involution**.

The set of all involutions of a bounded BCK-algebra X is denoted by $S(X)$. Since $0^{**} = e^* = 0$ and $e^{**} = 0^* = e$, the elements 0 and e are contained in $S(X)$. Hence $S(X)$ is not empty set.

THEOREM 1.3.7.

In a bounded BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, we have $x * y^* = y * x^*$, for all $x, y \in S(X)$.

THEOREM 1.3.8.

For any bounded BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, $S(X)$ is bounded subalgebra of X , which is called **the involutory subalgebra of X** .

Proof.

Let $x, y \in S(X)$. Then by Theorem (1.1.11) and Theorem (1.3.5(h)),

$$\begin{aligned} (x * y) * (x * y)^{**} &= (x^{**} * y) * (x * y)^{**} \\ &= ((x * y)^{***} * y) * x^* = ((x * y)^* * y) * x^* \\ &= (x^{**} * y) * (x * y) = (x * y) * (x * y) = 0. \end{aligned}$$

But then, $(x * y)^{**} * (x * y) = 0$ follows from BCI-2. Thus applying BCI-4 we obtain $(x * y)^{**} = x * y$, which says $x * y \in S(X)$, and consequently $S(X)$ is closed with respect to the operation $*$ namely, $S(X)$ is a subalgebra of X . ■

In the Example (1.3.3), $S(X) = \{0, 1, w\}$. The following theorem give a way extending BCK-algebras.

THEOREM 1.3.9.

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCK-algebra and $e \notin X$. We define the operation $*'$ on $\bar{X} = X \cup \{e\}$ as follows

$$x *' y = \begin{cases} x * y & \text{if } x, y \in X \\ 0 & \text{if } x \in X \text{ and } y = e \\ e & \text{if } x = e \text{ and } y \in X \\ 0 & \text{if } x = y = e \end{cases} . \text{ Then } (\bar{X}; *', 0) \text{ is a bounded BCK-algebra with unit } e.$$

Proof.

In view of Theorem (1.1.17) it suffices to verify BCK-1. If $x, y, z \in X$, then BCK-1, to prove $((x *' y) *' (x *' z)) *' (z *' y) = 0$,

If $x = e$, then $((e *' y) *' (e *' z)) *' (z *' y) = (e *' e) *' (z *' y) = 0 *' (z *' y) = 0$,

If $x = e$ and $y = e$, then $((e *' e) *' (e *' z)) *' (z *' e) = (0 *' e) *' 0 = 0 *' 0 = 0$,

If $x = e$ and $z = e$, then $((e *' y) *' (e *' e)) *' (e *' y) = (e *' 0) *' e = e *' e = 0$,

If $x = y = z = e$, then $((e *' e) *' (e *' e)) *' (e *' e) = (0 *' 0) *' 0 = 0$,

If $x \neq e$, $z \neq e$ and $y = e$, then $((x *' e) *' (x *' z)) *' (z *' e) = (0 *' (x *' z)) *' 0 = 0$,

If $x \neq e$, $y \neq e$ and $z = e$, then $((x *' y) *' (x *' e)) *' (e *' y) = ((x *' y) *' 0) *' e = 0$,

If $x \neq e$ and $y = z = e$, then $(x *' e) *' (x *' e) *' (e *' e) = (0 *' 0) *' 0 = 0$.

This shows that $(\bar{X}; *', 0)$ satisfies BCK-1.

BCK-2, to prove $(x *' (x *' y)) *' y = 0$, if $x = e$, $(e *' (e *' y)) *' y = (e *' e) *' y = 0 *' y = 0$

If $x \neq e$ and $y = e$, $(x *' (x *' e)) *' e = (x *' 0) *' e = x *' e = 0$

If $x \neq e$ and $y \neq e$, $(x *' (x *' y)) *' y = 0$

This shows that $(\bar{X}; *', 0)$ satisfies BCK-2.

BCK-3, to prove $x *' x = 0$, if $x = e$, then $e *' e = 0$, and if $x \neq e$, then $x *' x = 0$

BCK-4, to prove $x *' y = 0$ and $y *' x = 0$, then $x = y$.

If $x *' y = 0$, then either $x \in X, y = e$ or $x = y = e$, then $x = y = e$.

If $y *' x = 0$, then either $y \in X, x = e$ or $x = y = e$, then $x = y = e$.

This shows that $(\bar{X}; *', 0)$ satisfies BCK-4.

BCK-5, to prove $0 *' x = 0$, if $x = e$, then $0 *' e = 0$. And if $x \neq e$, then $0 *' x = 0$

and so it is a BCK-algebra.

Since $e *' x = e$, for all $x \in X$, then $x = e$. And $e *' e = e$. It is clear that e is unit of \bar{X} . ■

It is worth to note that each nonzero element of X is not an involution in \bar{X} . This shows that there is such a BCK-algebra that the set of all involutions consists of 0 and unit. From now on we call $(\bar{X}; *', 0)$ **the Iséki's extension** of $(X; *, 0)$.

EXAMPLE 1.3.10.

Let $X = \{0, a, b, 1\}$ and $*$ be given by :

$*$	0	a	b	1
0	0	0	0	0
a	a	0	0	0
b	b	b	0	0
1	1	b	a	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a bounded BCK algebra and 1 is unit of X . It is easy to see that $S(X) = X$.

CHAPTER ONE

SECTION FOUR

1.4 Positive implicative BCI/BCK-algebras

In this section, we will discuss an important class of algebras called positive implicative BCK-algebras, which was introduced by K. Iséki in 1975.

DEFINITION 1.4.1.

A BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is called to be **positive implicative** if it satisfies for all $x, y, z \in X$, $(x * z) * (y * z) = (x * y) * z$.

In order to give some equivalent conditions of positive implicativity we need following lemma.

LEMMA 1.4.2.

In any BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, we have $(x * (x * y)) * (y * x) \leq x * (x * (y * (y * x)))$, for all $x, y \in X$.

Proof. To prove it, we enough prove

$$\begin{aligned} & ((x * (x * y)) * (y * x)) * (x * (x * (y * (y * x)))) = 0. \text{ Because} \\ & ((x * (x * y)) * (y * x)) * (x * (x * (y * (y * x)))) \\ & \quad = ((x * (x * (x * (y * (y * x)))) * (x * y)) * (y * x), \text{ by Theorem} \\ & (1.1.11). \\ & \quad = ((x * (y * (y * x))) * (x * y)) * (y * x), \text{ by Theorem (1.1.16).} \\ & \quad \leq (y * (y * (y * x))) * (y * x), \text{ by BCI-1.} \\ & \quad = (y * x) * (y * x) = 0, \text{ by BCI-2.} \end{aligned}$$

Hence $(x * (x * y)) * (y * x) \leq x * (x * (y * (y * x)))$. ■

THEOREM 1.4.3.

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCK-algebra. Then the following conditions are equivalent each other: for all $x, y \in X$,

- (a) X is positive implicative,
- (b) $x * y = (x * y) * y$,
- (c) $(x * (x * y)) * (y * x) = x * (x * (y * (y * x)))$,
- (d) $x * y = (x * y) * (x * (x * y))$,
- (e) $x * (x * y) = (x * (x * y)) * (x * y)$,
- (f) $(x * (x * y)) * (y * x) = (y * (y * x)) * (x * y)$.

Proof.

(a) \Rightarrow (b) By Definition (1.4.1), we have $x * y = (x * y) * 0 = (x * y) * (y * y) = (x * y) * y$, which is (b).

(b) \Rightarrow (c) In (b), if we substitute $x * (y * (y * x))$ for y , then we obtain $x * (x * (y * (y * x))) = (x * (x * (y * (y * x)))) * (x * (y * (y * x)))$, by (b).
 $\leq (y * (y * x)) * (x * (y * (y * x)))$, by BCI-1.
 $\leq (y * (y * x)) * (x * y)$, by
 $= (y * (x * y)) * (y * x)$, by Theorem (1.1.11).

$$= ((y * (x * y)) * (y * x)) * (y * x), \text{ by (b),}$$

$$\leq (x * (x * y)) * (y * x), \text{ by BCI-1.}$$

in the above proof, we use $x * y \leq x * (y * (y * x))$. Combining Lemma (1.4.2), we obtain (c).

(c) \Rightarrow (d). Replacing x by $y * x$ in (c) we obtain

$$(y * x) * ((y * x) * y) * (y * (y * x))$$

$$= (y * x) * ((y * x) * (y * (y * (y * x)))).$$

$$= (y * x) * ((y * x) * (y * x)) = (y * x). \text{ Thus (d) holds.}$$

(d) \Rightarrow (e). Substituting $x * y$ for y we get

$$x * (x * y) = (x * (x * y)) * (x * (x * (x * y))) = (x * (x * y)) * (x * y),$$

thus (e) holds.

(e) \Rightarrow (f). Right $*$ multiplying both sides of (e) by $y * x$, we have

$$(x * (x * y)) * (y * x) = ((x * (x * y)) * (x * y)) * (y * x)$$

$$\leq (y * (x * y)) * (y * x), \text{ by BCI-1.}$$

$$= (y * (y * x)) * (x * y), \text{ by Theorem (1.1.11).}$$

By symmetry, we obtain the converse inequality. Thus (f) holds.

$$(x * (x * y)) * (y * x) = (y * (y * x)) * (x * y).$$

(f) \Rightarrow (b). If we substitute $x * y$ for y in (f), then we obtain

$$x * y = (x * (x * (x * y))) * 0$$

$$= (x * (x * (x * y))) * ((x * y) * x), \text{ by}$$

$$= ((x * y) * ((x * y) * x)) * (x * (x * y)) \text{ by (f) and } x * y = y.$$

$$= (x * y) * (x * (x * y)), \text{ by}$$

$$= (x * (x * (x * y))) * y, \text{ by Theorem (1.1.11).}$$

$$= (x * y) * y, \text{ which is (b).}$$

(b) \Rightarrow (a). Suppose (b) holds. Then

$$((x * z) * (y * z)) * ((x * y) * z)$$

$$= (((x * z) * z) * (y * z)) * ((x * y) * z), \text{ by Theorem (1.1.11).}$$

$$\leq ((x * z) * y) * ((x * y) * z), \text{ by BCI-1.}$$

$$= ((x * y) * z) * ((x * y) * z), \text{ by Theorem (1.1.11).}$$

$$= 0, \text{ thus } (x * z) * (y * z) \leq (x * y) * z.$$

The converse inequality is clear, and (a) holds. This finishes the proof of the theorem. ■
The identity (f) motivates us to characterize positive implicative BCK-algebra by a set of identities.

THEOREM 1.4.4.

An algebra $(X; *, 0)$ of type $(2, 0)$ is a positive implicative BCK-algebra if and only if it satisfies BCI-1, BCK-5 and

$$(f) (x * (x * y)) * (y * x) = (y * (y * x)) * (x * y),$$

$$(g) x * 0 = x.$$

Proof.

Necessity being obvious, we only give the proof of the part " if " as follows. By BCK-5 and (g), we obtain $x * (0 * y) = x * 0 = x$, which in Theorem (1.1.15(a)).

If $x * y = 0$ and $y * x = 0$, then (f) and (g) give

$$\begin{aligned} x &= (x * 0) * 0 = (x * (x * y)) * (y * x) \\ &= (y * (y * x)) * (x * y), \text{ by (f).} \\ &= (y * 0) * 0 \\ &= y, \text{ hence BCI-4 holds.} \end{aligned}$$

By Theorem (1.1.15), $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra. Since it satisfies (f), using Theorem (1.4.3) we know that X is also positive implicative, proving the theorem. ■

THEOREM 1.4.5.

Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCK-algebra. Then the following conditions are equivalent:

- (a) X is positive implicative,
- (b) $(x * y) * z = 0$ implies $(x * z) * (y * z) = 0$,
- (c) $(x * y) * y = 0$ implies $x * y = 0$.

Proof.

(a) \Rightarrow (b) is trivial.

(b) \Rightarrow (c). If $(x * y) * y = 0$, then (b) gives $x * y = (x * y) * (y * y) = 0$ (by $z=y$). This says that (c) holds.

(c) \Rightarrow (a) Denote $u = (x * y) * y$. Then we gives
 $((x * u) * y) * y = ((x * y) * y) * u$, Theorem (1.1.11),
 $= ((x * y) * y) * ((x * y) * y) = 0$.

By (c) we have $(x * u) * y = 0 \Rightarrow (x * y) * u = 0$, Theorem (1.1.11), *that is* $(x * y) * ((x * y) * y) = 0$. Since $((x * y) * y) * (x * y) = 0$ holds in any BCK-algebra by BCK-5, we have by BCI-4 $x * y = (x * y) * y$, i.e. X is positive implicative. Hence (a) holds. The proof is complete. ■

THEOREM 1.4.6.

The Iséki's extension of a positive implicative BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is still positive implicative.

Proof.

Let $e \notin X$ and denote $\bar{X} = X \cup \{e\}$. Let $'$ be defined as in Theorem (1.3.9). Then for all x in X ,

$$(e *' x) *' x = e *' x, (x *' e) *' e = 0 *' e = 0 = x *' e, (e *' e) *' e = 0 *' e = 0 = e *' e.$$

Since X is positive implicative, for x, y in X we have $x * y = (x * y) * y$. The above results show that $(\bar{X}; *', 0)$ is positive implicative. This completes the proof.

EXAMPLE 1.4.7.

Let $X = \{0, a, b, 1\}$ and $*$ on X be given by the table:

*	0	a	b	1
0	0	0	0	0
a	a	0	a	0
b	b	b	0	0
1	1	1	1	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a positive implicative BCK-algebra .

EXAMPLE 1.4.8.

Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, n\}$ with the natural order and $*$ be defined as follows

$x * y = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x \leq y, \\ x & \text{if } y < x. \end{cases}$ Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a bounded positive implicative BCK-algebra and $(X; \leq)$ is a totally ordered set where \leq is the BCK-order.

CHAPTER ONE

SECTION FIVE

1.5. Commutative BCK-algebras

In 1975, S. Tanaka introduced and investigated a new class of BCK-algebras, called commutative BCK-algebras.

DEFINITION 1.5.1.

A BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is said to be **commutative** if it satisfies for all $x, y \in X$, $x * (x * y) = y * (y * x)$, i.e., $x \wedge y = y \wedge x$.

From the symmetry of x and y in the above equality and BCI-4 we have the following theorem.

THEOREM 1.5.2. For a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, the following are equivalent:

- (a) X is commutative,
- (b) $x * (x * y) \leq y * (y * x)$,
- (c) $(x * (x * y)) * (y * (y * x)) = 0$.

Proof. H.W.

Obviously, any subalgebra of a commutative BCK-algebra is still commutative.

EXAMPLE 1.5.3. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ in which $*$ is given by the table

*	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0	0
2	2	1	0	0	0
3	3	1	1	0	0
4	4	3	2	1	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra, but it is not commutative.

EXAMPLE 1.5.4. Let $X = \cup_{i=1}^m A_i$, where $A_i \cap A_j = \{0\}$ ($i \neq j$) and A_i consists of

$0 = a_{i0} < a_{i1} < \dots < a_{ij} < \dots$. For $x, y \in X$, we define $x * y = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x \leq y, \\ a_{ik-1} & \text{if } y < x \text{ and } x = a_{ik}, y = a_{i1} \\ x & \text{otherwise,} \end{cases}$ of course \leq and $<$ are the order on A_i . Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a commutative BCK-algebra.

EXAMPLE 1.5.5. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, n, a, b, \dots, c\}$ and suppose the order is defined as follows: $0 < 1 < 2 < \dots < b, n < a, b, \dots, c$, and every pair of a, b, c is incomparable.

Denote $N = \{0, 1, 2, \dots, n\}$ and $A = \{a, b, \dots, c\}$. In X the binary operation $(*)$ is given by

$$x * y = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{if } x \leq y, \\ x - y & \text{if } y < x \text{ and } x \in N, \\ n + 1 - y & \text{if } y < x, y \neq 0, x \in A \text{ and } y \in N, \\ x & \text{if } y = 0 \text{ and } x \in A, \\ 1 & \text{if } x \neq y \text{ and } x, y \in A \end{cases}$$

then $(X; *, 0)$ is commutative BCK-algebra.

EXAMPLE 1.5.6. Suppose $|X| \geq 2$ and $0 \in X$. if $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra, then the Iséki's extension is not commutative.

DEFINITION 1.5.7.

A partially ordered set (L, \leq) is said to be a lower semilattice if every pair of elements in L has a greatest lower bound (meet); it is called to be an upper semilattice if every pair of elements in L as a least upper bound (join); the operations join and meet are denoted by \vee and \wedge respectively. If (L, \leq) is both an upper and a lower semilattice, then it is called to be a lattice. A lattice is said to be distributive if it satisfies either of the distributive laws:

- (D₁) $x \wedge (y \vee z) = (x \wedge y) \vee (x \wedge z)$,
- (D₂) $x \vee (y \wedge z) = (x \vee y) \wedge (x \vee z)$.

DEFINITION 1.5.8.

1- A lattice (L, \leq) is said to be **bounded** if there are elements 0 and e in L such that for any x in L , $0 \leq x \leq e$, which is equivalent to $x \wedge 0 = 0$ and $x \vee e = e$. Two elements a, b of a bounded lattice are complements if $a \vee b = e$ and $a \wedge b = 0$. In this case each of a, b is the complement of the other .

2- A **complemented lattice** is a bounded lattice in which every element has a complement.

THEOREM 1.5.9. A BCK-algebra $(X ; *, 0)$ is commutative if and only if, it is a lower semilattice with respect to BCK-order \leq .

Proof.

Suppose $(X ; *, 0)$ is a commutative BCK-algebra. By BCI-2' and Theorem (1.1.12(d)), we know that $x \wedge y \leq x, y$.

Let z be any element of X such that $z < x, y$. Then $z * x = z * y = 0$, so $z = z * 0 = z * (z * x) = x * (x * z)$, by commutative. And $z = z * 0 = z * (z * y) = y * (y * z)$, by commutative. By the same reason we have $z = y * (y * z)$, hence

$$z = x * (x * z) = x * (x * (y * (y * z))) \leq x * (x * y) = x \wedge y.$$

This says that for all x, y in X , $x \wedge y$ is the greatest lower bound, and so (X, \leq) is a lower semilattice.

Conversely, if $(X; *, 0)$ is a lower semilattice, then for any $x, y \in X$, $x \wedge y$ is the greatest lower bound of x and y . Since $y \wedge x$ is a common lower bound of x and y , it follows that $y \wedge x \leq x \wedge y$. Then $x * (x * y) \leq y * (y * x)$. By Theorem (1.5.2), X is commutative, completing the proof.

DEFINITION 1.5.10.

For a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, the set $A(x) = \{y \in X : y \leq x\}$ is an **initial section of an element x** .

THEOREM 1.5.11.

A BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is commutative if and only if, $A(x) \cap A(y) = A(x \wedge y)$, for all x, y of X .

Proof.

Let X be a commutative BCK-algebra. If $z \in A(x) \cap A(y)$, then $z \in A(x)$ and $z \in A(y)$, implies that $z \leq x, y$. Hence $z \leq x \wedge y$, which implies $z \in A(x \wedge y)$. Thus $A(x) \cap A(y) \subseteq A(x \wedge y)$.

If $z \in A(x \wedge y)$, then $z \leq x \wedge y$, implies that $z \leq x, y$. Hence, $z \in A(x)$ and $z \in A(y)$, which implies $z \in A(x) \cap A(y)$. Thus $A(z \wedge y) \subseteq A(x) \cap A(y)$. Hence $A(x) \cap A(x) = A(x \wedge y)$.

Conversely, if we assume that $A(x) \cap A(y) = A(x \wedge y)$, then $A(x \wedge y) = A(x) \cap A(y) = A(y) \cap A(x) = A(y \wedge x)$. Hence $x \wedge y \in A(y \wedge x)$. Therefore $x \wedge y \leq y \wedge x$. By Theorem (1.5.2(b)), X is commutative. ■

THEOREM 1.5.12. A BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is commutative if and only if, $x * (x * y) = y * (y * (x * (x * y)))$, for all $x, y \in X$.

Proof.

(\Rightarrow) **H.W.**

(\Leftarrow) holds. The proof is complete. ■

Next, we discuss bounded commutative BCK-algebras, in such algebras denote $x \vee y = (x^* \wedge y^*)^*$.

THEOREM 1.5.13. For a bounded commutative BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, we have for all $x, y \in X$

- (a) $x^{**} = x$,
- (b) $x^* \vee y^* = (x \wedge y)^*$, $x^* \wedge y^* = (x \vee y)^*$,
- (c) $x^* * y^* = y * x$.

Proof. Trivial.

THEOREM 1.5.14.

Any bounded commutative BCK-algebra X with respect to the BCK-order \leq is a lattice.

Proof.

Since $x^* \wedge y^* \leq x^*, y^*$, from Theorem (1.1.11(a)) we have $x = x^{**} \leq (x^* \wedge y^*)^* = x \vee y$ and $y = y^{**} \leq (x^* \wedge y^*)^* = x \vee y$.

This shows that $x \vee y$ is a common upper bound of x and y .

Next, if $x, y \leq z$, then $z^* \leq x^*, y^*$. By Theorem (1.5.9) we obtain $z^* \leq x^* \wedge y^*$, $(x^* \wedge y^*)^* \leq z^{**}$ and $x \vee y \leq z$. Hence $x \vee y$ is a least upper bound of x and y . Therefore $(X; \leq)$ is an upper semilattice, and so a lattice in view of Theorem (1.5.9). ■

It is clear that for a bounded commutative BCK-algebra, the operations \vee and \wedge satisfy commutative laws, associative laws, idempotent laws and absorption laws.

THEOREM 1.5.15.

Suppose $(X ; * , 0)$ is a bounded commutative BCK-algebra. If there exists a complement of each element of X , then it is unique.

Proof.

Suppose y and y' are complements of x , namely, $x \wedge y = x \wedge y' = 0$ and $x \vee y = x \vee y' = e$. Then $0 = x \wedge y = y * (y * x)$. Hence $y \leq y * x \leq y$, which implies $y = y * x$.

Similarly, $y' = y' * x$. Thus

$$\begin{aligned} y * y' &= (y * x) * (y' * x) = (x^* * y^*) * (x^* * y'^*), \text{ by Theorem (1.5.13(c)).} \\ &= (x^* * (x^* * y'^*)) * y^*, \text{ by Theorem (1.1.12).} \\ &= (y'^* \wedge x^*) * y^*, \text{ by definite of } \wedge . \\ &= (x \vee y')^* * y^*, \text{ by Theorem (1.5.13(b)).} \\ &= y^{**} * (x \vee y'), \text{ by Theorem (1.1.12).} \\ &= y * (x \vee y'), \text{ by Theorem (1.5.13(a)).} \\ &= y * e = 0, \text{ by definition of } \vee . \end{aligned}$$

Likewise, we have $y' * y = 0$. By BCI-4 we have $y = y'$, which says that complements of x are unique. ■

We should note that for a bounded commutative BCK-algebra element need not have any complement .

EXAMPLE 1.5.16. Let $X = \{0, a, b, c, d, 1\}$ in which $*$ is given by:

*	0	a	b	c	d	1
0	0	0	0	0	0	0
a	a	0	a	a	0	0
b	b	b	0	0	0	0
c	c	c	b	0	b	0
d	d	b	a	a	0	0
1	1	c	d	a	b	0

Then $(X ; * , 0)$ is a BCK-algebra with unit 1. The element b has no any complement.

THEOREM 1.5.17.

In a bounded commutative BCK-algebra $(X ; * , 0)$ the following conditions are equivalent:

- (a) $x = x * (y * x)$,
- (b) $x * y = (x * y) * y$,
- (c) $(x * z) * (y * z) = (x * y) * z$,
- (d) $x \wedge x^* = 0$,
- (e) $x \vee x^* = e$,
- (f) $x = x * x^*$,
- (g) $x^* = x^* * x$,
- (h) $x * (x * y^*) = x * y, i. e., y^* \wedge x = x * y$,
- (i) $x * (x * y) = x * y^*, i. e., y \wedge x = x * y^*$,
- (j) $(x * (y * z)) * (x * y) \leq x * z^*$.

Proof.

(a) \Rightarrow (b). Substituting $x * y$ for x in(a) and noticing $y = y * (x * y)$, we obtain $x * y = (x * y) * (y * (x * y)) = (x * y) * y$, (b) holds.

(b) \Rightarrow (c). See Theorem (1.4.2).

(c) \Rightarrow (d). Suppose(c) holds. Then

$$\begin{aligned} x \wedge x^* &= x^* \wedge x = x * (x * x^*) = x^{**} * (x * x^*) \\ &= (e * x^*) * (x * x^*) = (e * x) * x^* = x^* * x^* = 0, \text{ (d) holds.} \end{aligned}$$

(d) \Rightarrow (e). $x \vee x^* = (x \vee x^*)^{**} = (x^* \wedge x^{**})^* = 0^* = e$. Thus (e) is true.

(e) \Rightarrow (f). Since $x * (x * x^*) = x \wedge x^* = (x \wedge x^*)^{**} = (x^* \vee x^{**})^* = e^* = 0$, it follows $x \leq x * x^*$. The inverse inequality is clear. Hence $x = x * x^*$, which is(f).

(f) \Rightarrow (g). Replacing x by x^* in(f) we have $x^* = x^* * x^{**} = x^* * z$, (g) holds.

(g) \Rightarrow (h) $y^* = y^* * y$ follows from(g).

Hence $x * (x * y^*) = y^* * (y^* * x) = (y^* * y) * (y^* * x) \leq x * y$.

Noticing $x \leq e$, we get $x * y^* \leq e * y^* = y^{**} = y$. So $x * y \leq x * (x * y^*)$.

Thus $x * y = x * (x * y^*)$, proving (h).

(h) \Rightarrow (i). Substituting y^* for y in(h) we obtain

$$x * (x * y) = x * (x * y^{**}) = x * y^*, \text{ which is (i).}$$

(i) \Rightarrow (j). Since $(x * (y * z)) * (x * y) = (x * (x * y)) * (y * z) = (x * y^*) * (y * z)$ [by(i)]

$$= (x * y^*) * (z^* * y^*) \leq x * z^*, \text{ (j) holds.}$$

(j) \Rightarrow (a). Noticing $y \leq e$, we obtain $y * x \leq e * x = x^*$, and $x * x^* \leq x * (y * x)$. If (j) holds, then $x = (x * 0) * 0 = (x * (x * x)) * (x * x) \leq x * x^* \leq x * (y * x)$, and so $x \leq x * (y * x)$. The inverse inequality holds for any BCK-algebra Therefore, $x = x * (y * x)$.(a) holds.

This completes the proof of the Theorem. ■

The equivalence of (a), (b) and(c) does not require to be bounded for X (see the next section)

THEOREM 1.5.18.

An algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is a commutative BCK-algebra if and only if it satisfies the following

(a) $x * (x * y) = y * (y * x)$,

(b) $(x * y) * z = (x * z) * y$,

(c) $x * x = 0$,

(d) $x * 0 = x$.

Proof.

It suffices to verify the part "if". Using the first three conditions, we obtain

$$(x * (x * y)) * y = (x * y) * (x * y) = 0, \text{ which is BCI-2.}$$

If $x * y = y * x = 0$ then by (a) and (d), $x = x * 0 = x * (x * y) = y * (y * x) = y * 0 = y$, namely, BCI-4 holds.

$$\text{(a) and(b) give } (x * y) * (x * z) = (x * (x * z)) * y = (z * (z * x)) * y = (z * y) * (z * x),$$

$$\text{hence } (x * y) * (x * z) = (z * y) * (z * x) \dots(1).$$

In the above equality, let $x = y$ and $z = 0$, then by(c) we obtain

$$0 * x = (x * x) * (x * 0) = (0 * x) * (0 * x) = 0, \text{ BCK-5 follows.}$$

By (1), (d) and BCK-5 we have

$$\begin{aligned} ((x * y) * (x * z)) * (z * y) &= ((z * y) * (z * x)) * ((z * y) * 0) \\ &= (0 * (z * x)) * (0 * (z * y)) = 0 * 0 = 0, \text{ which is BCI-1.} \end{aligned}$$

Putting the above results together we have proved that $(X; *, 0)$ is a commutative BCK-algebra. ■

CHAPTER ONE

SECTION SIX

1.6. Implicative BCK-algebras

DEFINITION 1.6.1. A BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is called **implicative** if for all $x, y \in X$,
 $x = x * (y * x)$.

EXAMPLE 1.6.2.

1- Let $X = \{0, e\}$ in which $*$ is given by putting $e * 0 = e$ and $0 * 0 = 0 * e = e * e = 0$. Then $(X; *, 0)$ is an implicative BCK-algebra. For convenience of further discussions this algebra is denoted by $\mathbf{2}$.

2- The Example (1.1.9) in the previous section is not implicative as $d * (c * d) = d * b = a \neq d$.

3- The Example (1.1.21) is an implicative BCK-algebra.

The next theorem exhibits the relationship among implicativity, commutativity and positive implicativity.

THEOREM 1.6.3.

A BCK-algebra is implicative if and only if it is both commutative and positive implicative.

Proof.

(\Rightarrow) Suppose X is implicative. Then $x * y = (x * y) * (y * (x * y)) = (x * y) * y$.

Hence X is positive implicative. By implicativity and BCK-1', the following hold
 $x * (x * y) = (x * (y * x)) * (x * y) \leq y * (y * x)$.

Therefore X is commutative.

(\Leftarrow) The necessity follows. For the sufficiency we note that

$$\begin{aligned} x * (x * (y * x)) &= (y * x) * ((y * x) * x), \text{ by commutativity.} \\ &= ((y * x) * x) * ((y * x) * x), \text{ by positive implicativity.} \\ &= 0, \text{ by BCI-3.} \end{aligned}$$

On the other hand, $(x * (y * x)) * x = 0$ by Theorem (1.1.12 (d)). By BCI-4,
 $x = x * (y * x)$. Therefore X is implicative. The proof is complete. ■

In view of the above theorem, for a bounded implicative BCK-algebra, (b) - (j) in Theorem (1.5.18) hold.

Proposition 1.6.4. In a bounded implicative BCK-algebra X , the following hold:

- (a) $x \vee y = y \vee x = (x^* * y)^* = (y^* * x)^*$,
- (b) $(x \vee y) * x \leq y$,
- (c) $x * y \leq z$ implies $x \leq y \vee z$, i.e., $(x * y) * z = 0$ implies $x * (y \vee z) = 0$.

Proof.

By Theorem (1.5.18(i)), $x \vee y = (x^* \wedge y^*)^* = (x^* * y^{**})^* = (x^* * y)^* = (y^* * x)^*$, which is (a).

By (a) we obtain $(x \vee y) * x = (x^* * y)^* * x = x^* * (x^* * y) \leq y$, so (b) holds.

If $x * y \leq z$, by (a), we have

$$\begin{aligned} x * (y \vee z) &= x * (y^* * z)^* = x^{**} * (y^* * z)^* = (y^* * z)^{**} * x^* = (y^* * z) * x^* \text{ by...} \\ &= (x^{**} * y) * z = (x * y) * z = 0, \text{ that is, } x \leq y \vee z. \text{ (c) follows. The proof is} \end{aligned}$$

complete. ■

THEOREM 1.6.5.

A bounded implicative BCK-algebra $(X ; * ,0)$ is distributive lattice and each element of X have a unique complement x^* .

Proof.

By Theorem (1.5.18(e) and(f)), for each $x \in X$, x^* is a complement of X . Then, by Theorem (1.5.17), we know that each x of X have a unique complement.

In order to prove the remainder, we observe

$$\begin{aligned} ((x \vee y) \wedge z) * (x \wedge z) &= ((x \vee y) * z^*) * (x * z^*) , \text{ by Theorem (1.5.18(i)).} \\ &= ((x \vee y) * x) * z^* , \text{ by positive implicativity .} \\ &\leq y * z^* , \text{ by Proposition (1.6.4(b)).} \\ &= y \wedge z . \text{ by Theorem (1.5.18(i)).} \end{aligned}$$

Consequently, $(x \vee y) \wedge z \leq (x \wedge z) \vee (y \wedge z)$ by Proposition (1.6.4(c)). The inverse inequality is trivial. Thus we get $(x \vee y) \wedge z = (x \wedge z) \vee (y \wedge z)$.

This shows that $(X ; \vee , \wedge)$ is a distributive lattice by means of Theorem (1.5.16). This completes the proof. ■

As is well-known, a complemented distributive lattice is a Boolean algebra. Hence the above theorem may be reformulated as follows.

THEOREM 1.6.6.

Any bounded implicative BCK-algebra is a Boolean algebra.

Proof. H.W.

THEOREM 1.6.7.

Let $(X ; * ,0)$ be a nontrivial BCK-algebra. Then the Iséki's extension of it is not implicative.

Proof.

Assume $x \in X$ and $x \neq 0$. Then $x * (e * x) = x * e = 0 \neq x$, completing the proof. ■

Finally, we give some equivalent conditions of implicativity.

THEOREM 1.6.8. Suppose $(X ; * ,0)$ is a BCK-algebra. Then the following are equivalent:

- (a) X is implicative,
- (b) $y * (y * x) = (x * (x * y)) * (x * y)$,
- (c) $y * (y * x) = (y * (y * x)) * (x * y)$,
- (d) $(x * (x * y)) * (x * y) = (y * (y * x)) * (y * x)$.

Proof.

(a) \Rightarrow (b). Assume(a). Then X is both positive implicative and commutative. Hence by positive implicativity we have $(x * (x * y)) * (x * y) = x * (x * y)$. By commutativity the following holds

$$x * (x * y) = y * (y * x) . \text{Combining the above results(b) follows.}$$

(b) \Rightarrow (c). From (b) it follows that $y * (y * x) = (x * (x * y)) * (x * y) \leq x * (x * y)$, so $x * (x * y) = y * (y * x)$. Again applying (b) we obtain

$$x * (x * y) = y * (y * x) = (x * (x * y)) * (x * y) = (y * (y * x)) * (x * y) , \text{ Which is (c) .}$$

(c) \Rightarrow (d) By the similar to (b) \Rightarrow (c) we obtain $x * (x * y) = y * (y * x)$.

$$\begin{aligned} \text{Thus } (x * (x * y)) * (x * y) &= (y * (y * x)) * (x * y) \\ &= x * (x * y) = y * (y * x) \\ &= (x * (x * y)) * (y * x) \\ &= (y * (y * x)) * (y * x) , \text{ and hence(d) holds.} \end{aligned}$$

(d) \Rightarrow (a). Replacing y by $x * y$ in(d) we obtain

$$\begin{aligned}
x * y &= ((x * y) * 0) * 0 = ((x * y) * ((x * y) * x)) * ((x * y) * x) \\
&= (x * (x * (x * y))) * (x * (x * y)) \\
&= (x * y) * (x * (x * y)) \\
&= (x * (x * (x * y))) * y = (x * y) * y. \text{ this says that } X \text{ is positive implicative.}
\end{aligned}$$

Combining(d) we have

$x * (x * y) = (x * (x * y)) * (x * y) = (y * (y * x)) * (y * x) = y * (y * x)$,
at is, X is also commutative. By virtue of Theorem (1.6.3), X is implicative and (a) holds. The proof is complete. ■

CHAPTER ONE

SECTION SEVEN

1.7. BCK-algebras with condition (S)

BCK-algebras with condition (S) were introduced by K. Iséki and died extensively by several authors.

DEFINITION 1.7.1. Given a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ and given elements $a, b \in X$, we define $A(a, b) = \{x \in X : x * a \leq b\}$.

Obviously, $0, a$ and b are in $A(a, b)$. If for all $x, y \in X$, $A(x, y)$ has a greatest element, written $x \circ y$, then the BCK-algebra is called to be **with condition (S)**.

From the definition it is easy to see that $a \leq a \circ b$, $b \leq a \circ b$ and $a \circ 0 = 0 \circ a = a$.

EXAMPLE 1.7.2. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$, $*$ be given by the table .

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0
2	2	2	0	0
3	3	2	1	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is BCK-algebra with condition (S), but it is neither positive implicative nor commutative. $A(1, 2) = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$, since $0 * 1 \leq 2, \Rightarrow (0 * 1) * 2 = 0 * 2 = 0$,
 $1 * 1 \leq 2, \Rightarrow (1 * 1) * 2 = 0 * 2 = 0$, $2 * 1 \leq 2, \Rightarrow (2 * 1) * 2 = 2 * 2 = 0$, and
 $3 * 1 \leq 2, \Rightarrow (3 * 1) * 2 = 3 * 2 = 0$.

EXAMPLE 1.7.3. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ in which $*$ is defined as follows :

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0
2	2	2	0	0
3	3	3	3	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra with condition (S). We should note that this BCK-algebra is positive implicative, but not commutative.

EXAMPLE 1.7.4. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ and the operation $*$ is as follows :

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	1
2	2	2	0	2
3	3	3	3	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a positive implicative BCK-algebra, but not with condition (S), in fact, $A(1,3) = \{0, 1, 3\}$ has no any greatest element.

Note that $2 * 1 \not\leq 3$, since $(2 * 1) * 3 = 2 * 3 = 2 \neq 0$.

LEMMA 1.7.5. If a, b are any fixed elements of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. If $a \circ b$ exists, then so $b \circ a$, exists and $a \circ b = b \circ a$.

Proof. Since $x * a \leq b$ is equivalent to $x * b \leq a$, therefore $A(a, b) = A(b, a)$, which implies $a \circ b = b \circ a$. ■

LEMMA 1.7.6. If $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra with condition (S) and $a, b, c \in X$, then $(a \circ b) \circ c = a \circ (b \circ c)$.

Proof. By the definition of the operation \circ we have $((a \circ b) \circ c) * c \leq a \circ b$ and so $((a \circ b) \circ c) * b \leq a$, hence $((a \circ b) \circ c) * b \leq a \circ c$, and $(a \circ b) \circ c \leq (a \circ c) \circ b$.

By symmetry, we have the inverse inequality. Thus $(a \circ b) \circ c = (a \circ c) \circ b$. Cabling Lemma (1.7.5), we have $(a \circ b) \circ c = (b \circ a) \circ c = (b \circ c) \circ a = a \circ (b \circ c)$. ■

DEFINITION 1.7.7.

By a semigroup (S, \cdot) , we will mean a nonempty set S on which a binary operation \cdot is defined and satisfies for $a, b, c \in S$, $(a \cdot b) \cdot c = a \cdot (b \cdot c)$.

Using the notion of semigroups, the above results may be reformulated as follows

THEOREM 1.7.8. A BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ with condition (S) is a semigroup respect to the operation \circ and 0 is zero element.

Proof. H.W.

COROLLARY 1.7.9. If $(X; *, 0)$ is a bounded BCK-algebra with condition (S), then for all $x \in X$, the following hold $x \circ e = e \circ x = e$ and $x \circ x^* = e$.

Proof. Since $u * x \leq e$, for all $u \in X$, $x \circ e = e$. And $u * x \leq e * x$ implies $x \circ (e * x) = e$, that is to say $x \circ x^* = e$. ■

THEOREM 1.7.9. A BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ with condition (S) is a commutative ordered semigroup with zero 0.

Proof. By virtue of Theorem (1.7.8), it suffices to show that the operation \circ is order preserving relative to the BCK-ordering \leq . To do this we suppose $x \leq y$ then $(x \circ z) * y \leq (x \circ z) * x \leq z$, so $x \circ z \leq y \circ z$. ■

THEOREM 1.7.10. Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCK-algebra with condition (S). Then

- (a) $(x * y) * z = x * (y \circ z)$,
- (b) $x * y \leq (x * z) \circ (z * y)$,
- (c) $(x \circ z) * (y \circ z) \leq x * y \leq x \circ y$.

Proof. H.W.

THEOREM 1.7.11. Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCK-algebra. If there is a binary operation \vee such that for all $x, y, z \in X$, $(x * y) * z = x * (y \vee z)$, then X is with condition (S) and \vee is exactly the operation \circ .

THEOREM 1.7.12. Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCK- algebra with condition (S). Then the least element x satisfying $a \leq b \circ x$, for given $a, b \in X$ is $a * b$.

THEOREM 1.7.13. Any non-trivial BCK-algebra X with condition(S) is never a group on \circ .

Proof.

Let a' be the inverse of a such that $(a' \neq 0)$ in X . Then $a \circ a' = 0$ and $0 \neq a \leq a \circ a' = 0$, a contradiction. Hence X is not a group on \circ .

In the following we will discuss positive implicative (resp. commutative, implicative) BCK-algebra with condition (S).

THEOREM 1.7.14. Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCK-algebra with condition(S). Then the following are equivalent:

- (a) X is positive implicative,
- (b) $x \leq y$ implies $x \circ y = y$,
- (c) $x \circ x = x$,
- (d) $(x \circ y) * z = (x * z) \circ (y * z)$,
- (e) $x \circ y = \text{lub} \{x, y\}$
- (f) $x \circ y = x \circ (y * x)$.

THEOREM 1.7.15. If $(X; *, 0)$ is a positive implicative BCK-algebra with condition (S) and bounded. Then each element a of X has a right implement a^* , that is, $a \circ a^* = e$ and $a \wedge a^* = 0$.

Proof From $b \leq e$ it follows that $b * a \leq e * a = a^*$, so $b \leq a \circ a^*$.

If we assume $b = e$, then $e \leq a \circ a^*$. The inverse inequality is obvious, and so $a \circ a^* = e$.

On the other hand, by positive implicatively of X we have

$$a \wedge a^* = a^* * (a^* * a) = a^* * ((e * a) * a) = a^* * (e * a) = a^* * a^* = 0. \blacksquare$$

CHAPTER ONE

SECTION EIGHT

1.8. The union of two BCK-algebras

DEFINITION 1.8.1.

Let $(X_1; *_1, 0)$ and $(X_2; *_2, 0)$ be two BCK-algebras and $X_1 \cap X_2 = \{0\}$. Suppose $X = X_1 \cup X_2$, define $*$ on X as $(a, b) * (c, d) = (a *_1 c, b *_2 d)$, where $a, c \in X_1$ and $b, d \in X_2$. And denoted by $X = X_1 \oplus X_2$ which is called **The union $X = X_1 \oplus X_2$** .

THEOREM 1.8.2. Let $(X_1; *_1, 0)$ and $(X_2; *_2, 0)$ be two BCK-algebras. The union $(X_1 \oplus X_2; *, (0,0))$ is a BCK-algebra.

Proof. H.W.

THEOREM 1.8.3. The union $X = X_1 \oplus X_2$ with $|X_1| \geq 2$ and $|X_2| \geq 2$ does not satisfy the condition (S).

Proof. Suppose a and b are non-zero elements in X and $a \in X_1, b \in X_2$. Then $a, b \in A(a, b)$, but there is no a non-zero c such that $a \leq c$ and $b \leq c$. This means that X does not satisfy the condition (S). The proof is complete. ■

Likewise, for an indexed family of BCK-algebras $\{X_i : i \in \Lambda\}$, we may define the union algebra $X = \bigoplus \{X_i : i \in \Lambda\}$, and the previous facts also hold.

LEMMA 1.8.4. Let x and y be any elements of a BCK-algebra X . If $A(x) \cap A(y) = \{0\}$, then $x * y = x$ and $y * x = y$.

Proof. Note that $x * (x * y) \leq x, y$ hold in X . Hence $x * (x * y) \in A(x) \cap A(y)$, which implies $x * (x * y) = 0$, i. e., $x \leq x * y$. The inverse inequality is clear, and so $x = x * y$. By the same way we obtain $y * x = y$ proving the lemma. ■

THEOREM 1.8.5. In the union $\bigoplus \{X_i : i \in \Lambda\}$, $x \in X_i$ implies $A(x) \subseteq X_i$.

Proof. H.W.

THEOREM 1.8.6. Let $\{S_i : i \in \Lambda\}$ be an indexed family of subsets of BCK-algebra X satisfying the following conditions:

- (a) $X = \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} S_i$,
- (b) $S_i \cap S_j = \{0\}$ for any distinct i and j ,
- (c) $x \in S_i$ implies $A(x) \subseteq S_i$ for any $i \in \Lambda$.

Then all S_i are subalgebras of X and X is the union of all BCK-algebras S_i ($i \in \Lambda$).

Proof. Since $x * y \leq x$, it follows that $x * y \in A(x)$, which means that for any $x, y \in S_i$, $x * y \in A(x) \subseteq S_i$. Hence S_i is a subalgebra of X . The conditions (b) and (c) are clearly equivalent to the one that $x \in S_i, y \in S_j$ and $i \neq j$ imply $A(x) \cap A(y) = \{0\}$. Consequently, by Lemma (1.8.4), $x \in S_i$ and $y \in S_j$, for distinct i and j imply $x * y = x$ and $y * x = y$. Hence X is the union of all BCK-algebras S_i ($i \in \Lambda$). This finishes the proof. ■

CHAPTER ONE

SECTION NINE

1.9. Direct product of BCK-algebras

DEFINITION 1.9.1. Let $(X_i; *_{i}, 0)$ ($i \in \Lambda$) be an indexed family of BCK-algebras and let $\prod_{i \in \Lambda} X_i$ be the set of all mappings $f : I \rightarrow \bigcup \{X_i : i \in \Lambda\}$, and $f(i) \in X_i$, for all $i \in \Lambda$. For $f, g \in \prod_{i \in \Lambda} X_i$, we define by $f * g$ by $(f * g)(i) = f(i) * g(i)$ for every $i \in \Lambda$ and 0 by $0(i) = 0_i$. Then $(\prod_{i \in \Lambda} X_i; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra, which is called **the direct product** X_i ($i \in \Lambda$).

THEOREM 1.9.2. Let $(X_i; *_{i}, 0)$ be an indexed family of BCK-algebras. Then we have the following:

- (a) $\prod_{i \in \Lambda} X_i$ is bounded if and only if every X_i is bounded
- (b) $\prod_{i \in \Lambda} X_i$ is commutative if and only if every X_i is commutative
- (c) $\prod_{i \in \Lambda} X_i$ is positive implicative if and only if every X_i is positive implicative,
- (d) $\prod_{i \in \Lambda} X_i$ is implicative if and only if every X_i is implicative,
- (e) $\prod_{i \in \Lambda} X_i$ is with condition (S) if and only if every X_i is with condition (S).

Proof. we only prove (e). The remainder is left to the reader as an exercise.

Let every X_i ($i \in \Lambda$) be with condition (S). For any $f, g \in \prod_{i \in \Lambda} X_i$, we define $f \circ g$ such that $(f \circ g)(i) = f(i) \circ g(i)$ for all $i \in \Lambda$.

For $h \in \prod_{i \in \Lambda} X_i$, if $h * f \leq g$, then $h(i) * f(i) = (h * f)(i) \leq g(i)$ for all $i \in \Lambda$.

From this it follows that $h(i) \leq f(i) \circ g(i)$. This says that $h * f \leq g$ implies $h \leq f \circ g$. his Moreover, for $i \in \Lambda$, we have $((f \circ g) * f)(i) = (f \circ g)(i) * f(i) = (f(i) \circ g(i)) * f(i) \leq g(i)$. This shows $(f \circ g) * f \leq g$. Hence $f \circ g$ is the element of $A(f, g)$. Consequently, $\prod_{i \in \Lambda} X_i$ is with condition (S).

Conversely, suppose $\prod_{i \in \Lambda} X_i$ is with condition (S). For any $x_i, y_i \in X_i$, take $f, g \in$

$$\prod_{i \in \Lambda} X_i \text{ such that } f(i) = \begin{cases} x_i & \text{if } j = i, \\ 0 & \text{if } j \neq i, \end{cases} \text{ and } g(j) = \begin{cases} y_i & \text{if } j = i, \\ 0 & \text{if } j \neq i, \end{cases}$$

Then $(f \circ g)(i) = x_i \circ y_i$. In fact, since $(f \circ g) * f \leq g$,
 $(f \circ g)(i) * x_i = (f \circ g)(i) * f(i) = ((f \circ g) * f)(i) \leq g(i) = y_i$.

On the other hand, if $z_i * x_i \leq y_i$ and h is such that $h(j) = \begin{cases} z_i & \text{if } j = i, \\ 0_j & \text{if } j \neq i, \end{cases}$

$$\text{Then } (h * f)(j) = \begin{cases} z_i * x_i & \text{if } j = i, \\ 0_j & \text{if } j \neq i, \end{cases}$$

Hence $h * f \leq g$, and $h \leq f \circ g$. In particular, $z(i) = h(i) \leq (f \circ g)(i)$. This shows that $z_i * x_i \leq y_i$ implies $z_i \leq (f \circ g)(i)$.

Therefore, $(f \circ g)(i) = x_i \circ y_i$. This finishes the proof. ■

In the following we discuss the close relationship between union algebras and direct products.

DEFINITION 1.9.3. If $(X_1; *_1, 0_1)$ and $(X_2; *_2, 0_2)$ are any two BCK-algebras, then we call the mapping $f : X_1 \rightarrow X_2$ to be a homomorphism whenever for any $x, y \in X_1$, we have

$$f(x *_1 y) = f(x) *_2 f(y).$$

If f is also onto, then f is said to be an epimorphism.

If a homomorphism is both onto and one to one, then we call it to be an isomorphism in his case, we say X_1 is isomorphic to X_2 , written $X_1 \cong X_2$.

Obviously, an isomorphic relation is an equivalent one.

Given a nonempty indexed family $\{X_i : i \in \Lambda\}$, we consider the direct product $\prod_{i \in \Lambda} X_i$. For

$$\text{any fixed } i \in \Lambda, \text{ assume } a_i \in \prod_{i \in \Lambda} X_i \text{ such that } a_i(j) = \begin{cases} a \in X_i & \text{if } j = i, \\ 0_i & \text{if } j \neq i, \end{cases}$$

Then $\tilde{X}_i = \{a_i : a_i \in X_i\}$ is a subalgebra of $\prod_{i \in \Lambda} X_i$ and isomorphic to X_i .

If $i \neq j$, then $a_i * a_j = a_i$ and $\tilde{X}_i \cap \tilde{X}_j = \{0\}$. Hence $\cup_{i \in \Lambda} \tilde{X}_i = \bigoplus_{i \in \Lambda} \tilde{X}_i$. So $\cup_{i \in \Lambda} X_i$ is a subalgebra of $\prod_{i \in \Lambda} X_i$, and for any projection map p_j , we have $p_j(\cup_{i \in \Lambda} \tilde{X}_i) = X_j$. Since $\cup_{i \in \Lambda} \tilde{X}_i$ is isomorphic to $\bigoplus_{i \in \Lambda} X_i$. ■

We have proved the following

THEOREM 1.9.4. $\bigoplus_{i \in \Lambda} X_i$ is a subalgebra of $\prod_{i \in \Lambda} X_i$ up to isomorphism.

Proof: H.W.

CHAPTER TWO

SECTION ONE

2.1. Ideals of BCK-algebras

The notion of ideals in BCK-algebras was introduced by K. Iséki in 1975. The ideal theory plays a fundamental role for the general development of BCK-algebras. The concepts of ideals, quotient algebras, and homomorphisms are all closely related. These will be the subject of this and next chapters.

DEFINITION 2.1.1. Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCK-algebra and let I be a nonempty subset of X .

Then I is called to be **an ideal of X** if, for all $x, y \in X$,

- (i) $0 \in I$,
- (ii) $x * y \in I$ and $y \in I$ imply $x \in I$.

$\{0\}$ and X are two ideals of X , we will call X and $\{0\}$ are **trivial** ideals. An ideal I is **proper** if $I \neq X, I \neq \{0\}$.

EXAMPLE 2.1.2. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2\}$ in which $*$ is given by the table:

*	0	1	2
0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1
2	2	2	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is an implicative BCK-algebra, and $\{0\}, X, \{0,1\}, \{0,2\}$ are all ideals of X .

EXAMPLE 2.1.2. Let $X = \{0,1, 2, 3\}$ in which $*$ is given by the table

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	3	0
2	2	1	0	0
3	3	2	1	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is an implicative BCK-algebra, it has only two ideals $\{0\}$ and X .

EXAMPLE 2.1.3. Let $(X; *, 0)$ be any BCK-algebra and let \bar{X} be the Iséki's extension of X . Then X is an ideal of \bar{X} .

Proposition 2.1.4. If I is an ideal of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, then I is subalgebra of X .

Proof. since $x * y \in I$ and $y \in I$ implies $x \in I$, put $y=0$, then $x * 0 = x \in I$ and $y \in I$ implies $x * 0 \in I$, thus I is subalgebra of X

Proposition 2.1.5. If I is an ideal of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ and $x \in I$. If $y \leq x$, then $y \in I$.

Proof. since $y \leq x$ implies $y * x = 0 \in I$. Combining $x \in I$ and using (ii), we obtain $y \in I$, proving the theorem. ■

Next, we give an equivalent condition of ideals.

THEOREM 2.1.6. If I is a nonempty subset of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, then I is an ideal of X if and only if, for any $x, y \in I$, $A(x, y) \subseteq I$.

Proof. Let I be an ideal and let $x \in I$ and $y \in I$.

If $z \in A(x, y)$, then $z * x \leq y$. By Theorem (2.1.4), we have $z * x \in I$. Using (ii) we obtain $z \in I$, that is to say $A(x, y) \subseteq I$.

Conversely, suppose $A(x, y) \subseteq I$, for all $x, y \in I$. Since I is a nonempty subset of X , we assume $x \in I$. By BCK-5, $0 * x \leq x$, and so $0 \in A(x, x) \subseteq I$, (i) holds for I .

Let $x * y \in I$ and $y \in I$. By BCI-2, $x * (x * y) \leq y$, This says that $x \in A(x * y, y) \subseteq I$, and so (ii) holds for I . Hence I is an ideal of X . This completes the proof. ■

COROLLARY 2.1.7. If I is an ideal of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ if and only if, for all $x, y \in I$

,
 $(z * x) * y = 0$ implies $z \in I$.

So far we have looked at some means constructing new algebras from the old algebras, for instance, subalgebras, union algebras, and direct. $x \in C_0$.

THEOREM 2.1.8. Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCK-algebra and let I be an ideal of it, then $(X/I; *, C_0)$ is also a BCK-algebra, where $X/I = \{C_x : x \in X\}$,

Proof.

Denote $X/I = \{C_x : x \in X\}$ and define that $C_x * C_y = C_{x*y}$. Since \sim is a congruence relation on X , the operation $*$ is well-defined.

In what follows, we will prove that $(X/I; *, C_0)$ is a BCK-algebra.

If $C_x * C_y = C_0$, then $x * y \sim 0$, hence we define $C_x \leq C_y$.

Since $C_0 * C_x = C_{0*x} = C_0$, we obtain $C_0 \leq C_x$ for all $x \in X$. Therefore BCK-5 is hold in X/I .

Let $C_x * C_y = C_y * C_x = C_0$, then $x * y \sim 0$ and $y * x \sim 0$. If $u \in C_x$, then $x \sim u$, and so $u * y \sim x * y \sim 0$, which shows $u \in C_y$. Hence $C_x \subseteq C_y$. Similarly, we have $C_y \subseteq C_x$, then $C_y = C_x$. Therefore BCI-4 is hold in X/I .

Let $C_x * C_x = C_0$, then $x * x \sim 0$, so This $C_x \leq C_x$. Therefore BCI-3 is hold in X/I . If $x \leq y$, we have $x * y = 0$ and $C_x * C_y = C_{x*y} = C_0$, then $x * y \sim 0$ Hence $C_x \leq C_y$.

By this $(C_x * C_y) * (C_x * C_z) = C_{x*y} * C_{x*z} = C_{(x*y)*(x*z)} \leq C_{z*y} = C_z * C_y$. Therefore BCK-1 is hold in X/I . Since $C_x * (C_x * C_y) = C_{x*(x*y)} \leq C_y$. Therefore BCI-2 is hold in X/I . Hence $(X/I; *, C_0)$ is a BCK-algebra. ■

Remark: Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCK-algebra and let I be an ideal of X . Then $(X/I; *, C_0)$ is also a BCK-algebra, which is called to be **the quotient algebra via I** , and $C_0 = I$.

There is a close relation between the ideals of X and the one of X/I .

THEOREM 2.1.9. Any ideal of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is a subalgebra of X .

Proof. Suppose I is an ideal of X and $x, y \in I$. Since $x * y \leq x$, it follows from Theorem (2.1.5) that $x * y \in I$. Hence I is a subalgebra of X . The proof is complete. ■

THEOREM 2.1.10. If I and J are any ideals of BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ and $I \subset J$, then

- (a) I is also an ideal of the subalgebra,
- (b) J/I as the quotient of the subalgebra J via the ideal I is an ideal of X/I .

Proof.

(a) It is immediate from Theorem (2.1.9).

(b) First, we have to show that each element of J/I is also an element of X/I . To avoid the ambiguity, we denote the element of J/I containing x by $C_x(J)$. Suppose $y \in X$ and $x \in J$.

If $x \sim y$ with respect to I , then $y * x \in I$ and so $y * x \in J$ and $x \in I$. By Definition (2.1.1(ii)), we have $y \in J$, this says $C_x(J) \in X/I$ or each element of J/I is also an element of X/I .

Next, we prove that J/I is an ideal of X/I . Since $I \subseteq J, C_0 = I \in J/I$. If $C_x * C_y \in J/I$ and $C_y \in J/I$, then $C_{x*y} \in J/I$. It follows that $x * y \in J$ and $y \in J$. By Definition (2.1.1(ii)), we obtain $x \in J$, and so $C_x \in J/I$. This means that J/I is an ideal of X/I . This finishes the proof. ■

THEOREM 2.1.11. If J^* is ideal of X/I , then $J = \{C_x : C_x \in J^*\}$ is an ideal of BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ and $I \subseteq J$.

Proof. Since $I = C_0 \in J^*, 0 \in J$ and $I \subseteq J$. Let $x * y \in J$ and $y \in J$, then $C_x * C_y = C_{x*y} \in J^*$ and $C_y \in J^*$. By Definition (2.1.1(ii)), we have $C_x \in J^*$ and $x \in J$. This shows that J is an ideal of X , proving the theorem. ■

THEOREM 2.1.12. If I is an ideal of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, then there is a bisection from $Y(X, I)$ to $Y(X/I)$.

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra. $\{0,1,3\}$ and $\{0,1,2,3\}$ are positive implicative ideals of X . $\{0\}$, $\{0,2\}$ and $\{0,2,4\}$ are ideals of X , but not positive implicative.

PROPOSITION 2.2.3. Any positive implicative ideal must be an ideal, but the inverse is not true.

Proof. Suppose I is a positive implicative ideal of BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$.

If $x * y \in I$ and $y \in I$, then $(x * y) * 0 \in I$ and $y * 0 \in I$. By (ii) we have $x = x * 0 \in I$, hence I is an ideal.

In the Example (2.2.2), $\{0,2\}$ is an ideal, but not positive implicative as $(3 * 2) * 0 \in \{0, 2\}$, $2 * 0 = 2 \in \{0, 2\}$ and $3 * 0 = 3 \notin \{0,2\}$. This shows that an ideal need not be positive implicative.

In the following, we give a number of equivalent conditions of positive implicative ideals needed for further discussion.

THEOREM 2.2.4. If we are given an ideal I of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, then I is positive implicative if and only if for any $a \in X$, the set $A_a = \{x \in X : x * a \in I\}$ is an ideal of X .

Proof. (\Rightarrow) . Suppose that I is positive implicative and $x * y \in A_a$ and $y \in A_a$. Then $(x * y) * a \in I$ and $y * a \in I$. By (ii) we obtain $x * a \in I$. i.e., $x \in A_a$, this says A_a is an ideal.

(\Leftarrow) Suppose that for any $a \in X$, A_a is an ideal of X . If $(x * y) * z \in I$ and $y * z \in I$, then $x * y \in A_z$ and $y \in A_z$. Since A_z is an ideal of X . $x \in A_z$, and so $x * z \in I$. This means that I is positive implicative.

COROLLARY 2.2.5. If I is a positive implicative ideal of BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, then for any

$a \in X$, $A_a = \{x \in X : x * a \in I\}$ is the least ideal containing I and a .

Proof. If I is a positive implicative ideal, then A_a is an ideal, as well as then least ideal containing I and a . In fact, if B is any ideal containing I and a , then for all $x \in A_a$ we have $x * a \in I$. It follows that $x * a \in B$ and $a \in B$, hence $x \in B$. This shows that $A_a \subseteq B$. The assertion holds.

THEOREM 2.2.6. If a nonempty subset I of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, the following are equivalent:

- (a) I is a positive implicative ideal
- (b) I is an ideal, and for any $x, y \in X$, $(x * y) * y \in I$ implies $x * y \in I$.
- (c) I is an ideal, and for any $x, y, z \in X$, $(x * y) * z \in I$ implies $(x * z) * (y * z) \in I$,
- (d) $0 \in I$, and $((x * y) * y) * z \in I$ and $z \in I$, imply $x * y \in I$.

Proof. $(a) \Rightarrow (b)$. If I is a positive implicative ideal, by Proposition (2.2.3), I is an ideal. Suppose $(x * y) * y \in I$. Since $y * y = 0 \in I$, by Definition (2.2.1(ii)), we have $x * y \in I$, (b) holds.

(b) \Rightarrow (c). Assume (b) and $(x * y) * z \in I$. Since $(x * z) * (y * z) = ((x * (y * z)) * z)$, then $((x * (y * z)) * z) * z = ((x * z) * (y * z)) * z \leq (x * y) * z \in I$,

it follows that $((x * (y * z)) * z) * z \in I$. By (b), we have $(x * z) * (y * z) = (x * (y * z)) * z \in I$ and so (c) holds.

(c) \Rightarrow (d). It is clear that $0 \in I$. If $((x * y) * y) * z \in I$ and $z \in I$, then $((x * z) * y) * y \in I$. By (c), we get $(x * y) * z = ((x * z) * y) * (y * y) \in I$. Since I is an ideal and $z \in I, x * y \in I$ follows. (d) holds.

(d) \Rightarrow (a). First observe that if I satisfies (d), then I is an ideal of X . In fact, suppose $x * y \in I$ and $y \in I$, then $((x * 0) * 0) * y \in I$ and $y \in I$. Using (d) we obtain $x = x * 0 \in I$, i.e., I is an ideal.

Next, let $(x * y) * z \in I$ and $y * z \in I$. As

$((x * z) * z) * (y * z) \leq (x * z) * y = (x * y) * z \in I$, it follows that $((x * z) * z) * (y * z) \in I$. Combining $y * x \in I$ and using (d), we have $x * z \in I$. This have proved that I is a positive implicative ideal. The proof is completed. ■

The next theorem describe a distributive case of all positive implicative ideals in a BCK-algebra, by means of which we will obtain a nice characterization for positive implicative BCK-algebras by ideals.

THEOREM 2.2.7. Suppose I and A are ideals of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, and $I \subseteq A$. If I is positive implicative, then so is A .

Proof. Let $(x * y) * z \in A$ and denote $u = (x * y) * z$. Then

$$((x * u) * y) * z = ((x * y) * z) * u = ((x * y) * z) * ((x * y) * z) = 0 \in I$$

Making use of positive implicatively of I and Theorem (2.2.6(c)), we have $((x * u) * z) * (y * z) \in I$, $((x * z) * (y * z)) * ((x * y) * z) = ((x * z) * (y * z)) * u \in I$. As $I \subset A$, we obtain $((x * z) * (y * z)) * ((x * y) * z) \in A$.

Combining $(x * y) * z \in A$ and A is an ideal, it follows that $(x * z) * (y * z) \in A$. This shows that for the ideal A , $(x * y) * z \in A$ implies $(x * z) * (y * z) \in A$. So A is positive implicative by Theorem (2.2.6(c)). This completes the proof. ■

COROLLARY 2.2.8. In a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, the following are equivalent:

- (a) X is a positive implicative BCK-algebra,
- (b) $\{0\}$ is a positive implicative ideal of X ,
- (c) All ideals of X are positive implicative,
- (d) For any a in X , $A(a) = \{x \in X : x \leq a\}$ is an ideal.

Proof. H.W.

From this corollary we see that in BCK-algebras, zero ideals play important roles.

THEOREM 2.2.9. A BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is positive implicative if and only if for any ideal I of X and any element a of X , $A_a = \{x \in X : x * a \in I\}$ is an ideal of X .

Proof. H.W.

CHAPTER TWO

SECTION THREE

2.3. Implicative ideals of BCK-algebras

In 1986, Jie Meng introduced the notion of implicative ideals and by means of such ideals implicative BCK-algebra was characterized.

DEFINITION 2.3.1. Suppose $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra. A nonempty subset I of X is said to be an **implicative ideal** if it satisfies the following: *for all $x, y, z \in X$*

(i) $0 \in I$,

(ii) $(x * (y * x)) * z \in I$ and $z \in I$ imply $x \in I$.

REMARK 2.3.2. Given a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, the set X is always an implicative ideal of X , which is called the **trivial implicative ideal**.

EXAMPLE 2.3.3. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ in which the operation $*$ is given by the table

*	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0	0
2	2	1	0	1	0
3	3	3	3	0	0
4	4	4	4	4	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra, but it is neither positive implicative nor commutative. It is easy to verify that $I = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ is an implicative ideal of X .

First, we discuss the relations of ideals, implicative ideals and positive is implicative ideals.

REMARK 2.3.4. If $(X; *, 0)$ is an implicative BCK-algebra, then every ideal of X is implicative.

Proposition 2.3.5. An implicative ideal must be an ideal, but the inverse does not hold.

Proof. Let I be an implicative ideal and $x * z \in I$, $z \in I$. Putting $y = x$ in Definition (2.3.1(ii)), we have $(x * (x * x)) * z = x * z \in I$ and $z \in I$. By Definition (2.1.1(ii)), we get $x \in I$, so I is an ideal. ■

The last part is shown by the following example.

EXAMPLE 2.3.6. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ with the operation $*$ be given by the table:

*	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1	0	1
2	2	2	0	2	0

3	3	1	3	0	3
4	4	4	4	4	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra. It is easy to verify that $\{0,2\}$ is an ideal, but not implicative.

THEOREM 2.3.7. An implicative ideal must be positive implicative, but a positive implicative ideal need not be implicative.

Proof. Suppose I is an implicative ideal and $(x * y) * z \in I, y * z \in I$. Since $((x * z) * z) * (y * z) \leq (x * z) * y = (x * y) * z \in I$, by Theorem (2.1.2), we get $((x * z) * z) * (y * z) \in I$. Combining $y * z \in I$ and making use of I being an ideal, we have $(x * z) * z \in I$. As $(x * z) * (x * (x * z)) = (x * (x * (x * z))) * z$
 $= (x * z) * z \in I$, it follows that $((x * z) * (x * (x * z))) * 0 \in I$.

Combining $0 \in I$, we obtain $x * z \in I$. This means that I is a positive implicative ideal.

In the Example (2.3.6), $\{0, 1, 3\}$ is a positive implicative ideal but not implicative. This finishes the proof. ■

For further relations we have the following.

THEOREM 2.3.8. Suppose I is a positive implicative ideal of BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. Then I is implicative if and only if for all $x, y \in X$, $y * (y * x) \in I$ implies $x * (x * y) \in I$
(a)

Proof. (\Rightarrow) Necessity. Suppose I is a positive implicative ideal and let $y * (y * x) \in I$. Since $x * (x * y) \leq x$, it follows that $y * x \leq y * (x * (x * y))$. Hence $(x * (x * y)) * (y * (x * (x * y))) \leq (x * (x * y)) * (y * x)$
 $= (x * (y * x)) * (x * y) \leq y * (y * x)$. Since I is also an ideal by Proposition (2.2.3), we obtain $((x * (x * y)) * (y * (x * (x * y)))) * 0 \in I$.

Combining $0 \in I$ and using Definition (2.3.1(ii)), we have $x * (x * y) \in I$. Thus we have proved that $y * (y * x) \in I$ implies $x * (x * y) \in I$, namely, I satisfies (a).

(\Leftarrow) Sufficiency. Suppose I satisfies (a) and let $(x * (y * x)) * z \in I$ and $z \in I$.

Now, we prove that $x \in I$. Since I is an ideal, $x * (y * x) \in I$. Noticing that $(y * (y * x)) * (y * x) \leq x * (y * x) \in I$, we have $(y * (y * x)) * (y * x) \in I$. It follows from Theorem (2.2.6(b)), that $y * (y * x) \in I$. By(a), we obtain $x * (x * y) \in I$ (1) .

Noticing that $(x * y) * z \leq x * y \leq x * (y * x) \in I$, we have $(x * y) * z \in I$. Combining $z \in I$ it follows that $x * y \in I$. From this and (1) $x \in I$ follows. Therefore I is an implicative ideal. This completes the proof. ■

Proposition 2.3.9. An ideal I is implicative of BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ if and only if, for all $x, y \in X, x * (y * x) \in I$ implies $x \in I$ (b) .

Proof.

(\Leftarrow) Suppose I is an ideal and satisfies (b). If $(x * (y * x)) * z \in I$ and $z \in I$. By the definition of ideal, we have $x * (y * x) \in I$. Then, by (b) it follows that $x \in I$. This proves that the direction.

(\Rightarrow) The opposite direction is evident. This finishes the proof. ■

THEOREM 2.3.10. Let I be an ideal of BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. If I is an implicative ideal of X , then every ideal A containing I is implicative

Proof. By means of Theorem (2.3.7), we know that I must be a positive implicative ideal. Using Theorem (2.2.7). A is a positive implicative ideal. In the order to prove that A is implicative, it is sufficient only to verify that A satisfies the condition (b) in Theorem (2.3.9). To do this suppose $x * (x * y) \in A$ and denote $u = x * (x * y)$. Since $(x * (x * y)) * u = 0 \in I$ and I is positive implicative, it follows from Theorem (2.2.6 (c)), that

$$(x * u) * ((x * y) * u) = (x * u) * ((x * u) * y) \in I$$

Using implicatively of I and Theorem (2.3.9), we have $y * (y * (x * u)) \in I$.

It follows from $I \subseteq A$ that $y * (y * (x * u)) \in A$. Note that

$$\begin{aligned} (y * (y * x)) * (y * (y * (x * u))) &\leq (y * (x * u)) * (y * x) \\ &\leq x * (x * u) = x * (x * (x * (x * y))) = x * (x * y) \in A. \end{aligned}$$

Hence $(y * (y * x)) * (y * (y * (x * u))) \in A$.

Combining $y * (y * (x * u)) \in A$, we have $y * (y * x) \in A$. By Theorem (2.3.9), A is an implicative ideal. ■

Finally, we give some characterizations of implicative BCK-algebras ideals.

THEOREM 2.3.11. Given a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, the following are equivalent:

- (a) X is an implicative BCK-algebra
- (b) Every ideal of X is implicative,
- (c) The zero ideal $\{0\}$ is implicative,
- (d) For all a of $X, A(a) = \{x \in X : x \leq a\}$ is an implicative ideal,

Proof. H.W.

CHAPTER TWO SECTION FOUR

2.4. Commutative ideals of BCK-algebras

Following the idea of implicative and positive implicative ideals, J. Meng introduced the notion of commutative ideals, and discussed the relations of commutative ideals, positive implicative ideals, and implicative ideals.

DEFINITION 2.4.1. A nonempty subset I of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is said to be a **commutative ideal of X** if it satisfies: $x, y, z \in X$

- (1) $0 \in I$,
- (2) $(x * y) * z \in I$ and $z \in I$ imply $x * (y * (y * x)) \in I$.

Obviously, X is always a commutative ideal of BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, which called the trivial commutative ideal.

In the Example (2.3.6), $\{0, 2\}$ and $\{0, 2, 4\}$ are commutative ideals, but not positive implicative ideals. Also $\{0, 1, 3\}$ is a positive implicative ideal but not commutative, and $\{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ is an implicative ideal.

Proposition 2.4.2. Let I be an ideal of BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. A commutative ideal must be an ideal, but the inverse hold

Proof. Suppose I is a commutative ideal, and let $x * y \in I$ and $y \in I$. Then $(x * 0) * y \in I$

and $y \in I$. By the definition, we have $x = x * (0 * (0 * x)) \in I$, and so I is an ideal. The last half part is shown by the previous example.

Proposition 2.4.3. Let I be an ideal of BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. An ideal I is commutative if and only if it satisfies $x * y \in I$ implies $x * (y * (y * x)) \in I$ (c).

Proof. If an ideal I is commutative ideal of X and $x * y \in I$, then $(x * y) * 0 \in I$ and $0 \in I$. By Definition (2.4.1(ii)), we have $x * (y * (y * x)) \in I$. This says that (c) holds.

Conversely, let an ideal I satisfies (c). If $(x * y) * z \in I$ and $z \in I$, then by the definition of ideals we obtain $x * y \in I$. It follows from (c) that $x * (y * (y * x)) \in I$. This means that I is a commutative ideal. ■

In the following theorem we will give a relation of commutative ideals, implicative ideas and positive implicative ideals, which is similar to Theorem (1.6.2).

THEOREM 2.4.4. Let $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra, and I is a nonempty subset of X . I is an implicative ideal if and only if it is both a commutative ideal and positive implicative ideal.

Proof. Suppose I is an implicative ideal. By Theorem (2.3.7), I is a positive implicative ideal. Now, we prove that I is also commutative. To do this let $x * y \in I$. Since $x * (y * (y * x)) \leq x$, we have $y * x \leq y * (x * (y * (y * x)))$. Denote $u = x * (y * (y * x))$, we obtain

$$u * (y * u) = (x * (y * (y * x))) * (y * (x * (y * (y * x)))) \\ \leq (x * (y * (y * x))) * (y * x) = (x * (y * x)) * (y * (y * x)) \leq x * y \in I$$

Hence $u * (x * u) \in I$. Making use of Proposition (2.3.9), we get $u \in I$, i.e.,

$x * (y * (y * x)) \in I$. This proves that $x * y \in I$ implies $x * (y * (y * x)) \in I$.

Therefore I is a commutative ideal, by Proposition (2.4.3).

Conversely, suppose I is both a commutative ideal and positive implicative ideal.

Let $x * (y * x) \in I$. Since $(y * (y * x)) * (y * x) \leq x * (y * x)$,
 $(y * (y * x)) * (y * x) \in I$. Making use of Theorem (2.2.6 (a)), we have
 $y * (y * x) \in I \dots (1)$.

Moreover, since $x * y \leq x * (y * x)$, we obtain $x * y \in I$. By Proposition (2.4.3),
 $x * (y * (y * x)) \in I$. Combining (1) we have $x \in I$. This proves that $x * (y * x) \in I$,
implies $x \in I$. Therefore I is an implicative ideal. ■

With respect to the distribution of commutative ideals in a BCK-algebra, we have

Proposition 2.4.5. Suppose I and A are ideals of BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ and let $I \subseteq A$. If I is commutative then so is A .

Proof. Let $x * y \in A$ and denote $u = x * y$, then $(x * u) * y = (x * y) * u = 0 \in I$.

Using the commutativity of I and Proposition (2.4.3), we have

$(x * u) * (y * (y * (x * u))) \in I$. The hypothesis $I \subseteq A$ implies
 $(x * (y * (y * (x * u)))) * u = (x * u) * (y * (y * (x * u))) \in A$. Combining
 $u \in A$, we have $x * (y * (y * (x * u))) \in A$. As
 $(x * (y * (y * x))) * (x * (y * (y * (x * u)))) \leq (y * (y * (x * u))) * (y * (y * x)) \leq (y * x) * (y * (x * u)) \leq (x * u) * x = 0 * u \in A$, we obtain
 $x * (y * (y * x)) \in A$. Hence A is a commutative ideal. ■

THEOREM 2.4.6 If $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra, then the following are equivalent:

- (a) X is a commutative BCK-algebra.
- (b) Every ideal of X is commutative,
- (c) The zero ideal $\{0\}$ is commutative,

Proof. (b) \Leftrightarrow (c) follows directly from Proposition (2.4.5). (H.W.) ■

CHAPTER TWO

SECTION FIVE

2.5. BCK-ideals of BCK-algebras

The notion of BCK-ideals in BCK-algebras was introduced by K. Iséki in 1975.

DEFINITION 2.5.1. Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCK-algebra and let I be a nonempty subset of X .

Then I is called to be a **BCK-ideal of X** if, for all $x, y \in X$,

- (i) $0 \in I$,
- (ii) $x * (y * z) \in I$ and $y \in I$ imply $x * z \in I$.

EXAMPLE 2.5.2. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ in which $*$ is given by the table

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	2	0
2	2	1	0	0
3	3	2	1	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra, it has BCK-ideals $\{0,1\}$, $\{0,1,2\}$ and X .

Proposition 2.5.3. Let $(X; *, 0)$ be any BCK-algebra and let \bar{X} be the Iséki's extension of X . Then X is a BCK-ideal of \bar{X} .

Proof. H.W.

Proposition 2.5.4. If I is a BCK-ideal of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, then I is ideal of X .

Proof. since $x * (y * z) \in I$ and $y \in I$ implies $x * z \in I$, put $z=0$, then $x * (y * 0) = x * y \in I$ and $y \in I$ implies $x * 0 = x \in I$, thus I is ideal of X

Proposition 2.5.5. If I is a BCK-ideal of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, then I is subalgebra of X .

Proof. By Proposition (2.5.4), I is ideal of X . and by Proposition (2.1.4), thus I is subalgebra of X .

CHAPTER TWO

SECTION SIX

2.6. BCK-Filters of BCK-algebras

A BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, if there is a special element e of a BCK-algebra X satisfying $x \leq e$ for all $x \in X$, then e is called **unit** of X . A BCK-algebra with unit is said to be **bounded**. In a bounded BCK-algebra X , we denote $e * x$ by x^* for every $x \in X$. In a bounded BCK-algebra, we have

- 1) $e^* = 0$ and $0^* = e$.
- 2) $y \leq x$ implies $x^* \leq y^*$.
- 3) $x^* * y^* \leq y * x$.

Definition 2.6.1. Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a bounded BCK-algebra and let F be a nonempty subset of X . Then F is called to be a **BCK-filter of X** if, for all $x, y \in X$,

- (i) $e \in F$,
- (ii) $(x^* * y^*)^* \in F$ and $y \in F$ imply $x \in F$.

$\{e\}$ and X are two **trivial BCK-filters of X** .

Example 2.6.2. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2\}$ in which $*$ is given by the table:

*	0	1	2
0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0
2	2	2	0

Then $(X;*, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra with unite 2, and $X, \{1,2\}, \{0,2\}$ are all BCK-filters of X .

Example 2.6.3. Let $X=\{0,1, 2, 3\}$ in which $*$ is given by the table

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	3	0
2	2	1	0	0
3	3	2	1	0

Then $(X;*, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra with unite 3, it has two BCK-filters $\{1,2,3\}$ and $\{0,1,2,3\}$.

Lemma 2.6.4. Let $(X;*, 0)$ be any bounded BCK-algebra and F is BCK-filter of X . $x \in F$ if and only if $(x^*)^* = x^{**} \in F$.

Proposition 2.6.5. Let $(X;*, 0)$ be a bounded BCK-algebra and F be a subset of X .

If $e * x \in F, \forall x \in X$, then F is BCK-filter.

Proof. H.W.

Proposition 2.6.6. Let $(X;*, 0)$ be any bounded BCK-algebra and let \bar{X} be the Iséki's extension of X . Then every subset contains 0 and e is BCK-filter of \bar{X} .

Proof. H.W.

Definition 2.6.7. A subset F of a bounded BCK-algebra $(X;*, 0)$ is said to be **complete BCK-filter of X** (c-BCK-filter), if,

- (i) $e \in F$,
- (ii) $(x^* * y^*)^* \in F, \forall y \in F$ imply $x \in F$.

Proposition 2.6.8. If f is a homomorphism from BCK-algebra $(X;*, 0)$ into BCK-algebra $(Y;*', 0')$, then f is isotone i.e, $x \leq y$ implies $f(x) \leq f(y)$.

Proof. H.W.

Proposition 2.6.9. Let $(X;*, 0)$ be a bounded BCK-algebra. If I is a c-BCK-filter of a BCK-algebra $(X;*, 0)$, then I is BCK-filter of X .

Proof. H.W.

Lemma 2.6.10. Suppose f is an epimorphism from bounded BCK-algebra $(X;*, 0)$ into bounded BCK-algebra $(Y;*', 0')$, then $f(e_x) = e_y$ where e_x, e_y are the units of X and Y respectively.

Proof. H.W.

Proposition 2.6.11. Let f be an epimorphism from bounded BCK-algebra $(X;*, 0)$ into bounded BCK-algebra $(Y;*', 0')$, then

- 1) $f(x^*) = (f(x))^*$, for all $x \in X$, and
- 2) $f^{-1}(y^*) = (f^{-1}(y))^*$, for all $y \in Y$, for all If f is isomorphism.

Proof.

- 1) $f(x^*) = f(e_x * x) = f(e_x) *' f(x) = e_y *' f(x) = (f(x))^*$, by Lemma (2.6.10).
- 2) $f^{-1}(y^*) = f^{-1}(e_y *' y) = f^{-1}(e_y) * f^{-1}(y) = e_x * f^{-1}(y) = (f^{-1}(y))^*$, by Lemma(2.6.10).

CHAPTER THREE
SECTION ONE

3.1. Fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of BCK-algebras

The notion of fuzzy BCK-subalgebras in BCK-algebras was introduced by O. G. Xi at Fuzzy BCK-algebras in 1991 and homomorphisms of it.

Definition 3.1.1. Let X be a non-empty set, a **fuzzy subset** μ of X is a function $\mu: X \rightarrow [0,1]$.

Definition 3.1.2. Let μ be a fuzzy subset of a set X . For $t \in [0, 1]$, the set $\mu_t = U(\mu, t) = \{x \in X \mid \mu(x) \geq t\}$, is called **upper level cut** (level subset) of μ and the set $L(\mu, t) = \{x \in X \mid \mu(x) \leq t\}$ is called **lower level cut of μ** .

Definition 3.1.3. Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCK-algebra. A fuzzy subset μ of X is called a **fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of X** if for all $x, y \in X$, $\mu(x * y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$.

Example 3.1.4. Let $X = \{0,1,2,3\}$ in which the operation $*$ is given by:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0
2	2	2	0	1
3	3	3	3	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra. Define a fuzzy subset $\mu: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ by $\mu(0) = 0.8$, $\mu(1) = \mu(2) = \mu(3) = 0.6$. Routine calculation gives that μ is fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of X .

Proposition 3.1.5. If μ is fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, then $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$.

Proof. Since μ be fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of X and $x \in X$, then $\mu(0) = \mu(x * x) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(x)\}$, then $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$.

Proposition 3.1.6. Every fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is order reversing.

Proof. Let μ be fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of X and let $x, y \in X$ be such that $x \leq y$, then $x * y = 0$ and $\mu(x * y) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$, then $\mu(0) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$.

Theorem 3.1.7. A fuzzy subset μ of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is a fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of X if and only if $\mu_t \neq \emptyset$ is a BCK-subalgebra of X .

Proof: Suppose that μ is a fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of X and $\mu_t \neq \emptyset$, for any $t \in (0,1]$, there exists $x \in \mu_t$ so that $\mu(x) \geq t$. Let $x, y \in X$ be such that $x \in \mu_t$ and $y \in \mu_t$. Using

Definition (2.1.1), we know that $\mu(x * y) \geq \min \{\mu(x), \mu(y)\} \geq \min\{t, t\} = t$, thus $x * y \in \mu_t$. Hence μ_t is a BCK-subalgebra of X .

Conversely, suppose that $\mu_t \neq \emptyset$ is a BCK-subalgebra of X , for every $t \in (0, 1]$. Now, we need to show that μ satisfies Definition (2.1.1). If not, then there exist $a, b \in X$ such that $\mu(a * b) < \min \{\mu(a), \mu(b)\}$. Taking $t = 1/2 (\mu(a * b) + \min \{\mu(a), \mu(b)\})$, then we have $\mu(a * b) < t < \min \{\mu(a), \mu(b)\}$. Hence $a \in \mu_t$ and $b \in \mu_t$, but $a * b \notin \mu_t$ which means that μ_t is not a BCK-subalgebra of X . This is a contradiction. Therefore μ is a fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of X .

Now, we introduce the concept homomorphism of fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of BCK-algebra, also we give examples and results of it.

Definition 3.1.8. Let $(X; *, 0)$ and $(Y; *, 0')$ be two BCK-algebras and f be a mapping from the set $(X; *, 0)$ to a set $(Y; *, 0')$. If μ is a fuzzy subset of X , then the fuzzy subset β of Y defined by: $f(\mu)(x) = \begin{cases} \sup\{\mu(x) : x \in f^{-1}(y)\} & \text{if } f^{-1}(y) = \{x \in X; f(x) = y\} \neq \emptyset \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$

is called **the image of μ under f** .

Similarly, if β is a fuzzy subset of Y , then the fuzzy subset defined by $\mu(x) = \beta(f(x))$, for all $x \in X$, is called **the pre-image of β under f** .

Theorem 3.1.9. Let $(X; *, 0)$ and $(Y; *, 0')$ be two BCK-algebras and

$f : (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, 0')$ be a homomorphism, then

- 1) If μ is a fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of X , then $f(\mu)$ is a fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of Y , where f is onto.
- 2) If β is a fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of Y , then $f^{-1}(\beta)$ is a fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of X .

Proof.

- 1) Let μ be a fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of X , then $\mu(a * b) \geq \min \{\mu(a), \mu(b)\}$, for all $a, b \in X$ and let $x, y \in Y$ that means $x = f(a)$, $y = f(b)$, for some $a, b \in X$. Then

$$\mu(x *' y) = \mu(f(a) *' f(b)) = \mu(f(a * b)) \geq \min \{\mu(f(a)), \mu(f(b))\} = \min \{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}. \text{ Hence } f(\mu) \text{ is a fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of } Y.$$

- 2) Let β be a fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of Y , then $\mu(a * b) \geq \min \{\mu(a), \mu(b)\}$, for all $a, b \in Y$ and let $x, y \in f^{-1}(X)$ that means $x = f^{-1}(a)$, $y = f^{-1}(b)$, for some $a, b \in X$, since $x, y \in f^{-1}(\beta)$ that means $a = f(x)$, $b = f(y)$, for some $a, b \in X$. Then

$$\mu(x *' y) = \mu(f^{-1}(a) *' f^{-1}(b)) = \mu(f^{-1}(a * b)) \geq \min \{\mu(f^{-1}(a)), \mu(f^{-1}(b))\} = \min \{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}. \text{ Hence } f^{-1}(\beta) \text{ is a fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of } X.$$

CHAPTER THREE

SECTION TWO

3.2. Fuzzy Ideals of BCK-algebras

The notion of Fuzzy ideals in BCK-algebras was introduced by O. G. Xi at Fuzzy BCK-algebras in 1991. The ideal theory plays a fundamental role for the general development of BCK-algebras. The concepts of ideals, quotient algebras, and homomorphisms are all closely related. These will be the subject of this and next chapters.

Definition 3.2.1. Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCK -algebra. A fuzzy subset μ of X is called a **fuzzy ideal of X** if it satisfies the following conditions: for all $x, y \in X$,

- (1) $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$.
- (2) $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(y)\}$.

Example 3.2.2. Let $X = \{0,1,2,3,4\}$ in which the operation $*$ is given by:

*	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0	0
2	2	0	0	0	0
3	3	3	3	0	0
4	4	4	4	4	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra. Define a fuzzy subset $\mu: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ by $\mu(0) = 0.8, \mu(1) = \mu(2) = 0.7, \mu(3) = \mu(4) = 0.6$. Routine calculation gives that μ is fuzzy ideal of BCK-algebra X .

Theorem 3.2.3. Let A be a nonempty subset of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ and μ be a fuzzy subset of X such that μ is into $\{0, 1\}$, so that μ is the characteristic function of A . Then μ is a fuzzy ideal in X if and only if, A is an ideal of X . ($\mu: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ by $\mu(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x \in A \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$)

Proof. Assume that μ is a fuzzy ideal in X , since $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$, clearly we have $\mu(0)=1$, and so $0 \in A$.

Let $x * y \in A$ and $y \in A$, since μ is a fuzzy ideal of X , it follows that $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(y)\}$, for all $x, y \in X$, and $\mu(x)=1$. This mean that $x \in A$. i.e. A is an ideal of X .

Conversely suppose A is an ideal of X , since $0 \in A, \mu(0)=1 \geq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$. Let $x, y \in X$, If $y \notin A$, or $x * y \notin A$, then $\mu(y) = 0$ or $\mu(x * y)=0$, and so $\mu(x) \geq 0 = \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(y)\}$. If $x * y \in A$, and $y \in A$, then $x \in A$ (since A is an ideal). $\mu(x) = 1 = \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(y)\}$. Hence μ is a fuzzy ideal of X . ■

Theorem 3.2.4. Let μ be a fuzzy subset of BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. μ is a fuzzy ideal of X if and only if, for every $t \in [0,1]$, μ_t is an ideal of X .

Proof. Assume that μ is a fuzzy ideal of X , by Definition (3.2.1(1)), we have $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ for all $x \in X$ therefore $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x) \geq t$, for any $x \in \mu_t$ and so $0 \in \mu_t$.

Let $x, y \in X$ be such that $(x * y) \in \mu_t$ and $y \in \mu_t$, then $\mu(x * y) \geq t$ and $\mu(y) \geq t$, since μ is a fuzzy ideal, it follows that $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(y)\} \geq t$ and we have that $x \in \mu_t$. Hence μ_t is an ideal of X .

Conversely, we only need to show that (1) and (2) in Definition (3.2.1) are true. If (1) is false, then there exist $x' \in X$ such that $\mu(0) < \mu(x')$. If we take

$t = (\mu(x') + \mu(0))/2$, then $\mu(0) < t$ and $0 \leq t < \mu(x') \leq 1$, then $x' \in \mu$ and $\mu \neq \emptyset$. As $\mu_{t'}$ is ideal of X , we have $0 \in \mu_{t'}$ and so $\mu(0) \geq t'$. This is a contradiction.

Now, assume (2) is not true, then there exist $x', y' \in X$ such that, $\mu(x') < \min\{\mu(x' * y'), \mu(y')\}$. Putting $t = (\mu(x') + \min\{\mu(x' * y'), \mu(y')\})/2$, then $\mu(x') < t$ and $0 \leq t < \min\{\mu(x' * y'), \mu(y')\} \leq 1$, hence $\mu(x' * y') > t$ and $\mu(y') > t$, which imply that $(x' * y') \in \mu_{t'}$ and $y' \in \mu_{t'}$. Since $\mu_{t'}$ is an ideal, it follows that $(x') \in \mu_{t'}$ and that $\mu(x') \geq t'$, this is also a contradiction. Hence μ is a fuzzy ideal of X . ■

Corollary 3.2.5. Let μ be a fuzzy subset of BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. If μ is a fuzzy ideal, then for every $t \in \text{Im}(\mu)$, μ_t is an ideal of X , when $\mu_t \neq \emptyset$.

Proof. H.W.

Proposition 3.2.6. Every fuzzy ideal of BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is a fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of X .

Proof. Since μ is a fuzzy ideal of BCK-algebra X , then by Theorem (3.2.4), for every $t \in [0,1]$, μ_t is ideal of X . By Theorem (2.1.4), for every $t \in [0,1]$, μ_t is subalgebra of X . Hence μ is a fuzzy subalgebra of BCK-algebra X by Proposition (3.1.7). ■

Theorem 3.2.7. Let A be an ideal of BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. Then for any fixed number (t) in an open interval $(0,1)$, there exists a fuzzy ideal μ of X such that $\mu_t = A$.

Proof. Define $\mu: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ by $\mu(x) = \begin{cases} t & \text{if } x \in A \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$. Where (t) is a fixed number in $(0, 1]$.

Clearly, $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$. Let $x, y \in X$.

If $y \notin A$, or $x * y \notin A$, then $\mu(y) = 0$ or $\mu(x * y) = 0$, and so $\mu(x) \geq 0 = \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(y)\}$. If $x * y \in A$, and $y \in A$, then $x \in A$ (since A is an ideal). $\mu(x) = t = \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(y)\}$. Hence μ is a fuzzy ideal of X . It is clear that $\mu_t = A$. ■

Theorem 3.2.8. Let μ be a fuzzy ideal of BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ and let μ_{t_1}, μ_{t_2} be two level ideals of μ , where $t_1 < t_2$, then the following are equivalent.

E₁) $\mu_{t_1} = \mu_{t_2}$.

E₂) There is no $x \in X$ such that $t_1 \leq \mu(x) < t_2$.

Proof. Assume that $\mu_{t_1} = \mu_{t_2}$, for $t_1 < t_2$ and that there exist $x \in X$ such that $t_1 \leq \mu(x) < t_2$.

Then μ_{t_2} is proper subset of μ_{t_1} , a contradiction. Hence $t_1 \leq \mu(x) < t_2$.

Conversely suppose that there is no $x \in X$ such that $t_1 \leq \mu(x) < t_2$. It follows from $t_1 < t_2$, that $\mu_{t_1} \subset \mu_{t_2}$. Let $x \in \mu_{t_2}$. Then $\mu(x) \geq t_2 > t_1$, because $\mu(x)$ does not lie between t_1 and t_2 . Hence $x \in \mu_{t_1}$, this implies that $\mu_{t_2} \subset \mu_{t_1}$. Therefore, $\mu_{t_1} = \mu_{t_2}$. ■

Theorem 3.2.9. Let $(X; *, 0)$ and $(Y; *, 0')$ be two BCK-algebras and $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, 0')$ be a homomorphism, then

1) If I is a fuzzy ideal of X , then $f(I)$ is a fuzzy ideal of Y , where f is onto.

2) If J is a fuzzy ideal of Y , then $f^{-1}(J)$ is a fuzzy ideal of X .

Proof.

1) Let I be a fuzzy ideal of X that mean $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ and

$\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(y)\}$, for all $x, y \in X$. Clearly, $0' \in f(I)$, then $\mu(f(0)) \geq \mu(f(x))$

for all $x \in X$, and let $x, y \in f(I)$ that means $x = f(a)$, $y = f(b)$, for some $a, b \in I$, then

$\mu(x) = \mu(f(a)) \geq \min\{\mu(f(a * b)), \mu(f(b))\}$

$$= \min\{\mu(f(a) * f(b)), \mu(f(b))\}$$

$$= \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(y)\}, \text{ for all } x, y \in Y.$$

Hence $f(I)$ is a fuzzy ideal of Y .

2) Let J be a fuzzy ideal of Y that mean $\mu(f(0)) = \mu(0') \geq \mu(f(x))$ and

$$\mu(f(x)) \geq \min\{\mu(f(x) * f(y)), \mu(f(y))\}, \text{ for all } x, y \in Y. \text{ Clearly, } 0' \in f(J) \text{ and let } a, b \in f^{-1}(J) \text{ that means } a = f^{-1}(x), b = f^{-1}(y), \text{ for some } x, y \in J, \text{ then}$$

$$\mu(a) = \mu(f^{-1}(x)) \geq \min\{\mu(f^{-1}(x * y)), \mu(f^{-1}(y))\}$$

$$= \min\{\mu(f^{-1}(x) * f^{-1}(y)), \mu(f^{-1}(y))\}$$

$$= \min\{\mu((a * b), \mu(b)\}, \text{ for all } a, b \in X. \text{ Hence } f^{-1}(J) \text{ is a fuzzy ideal of } X. \blacksquare$$

CHAPTER THREE

SECTION THREE

3.3. Fuzzy BCK-ideals of BCK-algebras

Definition 3.3.1. Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCK-algebra. A fuzzy subset μ of X is called a **fuzzy BCK-ideal of X** if it satisfies the following conditions: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

- (1) $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$.
- (2) $\mu(x * z) \geq \min\{\mu(x * (y * z)), \mu(y)\}$.

Example 3.3.2. Let $X = \{0,1,2,3,4\}$ in which the operation $*$ is given by:

*	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	1	2	3	4
1	0	0	0	3	4
2	0	0	0	3	4
3	0	0	1	0	4
4	0	0	0	0	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is an BCK-algebra. Define a fuzzy subset $\mu: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ by $\mu(0) = 0.6, \mu(1) = \mu(2) = 0.5, \mu(3) = \mu(4) = 0.4$. Routine calculation gives that μ is fuzzy BCK-ideal of BCK-algebra X .

Theorem 3.3.3. Let A be a nonempty subset of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ and μ be a fuzzy subset of X such that μ is into $\{0, 1\}$, so that μ is the characteristic function of A . Then μ is a fuzzy BCK-ideal in X if and only if, A is a BCK-ideal of X .

Proof. Assume that μ is a fuzzy BCK-ideal in X , since $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$, clearly we have $\mu(0)=1$, and so $0 \in A$.

Let $(x * (y * z)) \in A$ and $y \in A$, since μ is a fuzzy BCK-ideal of X , it follows that $\mu(x * z) \geq \min\{\mu(x * (y * z)), \mu(y)\}$, for all $x, y, z \in X$, and $\mu(x)=1$. This mean that $\mu(x) \in A$. i.e. A is a BCK-ideal of X .

Conversely suppose A is a BCK-ideal of X , since $0 \in A, \mu(0)=1 \geq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$. Let $x, y, z \in X$, if $y \notin A$, then $\mu(y) = 0$, and so $\mu(x * z) \geq 0 = \min\{\mu(x * (y * z)), \mu(y)\}$. If $x * (y * z) \in A$, and $y \in A$, then $x * y \notin A$ (since A is a BCK-ideal). Thus $\mu(x * y) = 0$.

$z) = 0 = \min\{\mu(x*(y*z)), \mu(y)\}$. Hence μ is a fuzzy BCK-ideal of X . ■

Lemma 3.3.4. Let μ be a fuzzy BCK-ideal of BCK-algebra X and if $x \leq y$, then $\mu(x) \geq \mu(y)$, for all $x, y \in X$.

Proof. Assume that $x \leq y$, then $x * y = 0$, this together with $x * 0 = x$ and

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(0) \geq \mu(y), \text{ we get } \mu(x * 0) = \mu(x) &\geq \min\{\mu(x * (y * 0)), \mu(y)\} \\ &= \min\{\mu(0 * 0), \mu(y)\} = \min\{\mu(0), \mu(y)\} = \mu(y). \quad \blacksquare \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 3.3.5. Let μ be a fuzzy subset of BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. μ is a fuzzy BCK-ideal of X if and only if, for every $t \in [0,1]$, μ_t is a BCK-ideal of X .

Proof. Assume that μ is a fuzzy BCK-ideal of X , by Definition (3.3.1(1)), we have $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ for all $x \in X$ therefore $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x) \geq t$ for $x \in \mu_t$ and so $0 \in \mu_t$.

Let $x, y, z \in X$ be such that $(x * (y * z)) \in \mu_t$ and $y \in \mu_t$, then $\mu(x * (y * z)) \geq t$ and $\mu(y) \geq t$, since μ is a fuzzy BCK-ideal, it follows that $\mu(x * z) \geq \min\{\mu(x * (y * z)), \mu(y)\} \geq t$ and we have that $x * z \in \mu_t$. Hence μ_t is a BCK-ideal of X .

Conversely, we only need to show that (1) and (2) in Definition (3.3.1) are true. If (1) is false, then there exist $x' \in X$ such that $\mu(0) < \mu(x')$. If we take $t = (\mu(x') + \mu(0))/2$, then $\mu(0) < t$ and $0 \leq t < \mu(x') \leq 1$, then $x' \in \mu$ and $\mu \neq \emptyset$. As μ_t is a-ideal of X , we have $0 \in \mu_t$, and so $\mu(0) \geq t$. This is a contradiction.

Now, assume (2) is not true, then there exist $x', y', z' \in X$ such that, $\mu(x' * z') < \min\{\mu(x' * (y' * z')), \mu(y')\}$. Putting $t = (\mu(x' * z') + \min\{\mu(x' * (y' * z')), \mu(y')\})/2$, then $\mu(x' * z') < t$ and $0 \leq t < \min\{\mu(x' * (y' * z')), \mu(y')\} \leq 1$, hence $\mu(x' * (y' * z')) > t$ and $\mu(y') > t$, which imply that $(x' * (y' * z')) \in \mu_t$, and $(y') \in \mu_t$. Since μ_t is an ideal, it follows that $(x' * z') \in \mu_t$ and that $\mu(x' * z') \geq t$, this is also a contradiction. Hence μ is a fuzzy BCK-ideal of X . ■

Corollary 3.3.6. Let μ be a fuzzy subset of BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. If μ is a fuzzy BCK-ideal, then for every $t \in \text{Im}(\mu)$, μ_t is a BCK-ideal of X , when $\mu_t \neq \emptyset$.

Proof. H.W.

Proposition 3.3.7. Every fuzzy BCK-ideal of BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is a fuzzy ideal of X .

Proof. Since μ is a fuzzy BCK-ideal of BCK-algebra X , then by Theorem (3.3.5), for every $t \in [0,1]$, μ_t is BCK-ideal of X . By Theorem (2.6.4), for every $t \in [0,1]$, μ_t is ideal of X . Hence μ is a fuzzy ideal of BCK-algebra X by Proposition (3.1.7). ■

Proposition 3.3.8. Every fuzzy ideal of BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is a fuzzy subalgebra of X .

Proof. Since μ is a fuzzy BCK-ideal of BCK-algebra X , then by Theorem (3.3.5), for every $t \in [0,1]$, μ_t is BCK-ideal of X . By Theorem (2.6.5), for every $t \in [0,1]$, μ_t is subalgebra of X . Hence μ is a fuzzy ideal of BCK-algebra X by Proposition (3.1.7). ■

Theorem 3.3.9. Let A be a BCK-ideal of BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. Then for any fixed number (t) in an open interval $(0,1)$, there exists a fuzzy BCK-ideal μ of X such that $\mu_t = A$.

Proof. Define $\mu: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ by $\mu(x) = \begin{cases} t & \text{if } x \in A \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$. Where (t) is a fixed number in $(0,$

1).

Clearly, $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$. Let $x, y \in X$. If $(x * (y * z)) \notin A$, then $\mu(x * (y * z)) = 0$ and so $\mu(x * z) \geq 0 = \min\{\mu(x * (y * z)), \mu(y)\}$.

If $(x * (y * z)) \in A$, then clearly $\mu(x * z) \geq \min\{\mu(x * (y * z)), \mu(y)\}$.

If $(x) \notin A, (x * y) \in A$, then $y \notin A$, since A is ideal. Thus

$\mu(x * z) = 0 = \min\{\mu(x * (y * z)), \mu(y)\}$. Hence μ is a fuzzy BCK-ideal of X . It is clear that $\mu_t = A$. ■

Theorem 3.3.10. Let A be a nonempty subset of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ and μ be a fuzzy subset of X such that μ is into $\{0, 1\}$, so that μ is the characteristic function of A . Then μ is a fuzzy BCK-ideal of X if and only if, A is BCK-ideal of X .

Proof. Assume that μ is a fuzzy BCK-ideal in X , since $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ for all $x \in X$, clearly we have $\mu(0)=1$, and so $0 \in A$. Let $x, y, z \in X$ be such that $(x * (y * z)) \in A$ and $y \in A$, since μ is a fuzzy BCK-ideal of X , it follows that

$$\mu(x * z) \geq \min\{\mu(x * (y * z)), \mu(y)\} = 1, \text{ and } \mu(x * z) = 1.$$

This mean that $x * z \in A$, i.e., A is BCK-ideal of X .

Conversely, suppose A is BCK-ideal of X , since $0 \in A, \mu(0)=1 \geq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$. Let $x, y, z \in X$,

If $y \notin A$, then $\mu(y) = 0$, and so $\mu(x * z) \leq 0 = \min\{\mu(x * (y * z)), \mu(y)\}$.

If $x * z \notin A$, and $y \in A$, then $(x * (y * z)) \notin A$ (since A is BCK-ideal).

Thus $\mu(x * z) = 0 = \min\{\mu(x * (y * z)), \mu(y)\}$. Hence μ is a fuzzy BCK-ideal of X . ■

Theorem 3.3.11. Let $(X; *, 0)$ and $(Y; *, 0')$ be two BCK-algebras and $f : (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, 0')$ be a homomorphism, then

- 1) If I is a fuzzy BCK-ideal of X , then $f(I)$ is a fuzzy BCK-ideal of Y , where f is onto.
- 2) If J is a fuzzy BCK-ideal of Y , then $f^{-1}(J)$ is a fuzzy BCK-ideal of X .

Proof.

1) Let I be a fuzzy BCK-ideal of X that mean $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ and

$\mu(x * z) \geq \min\{\mu(x * (y * z)), \mu(y)\}$, for all $x, y, z \in X$. Clearly, $0' \in f(I)$, then $\mu(f(0)) \geq \mu(f(x))$ for all $x \in X$, and let $x, y, z \in f(I)$ that means $x = f(a), y = f(b), z = f(c)$ for some $a, b, c \in I$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(x * z) &= \mu(f(a) * f(c)) \geq \min\{\mu(f(a * (b * c))), \mu(f(b))\} \\ &= \min\{\mu((f(a) * f(b)) * f(c)), \mu(f(b))\} \\ &= \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(y)\}, \text{ for all } x, y \in Y. \end{aligned}$$

Hence $f(I)$ is a fuzzy BCK-ideal of Y .

2) Let J be a fuzzy BCK-ideal of Y that mean $\mu(f(0)) = \mu(0') \geq \mu(f(x))$ and

$\mu(f(x)) \geq \min\{\mu(f(x) * (f(y) * f(z))), \mu(f(y))\}$, for all $x, y, z \in Y$. Clearly, $0' \in f(J)$ and let $a, b \in f^{-1}(J)$ that means $a = f^{-1}(x), b = f^{-1}(y), c = f^{-1}(z)$, for some $x, y, z \in J$, then $\mu(a * c) = \mu(f^{-1}(x) * f^{-1}(z)) \geq \min\{\mu(f^{-1}(x * (y * z))), \mu(f^{-1}(y))\}$

$$\begin{aligned} &= \min\{\mu((f^{-1}(x) * f^{-1}(y)) * f^{-1}(z)), \mu(f^{-1}(y))\} \\ &= \min\{\mu((a * (b * c))), \mu(b)\}, \text{ for all } a, b \in X. \end{aligned}$$

Hence $f^{-1}(J)$ is a fuzzy BCK-ideal of X . ■

CHAPTER TWO

SECTION FIVE

2.5. BCK-ideals of BCK-algebras

The notion of BCK-ideals in BCK-algebras was introduced by K. Iséki in 1975.

DEFINITION 2.5.1. Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCK-algebra and let I be a nonempty subset of X . Then I is called to be a **BCK-ideal of X** if, for all $x, y \in X$,

- (i) $0 \in I$,
- (ii) $x * (y * z) \in I$ and $y \in I$ imply $x * z \in I$.

EXAMPLE 2.5.2. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ in which $*$ is given by the table

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	2	0
2	2	1	0	0
3	3	2	1	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra, it has BCK-ideals $\{0, 1\}$, $\{0, 1, 2\}$ and X .

Proposition 2.5.3. Let $(X; *, 0)$ be any BCK-algebra and let \bar{X} be the Iséki's extension of X . Then X is a BCK-ideal of \bar{X} .

Proof. H.W.

Proposition 2.5.4. If I is a BCK-ideal of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, then I is ideal of X .

Proof. since $x * (y * z) \in I$ and $y \in I$ implies $x * z \in I$, put $z=0$, then $x * (y * 0) = x * y \in I$ and $y \in I$ implies $x * 0 = x \in I$, thus I is ideal of X

Proposition 2.5.5. If I is a BCK-ideal of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, then I is subalgebra of X .

Proof. By Proposition (2.5.4), I is ideal of X . and by Proposition (2.1.4), thus I is subalgebra of X .

CHAPTER TWO SECTION SIX

2.6. BCK-Filters of BCK-algebras

A BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, if there is a special element e of a BCK-algebra X satisfying $x \leq e$ for all $x \in X$, then e is called **unit** of X . A BCK-algebra with unit is said to be **bounded**. In a bounded BCK-algebra X , we denote $e * x$ by x^* for every $x \in X$. In a bounded BCK-algebra, we have

- 1) $e^* = 0$ and $0^* = e$.
- 2) $y \leq x$ implies $x^* \leq y^*$.
- 3) $x^* * y^* \leq y * x$.

Definition 2.6.1. Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a bounded BCK-algebra and let F be a nonempty subset of X . Then F is called to be a **BCK-filter of X** if, for all $x, y \in X$,

- (i) $e \in F$,
- (ii) $(x^* * y^*)^* \in F$ and $y \in F$ imply $x \in F$.

$\{e\}$ and X are two **trivial BCK-filters of X** .

Example 2.6.2. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2\}$ in which $*$ is given by the table:

*	0	1	2
0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0
2	2	2	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra with unite 2, and $X, \{1,2\}, \{0,2\}$ are all BCK-filters of X .

Example 2.6.3. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3\}$ in which $*$ is given by the table

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	3	0
2	2	1	0	0
3	3	2	1	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra with unite 3, it has two BCK-filters $\{1,2,3\}$ and $\{0,1,2,3\}$.

Lemma 2.6.4. Let $(X; *, 0)$ be any bounded BCK-algebra and F is BCK-filter of X . $x \in F$ if and only if $(x^*)^* = x^{**} \in F$.

Proposition 2.6.5. Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a bounded BCK-algebra and F be a subset of X . If $e * x \in F, \forall x \in X$, then F is BCK-filter.

Proof. H.W.

Proposition 2.6.6. Let $(X; *, 0)$ be any bounded BCK-algebra and let \bar{X} be the Iséki's extension of X . Then every subset contains 0 and e is BCK-filter of \bar{X} .

Proof. H.W.

Definition 2.6.7. A subset F of a bounded BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is said to be **complete BCK-filter of X** (c-BCK-filter), if,

- (i) $e \in F$,
- (ii) $(x^* * y^*)^* \in F, \forall y \in F$ imply $x \in F$.

Proposition 2.6.8. If f is a homomorphism from BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ into BCK-algebra $(Y; *', 0')$, then f is isotone i.e, $x \leq y$ implies $f(x) \leq f(y)$.

Proof. H.W.

Proposition 2.6.9. Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a bounded BCK-algebra. If I is a c-BCK-filter of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, then I is BCK-filter of X .

Proof. H.W.

Lemma 2.6.10. Suppose f is an epimorphism from bounded BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ into bounded BCK-algebra $(Y; *', 0')$, then $f(e_x) = e_y$ where e_x, e_y are the units of X and Y respectively.

Proof. H.W.

Proposition 2.6.11. Let f be an epimorphism from bounded BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ into bounded BCK-algebra $(Y; *', 0')$, then

- 1) $f(x^*) = (f(x))^*$, for all $x \in X$, and
- 2) $f^{-1}(y^*) = (f^{-1}(y))^*$, for all $y \in Y$, for all If f is isomorphism .

Proof.

- 1) $f(x^*) = f(e_x * x) = f(e_x) *' f(x) = e_y *' f(x) = (f(x))^*$, by Lemma (2.6.10).
- 2) $f^{-1}(y^*) = f^{-1}(e_y *' y) = f^{-1}(e_y) * f^{-1}(y) = e_x * f^{-1}(y) = (f^{-1}(y))^*$, by Lemma(2.6.10).

CHAPTER THREE

SECTION ONE

3.1. Fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of BCK-algebras

The notion of fuzzy BCK-subalgebras in BCK-algebras was introduced by O. G. Xi at Fuzzy BCK-algebras in 1991 and homomorphisms of it.

Definition 3.1.1. Let X be a non-empty set, a **fuzzy subset** μ of X is a function $\mu: X \rightarrow [0,1]$.

Definition 3.1.2. Let μ be a fuzzy subset of a set X . For $t \in [0, 1]$, the set $\mu_t = U(\mu, t) = \{x \in X \mid \mu(x) \geq t\}$, is called **upper level cut** (level subset) of μ and the set $L(\mu, t) = \{x \in X \mid \mu(x) \leq t\}$ is called **lower level cut of μ** .

Definition 3.1.3. Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCK-algebra. A fuzzy subset μ of X is called a **fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of X** if for all $x, y \in X$, $\mu(x * y) \geq \min \{ \mu(x), \mu(y) \}$.

Example 3.1.4. Let $X = \{0,1,2,3\}$ in which the operation $*$ is given by:

*	0	1	2	3
0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0
2	2	2	0	1
3	3	3	3	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra. Define a fuzzy subset $\mu: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ by $\mu(0) = 0.8$, $\mu(1) = \mu(2) = \mu(3) = 0.6$. Routine calculation gives that μ is fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of X .

Proposition 3.1.5. If μ is fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, then $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$.

Proof. Since μ be fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of X and $x \in X$, then

$\mu(0) = \mu(x * x) \geq \min \{\mu(x), \mu(x)\}$, then $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$.

Proposition 3.1.6. Every fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is order reversing.

Proof. Let μ be fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of X and let $x, y \in X$ be such that $x \leq y$, then $x * y = 0$ and $\mu(x * y) \geq \min \{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$, then $\mu(0) \geq \min\{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}$.

Theorem 3.1.7. A fuzzy subset μ of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is a fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of X if and only if $\mu_t \neq \emptyset$ is a BCK-subalgebra of X .

Proof: Suppose that μ is a fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of X and $\mu_t \neq \emptyset$, for any $t \in (0,1]$, there exists $x \in \mu_t$ so that $\mu(x) \geq t$. Let $x, y \in X$ be such that $x \in \mu_t$ and $y \in \mu_t$. Using Definition (2.1.1), we know that $\mu(x * y) \geq \min \{\mu(x), \mu(y)\} \geq \min\{t, t\} = t$, thus $x * y \in \mu_t$. Hence μ_t is a BCK-subalgebra of X .

Conversely, suppose that $\mu_t \neq \emptyset$ is a BCK-subalgebra of X , for every $t \in (0,1]$. Now, we need to show that μ satisfies Definition (2.1.1). If not, then there exist $a, b \in X$ such that $\mu(a * b) < \min \{\mu(a), \mu(b)\}$. Taking $t = 1/2 (\mu(a * b) + \min \{\mu(a), \mu(b)\})$, then we have $\mu(a * b) < t < \min \{\mu(a), \mu(b)\}$. Hence $a \in \mu_t$ and $b \in \mu_t$, but $a * b \notin \mu_t$ which means that μ_t is not a BCK-subalgebra of X . this is contradiction. Therefore μ is a fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of X .

Now, we introduce the concept homomorphism of fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of BCK-algebra, also we give examples and results of it.

Definition 3.1.8. Let $(X; *, 0)$ and $(Y; *, 0')$ be two BCK-algebras and f be a mapping from the set $(X; *, 0)$ to a set $(Y; *, 0')$. If μ is a fuzzy subset of X , then the fuzzy subset β of Y defined by: $f(\mu)(x) = \begin{cases} \sup\{\mu(x): x \in f^{-1}(y)\} & \text{if } f^{-1}(y) = \{x \in X; f(x) = y\} \neq \emptyset \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$ is called **the image of μ under f** .

Similarly, if β is a fuzzy subset of Y , then the fuzzy subset defined by $\mu(x) = \beta(f(x))$, for all $x \in X$, is called **the pre-image of β under f** .

Theorem 3.1.9. Let $(X; *, 0)$ and $(Y; *, 0')$ be two BCK-algebras and

$f : (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, 0')$ be a homomorphism, then

- 3) If μ is a fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of X , then $f(\mu)$ is a fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of Y , where f is onto.
- 4) If β is a fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of Y , then $f^{-1}(\beta)$ is a fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of X .

Proof.

- 3) Let μ be a fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of X , then $\mu(a * b) \geq \min \{\mu(a), \mu(b)\}$, for all $a, b \in X$ and let $x, y \in Y$ that means $x = f(a)$, $y = f(b)$, for some $a, b \in X$. Then

$$\mu(x * 'y) = \mu(f(a) * 'f(b)) = \mu(f(a * b)) \geq \min \{\mu(f(a)), \mu(f(b))\} = \min \{\mu(x), \mu(y)\}. \text{ Hence } f(\mu) \text{ is a fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of } Y.$$

- 4) Let β be a fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of Y , then $\mu(a * b) \geq \min \{\mu(a), \mu(b)\}$, for all $a, b \in Y$ and let $x, y \in f^{-1}(X)$ that means $x = f^{-1}(a)$, $y = f^{-1}(b)$, for some $a, b \in X$, since $x, y \in f^{-1}(\beta)$ that means $a = f(x)$, $b = f(y)$, for some $a, b \in X$. Then

$$\mu(x * 'y) = \mu(f^{-1}(a) * 'f^{-1}(b)) = \mu(f^{-1}(a * b)) \geq \min \{\mu(f^{-1}(a)), \mu(f^{-1}(b))\}$$

$= \min \{ \mu(x), \mu(y) \}$. Hence $f^{-1}(\beta)$ is a fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of X .

CHAPTER THREE

SECTION TWO

3.2. Fuzzy Ideals of BCK-algebras

The notion of Fuzzy ideals in BCK-algebras was introduced by O. G. Xi at Fuzzy BCK-algebras in 1991. The ideal theory plays a fundamental role for the general development of BCK-algebras. The concepts of ideals, quotient algebras, and homomorphisms are all closely related. These will be the subject of this and next chapters.

Definition 3.2.1. Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCK -algebra. A fuzzy subset μ of X is called a **fuzzy ideal of X** if it satisfies the following conditions: for all $x, y \in X$,

- (1) $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$.
- (2) $\mu(x) \geq \min \{ \mu(x * y), \mu(y) \}$.

Example 3.2.2. Let $X = \{0,1,2,3,4\}$ in which the operation $*$ is given by:

*	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0	0
2	2	0	0	0	0
3	3	3	3	0	0
4	4	4	4	4	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra. Define a fuzzy subset $\mu: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ by $\mu(0) = 0.8, \mu(1) = \mu(2) = 0.7, \mu(3) = \mu(4) = 0.6$. Routine calculation gives that μ is fuzzy ideal of BCK-algebra X .

Theorem 3.2.3. Let A be a nonempty subset of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ and μ be a fuzzy subset of X such that μ is into $\{0, 1\}$, so that μ is the characteristic function of A . Then μ is a fuzzy ideal in X if and only if, A is an ideal of X . ($\mu: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ by $\mu(x) = \begin{cases} 1 & \text{if } x \in A \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$.)

Proof. Assume that μ is a fuzzy ideal in X , since $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$, clearly we have $\mu(0)=1$, and so $0 \in A$.

Let $x * y \in A$ and $y \in A$, since μ is a fuzzy ideal of X , it follows that $\mu(x) \geq \min \{ \mu(x * y), \mu(y) \}$, for all $x, y \in X$, and $\mu(x)=1$. This mean that $x \in A$. i.e. A is an ideal of X .

Conversely suppose A is an ideal of X , since $0 \in A, \mu(0)=1 \geq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$. Let $x, y \in X$, If $y \notin A$, or $x * y \notin A$, then $\mu(y) = 0$ or $\mu(x * y) = 0$, and so $\mu(x) \geq 0 = \min \{ \mu(x * y), \mu(y) \}$. If $x * y \in A$, and $y \in A$, then $x \in A$ (since A is an ideal). $\mu(x) = 1 = \min \{ \mu(x * y), \mu(y) \}$. Hence μ is a fuzzy ideal of X . ■

Theorem 3.2.4. Let μ be a fuzzy subset of BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. μ is a fuzzy ideal of X if and only if, for every $t \in [0,1], \mu_t$ is an ideal of X .

Proof. Assume that μ is a fuzzy ideal of X , by Definition (3.2.1(1)), we have $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ for all $x \in X$ therefore $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x) \geq t$, for any $x \in \mu_t$ and so $0 \in \mu_t$.

Let $x, y \in X$ be such that $(x * y) \in \mu_t$ and $y \in \mu_t$, then $\mu(x * y) \geq t$ and $\mu(y) \geq t$, since μ is a fuzzy ideal, it follows that $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(y)\} \geq t$ and we have that $x \in \mu_t$. Hence μ_t is an ideal of X .

Conversely, we only need to show that (1) and (2) in Definition (3.2.1) are true. If (1) is false, then there exist $x' \in X$ such that $\mu(0) < \mu(x')$. If we take $t' = (\mu(x') + \mu(0))/2$, then $\mu(0) < t'$ and $0 \leq t' < \mu(x') \leq 1$, then $x' \in \mu_{t'}$ and $\mu \neq \emptyset$. As $\mu_{t'}$ is ideal of X , we have $0 \in \mu_{t'}$, and so $\mu(0) \geq t'$. This is a contradiction.

Now, assume (2) is not true, then there exist $x', y' \in X$ such that, $\mu(x') < \min\{\mu(x' * y'), \mu(y')\}$. Putting $t' = (\mu(x') + \min\{\mu(x' * y'), \mu(y')\})/2$, then $\mu(x') < t'$ and $0 \leq t' < \min\{\mu(x' * y'), \mu(y')\} \leq 1$, hence $\mu(x' * y') > t'$ and $\mu(y') > t'$, which imply that $(x' * y') \in \mu_{t'}$ and $y' \in \mu_{t'}$. Since $\mu_{t'}$ is an ideal, it follows that $x' \in \mu_{t'}$ and that $\mu(x') \geq t'$, this is also a contradiction. Hence μ is a fuzzy ideal of X . ■

Corollary 3.2.5. Let μ be a fuzzy subset of BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. If μ is a fuzzy ideal, then for every $t \in \text{Im}(\mu)$, μ_t is an ideal of X , when $\mu_t \neq \emptyset$.

Proof. H.W.

Proposition 3.2.6. Every fuzzy ideal of BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is a fuzzy BCK-subalgebra of X .

Proof. Since μ is a fuzzy ideal of BCK-algebra X , then by Theorem (3.2.4), for every $t \in [0,1]$, μ_t is ideal of X . By Theorem (2.1.4), for every $t \in [0,1]$, μ_t is subalgebra of X . Hence μ is a fuzzy subalgebra of BCK-algebra X by Proposition (3.1.7). ■

Theorem 3.2.7. Let A be an ideal of BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. Then for any fixed number (t) in an open interval $(0,1)$, there exists a fuzzy ideal μ of X such that $\mu_t = A$.

Proof. Define $\mu: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ by $\mu(x) = \begin{cases} t & \text{if } x \in A \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$. Where (t) is a fixed number in $(0, 1]$.

Clearly, $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$. Let $x, y \in X$.

If $y \notin A$, or $x * y \notin A$, then $\mu(y) = 0$ or $\mu(x * y) = 0$, and so $\mu(x) \geq 0 = \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(y)\}$. If $x * y \in A$, and $y \in A$, then $x \in A$ (since A is an ideal). $\mu(x) = t = \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(y)\}$. Hence μ is a fuzzy ideal of X . It is clear that $\mu_t = A$. ■

Theorem 3.2.8. Let μ be a fuzzy ideal of BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ and let μ_{t_1}, μ_{t_2} be two level ideals of μ , where $t_1 < t_2$, then the following are equivalent.

E₁) $\mu_{t_1} = \mu_{t_2}$.

E₂) There is no $x \in X$ such that $t_1 \leq \mu(x) < t_2$.

Proof. Assume that $\mu_{t_1} = \mu_{t_2}$, for $t_1 < t_2$ and that there exist $x \in X$ such that $t_1 \leq \mu(x) < t_2$.

Then μ_{t_2} is proper subset of μ_{t_1} , a contradiction. Hence $t_1 \leq \mu(x) < t_2$.

Conversely suppose that there is no $x \in X$ such that $t_1 \leq \mu(x) < t_2$. It follows from $t_1 < t_2$, that $\mu_{t_1} \subset \mu_{t_2}$. Let $x \in \mu_{t_2}$. Then $\mu(x) \geq t_2 > t_1$, because $\mu(x)$ does not lie between t_1 and t_2 . Hence $x \in \mu_{t_1}$, this implies that $\mu_{t_2} \subset \mu_{t_1}$. Therefore, $\mu_{t_1} = \mu_{t_2}$. ■

Theorem 3.2.9. Let $(X; *, 0)$ and $(Y; *, 0')$ be two BCK-algebras and $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, 0')$ be a homomorphism, then

- 3) If I is a fuzzy ideal of X , then $f(I)$ is a fuzzy ideal of Y , where f is onto.
 4) If J is a fuzzy ideal of Y , then $f^{-1}(J)$ is a fuzzy ideal of X .

Proof.

3) Let I be a fuzzy ideal of X that mean $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ and $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(y)\}$, for all $x, y \in X$. Clearly, $0' \in f(I)$, then $\mu(f(0)) \geq \mu(f(x))$ for all $x \in X$, and let $x, y \in f(I)$ that means $x = f(a)$, $y = f(b)$, for some $a, b \in I$, then $\mu(x) = \mu(f(a)) \geq \min\{\mu(f(a * b)), \mu(f(b))\}$
 $= \min\{\mu(f(a) * f(b)), \mu(f(b))\}$
 $= \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(y)\}$, for all $x, y \in Y$.

Hence $f(I)$ is a fuzzy ideal of Y .

4) Let J be a fuzzy ideal of Y that mean $\mu(f(0)) = \mu(0') \geq \mu(f(x))$ and $\mu(f(x)) \geq \min\{\mu(f(x) * f(y)), \mu(f(y))\}$, for all $x, y \in Y$. Clearly, $0' \in f(J)$ and let $a, b \in f^{-1}(J)$ that means $a = f^{-1}(x)$, $b = f^{-1}(y)$, for some $x, y \in J$, then $\mu(a) = \mu(f^{-1}(x)) \geq \min\{\mu(f^{-1}(x * y)), \mu(f^{-1}(y))\}$
 $= \min\{\mu(f^{-1}(x) * f^{-1}(y)), \mu(f^{-1}(y))\}$
 $= \min\{\mu((a * b)), \mu(b)\}$, for all $a, b \in X$. Hence $f^{-1}(J)$ is a fuzzy ideal of X . ■

CHAPTER THREE

SECTION THREE

3.3. Fuzzy BCK-ideals of BCK-algebras

Definition 3.3.1. Let $(X; *, 0)$ be a BCK-algebra. A fuzzy subset μ of X is called a **fuzzy BCK-ideal of X** if it satisfies the following conditions: for all $x, y, z \in X$,

- (1) $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$.
 (2) $\mu(x * z) \geq \min\{\mu(x * (y * z)), \mu(y)\}$.

Example 3.3.2. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ in which the operation $*$ is given by:

*	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	1	2	3	4
1	0	0	0	3	4
2	0	0	0	3	4
3	0	0	1	0	4
4	0	0	0	0	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is an BCK-algebra. Define a fuzzy subset $\mu: X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ by $\mu(0) = 0.6$, $\mu(1) = \mu(2) = 0.5$, $\mu(3) = \mu(4) = 0.4$. Routine calculation gives that μ is fuzzy BCK-ideal of BCK-algebra X .

Theorem 3.3.3. Let A be a nonempty subset of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ and μ be a fuzzy subset of X such that μ is into $\{0, 1\}$, so that μ is the characteristic function of A . Then μ is a fuzzy BCK-ideal in X if and only if, A is a BCK-ideal of X .

Proof. Assume that μ is a fuzzy BCK-ideal in X , since $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$, clearly we have $\mu(0) = 1$, and so $0 \in A$.

Let $(x * (y * z)) \in A$ and $y \in A$, since μ is a fuzzy BCK-ideal of X , it follows that $\mu(x * z) \geq \min\{\mu(x * (y * z)), \mu(y)\}$, for all $x, y, z \in X$, and $\mu(x)=1$. This mean that $\mu(x) \in A$. i.e. A is a BCK-ideal of X .

Conversely suppose A is a BCK-ideal of X , since $0 \in A$, $\mu(0)=1 \geq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$. Let $x, y, z \in X$, if $y \notin A$, then $\mu(y) = 0$, and so $\mu(x * z) \geq 0 = \min\{\mu(x * (y * z)), \mu(y)\}$. If $x * (y * z) \in A$, and $y \in A$, then $x * y \notin A$ (since A is a BCK-ideal). Thus $\mu(x * z) = 0 = \min\{\mu(x * (y * z)), \mu(y)\}$. Hence μ is a fuzzy BCK-ideal of X . ■

Lemma 3.3.4. Let μ be a fuzzy BCK-ideal of BCK-algebra X and if $x \leq y$, then $\mu(x) \geq \mu(y)$, for all $x, y \in X$.

Proof. Assume that $x \leq y$, then $x * y = 0$, this together with $x * 0 = x$ and $\mu(0) \geq \mu(y)$, we get $\mu(x * 0) = \mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(x * (y * 0)), \mu(y)\} = \min\{\mu(0 * 0), \mu(y)\} = \min\{\mu(0), \mu(y)\} = \mu(y)$. ■

Theorem 3.3.5. Let μ be a fuzzy subset of BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. μ is a fuzzy BCK-ideal of X if and only if, for every $t \in [0,1]$, μ_t is an BCK-ideal of X .

Proof. Assume that μ is a fuzzy BCK-ideal of X , by Definition (3.3.1(1)), we have $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ for all $x \in X$ therefore $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x) \geq t$ for $x \in \mu_t$ and so $0 \in \mu_t$.

Let $x, y, z \in X$ be such that $(x * (y * z)) \in \mu_t$ and $y \in \mu_t$, then $\mu(x * (y * z)) \geq t$ and $\mu(y) \geq t$, since μ is a fuzzy BCK-ideal, it follows that $\mu(x * z) \geq \min\{\mu(x * (y * z)), \mu(y)\} \geq t$ and we have that $x * z \in \mu_t$. Hence μ_t is an BCK-ideal of X .

Conversely, we only need to show that (1) and (2) in Definition (3.3.1) are true. If (1) is false, then there exist $x' \in X$ such that $\mu(0) < \mu(x')$. If we take $t' = (\mu(x') + \mu(0))/2$, then $\mu(0) < t'$ and $0 \leq t' < \mu(x') \leq 1$, then $x' \in \mu$ and $\mu \neq \emptyset$. As $\mu_{t'}$ is a-ideal of X , we have $0 \in \mu_{t'}$ and so $\mu(0) \geq t'$. This is a contradiction.

Now, assume (2) is not true, then there exist $x', y', z' \in X$ such that, $\mu(x' * z') < \min\{\mu(x' * (y' * z')), \mu(y')\}$. Putting $t' = (\mu(x' * z') + \min\{\mu(x' * (y' * z')), \mu(y')\})/2$, then $\mu(x' * z') < t'$ and $0 \leq t' < \min\{\mu(x' * (y' * z')), \mu(y')\} \leq 1$, hence $\mu(x' * (y' * z')) > t'$ and $\mu(y') > t'$, which imply that $(x' * (y' * z')) \in \mu_{t'}$ and $(y') \in \mu_{t'}$. Since $\mu_{t'}$ is an ideal, it follows that $(x' * z') \in \mu_{t'}$ and that $\mu(x' * z') \geq t'$, this is also a contradiction. Hence μ is a fuzzy BCK-ideal of X . ■

Corollary 3.3.6. Let μ be a fuzzy subset of BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. If μ is a fuzzy BCK-ideal, then for every $t \in \text{Im}(\mu)$, μ_t is a BCK-ideal of X , when $\mu_t \neq \emptyset$.

Proof. H.W.

Proposition 3.3.7. Every fuzzy BCK-ideal of BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is a fuzzy ideal of X .

Proof. Since μ is a fuzzy BCK-ideal of BCK-algebra X , then by Theorem (3.3.5), for every $t \in [0,1]$, μ_t is BCK-ideal of X . By Theorem (2.6.4), for every $t \in [0,1]$, μ_t is ideal of X . Hence μ is a fuzzy ideal of BCK-algebra X by Proposition (3.1.7). ■

Proposition 3.3.8. Every fuzzy ideal of BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is a fuzzy subalgebra of X .

Proof. Since μ is a fuzzy BCK-ideal of BCK-algebra X , then by Theorem (3.3.5), for every $t \in [0,1]$, μ_t is BCK-ideal of X . By Theorem (2.6.5), for every $t \in [0,1]$, μ_t is subalgebra of X . Hence μ is a fuzzy ideal of BCK-algebra X by Proposition (3.1.7). ■

Theorem 3.3.9. Let A be a BCK-ideal of BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. Then for any fixed number (t) in an open interval $(0,1)$, there exists a fuzzy BCK-ideal μ of X such that $\mu_t = A$.

Proof. Define $\mu: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ by $\mu(x) = \begin{cases} t & \text{if } x \in A \\ 0 & \text{otherwise} \end{cases}$. Where (t) is a fixed number in $(0,$

1).

Clearly, $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$. Let $x, y \in X$. If $(x * (y * z)) \notin A$, then $\mu(x * (y * z)) = 0$ and so $\mu(x * z) \geq 0 = \min\{\mu(x * (y * z)), \mu(y)\}$.

If $(x * (y * z)) \in A$, then clearly $\mu(x * z) \geq \min\{\mu(x * (y * z)), \mu(y)\}$.

If $(x) \notin A, (x * y) \in A$, then $y \notin A$, since A is ideal. Thus

$\mu(x * z) = 0 = \min\{\mu(x * (y * z)), \mu(y)\}$. Hence μ is a fuzzy BCK-ideal of X . It is clear that $\mu_t = A$. ■

Theorem 3.3.10. Let A be a nonempty subset of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ and μ be a fuzzy subset of X such that μ is into $\{0, 1\}$, so that μ is the characteristic function of A . Then μ is a fuzzy BCK-ideal of X if and only if, A is BCK-ideal of X .

Proof. Assume that μ is a fuzzy BCK-ideal in X , since $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ for all $x \in X$, clearly we have $\mu(0)=1$, and so $0 \in A$. Let $x, y, z \in X$ be such that $(x * (y * z)) \in A$ and $y \in A$, since μ is a fuzzy BCK-ideal of X , it follows that

$\mu(x * z) \geq \min\{\mu(x * (y * z)), \mu(y)\} = 1$, and $\mu(x * z) = 1$.

This mean that $x * z \in A$, i.e., A is BCK-ideal of X .

Conversely, suppose A is BCK-ideal of X , since $0 \in A, \mu(0) = 1 \geq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$. Let $x, y, z \in X$,

If $y \notin A$, then $\mu(y) = 0$, and so $\mu(x * z) \leq 0 = \min\{\mu(x * (y * z)), \mu(y)\}$.

If $x * z \notin A$, and $y \in A$, then $(x * (y * z)) \notin A$ (since A is BCK-ideal).

Thus $\mu(x * z) = 0 = \min\{\mu(x * (y * z)), \mu(y)\}$. Hence μ is a fuzzy BCK-ideal of X . ■

Theorem 3.3.11. Let $(X; *, 0)$ and $(Y; *, 0')$ be two BCK-algebras and

$f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, 0')$ be a homomorphism, then

- 3) If I is a fuzzy BCK-ideal of X , then $f(I)$ is a fuzzy BCK-ideal of Y , where f is onto.
- 4) If J is a fuzzy BCK-ideal of Y , then $f^{-1}(J)$ is a fuzzy BCK-ideal of X .

Proof.

3) Let I be a fuzzy BCK-ideal of X that mean $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ and

$\mu(x * z) \geq \min\{\mu(x * (y * z)), \mu(y)\}$, for all $x, y, z \in X$. Clearly, $0' \in f(I)$, then $\mu(f(0)) \geq \mu(f(x))$ for all $x \in X$, and let $x, y, z \in f(I)$ that means $x = f(a), y = f(b), z = f(c)$ for some $a, b, c \in I$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(x * z) &= \mu(f(a) * f(c)) \geq \min\{\mu(f(a * (b * c))), \mu(f(b))\} \\ &= \min\{\mu((f(a) * f(b)) * f(c)), \mu(f(b))\} \\ &= \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(y)\}, \text{ for all } x, y \in Y. \end{aligned}$$

Hence $f(I)$ is a fuzzy BCK-ideal of Y .

4) Let J be a fuzzy BCK-ideal of Y that mean $\mu(f(0)) = \mu(0') \geq \mu(f(x))$ and

$\mu(f(x)) \geq \min\{\mu(f(x) * f(y) * f(z)), \mu(f(y))\}$, for all $x, y, z \in Y$. Clearly, $0' \in f(J)$ and let $a, b \in f^{-1}(J)$ that means $a = f^{-1}(x), b = f^{-1}(y), c = f^{-1}(z)$, for some $x, y, z \in J$, then $\mu(a * c) = \mu(f^{-1}(x) * f^{-1}(z)) \geq \min\{\mu(f^{-1}(x * (y * z))), \mu(f^{-1}(y))\}$

$$= \min \{ \mu((f^{-1}(x) * (f^{-1}(y) * f^{-1}(z))), \mu(f^{-1}(y)) \}$$

$$= \min \{ \mu((a * (b * c)), \mu(b)) \}, \text{ for all } a, b \in X. \text{ Hence } f(J) \text{ is a fuzzy BCK-ideal of } X. \blacksquare$$

CHAPTER THREE

SECTION FOUR

3.4. Implicative Fuzzy Ideals of BCK-algebras

In this section, we discuss the notion of sub-implicative ideals, and we give some characterizations of this concept.

Definition 3.4.1. A nonempty subset μ of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is called a **implicative fuzzy ideal** (briefly IF-ideal) of X , if for all $x, y, z \in X$,

$$(IF_1) \mu(0) \geq \mu(x),$$

$$(IF_2) \mu(x) \geq \min \{ \mu((x * y) * x * z), \mu(z) \}.$$

Example 3.4.2. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ in which the operation $*$ is given by:

*	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0	0
2	2	1	0	0	0
3	3	1	1	0	0
4	4	3	2	1	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra. Define a fuzzy subset $\mu: X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ by $\mu(0) = t_0$, $\mu(1) = \mu(2) = t_1$, $\mu(3) = t_2$ and $\mu(4) = t_3$, where $t_0, t_1, t_2, t_3 \in [0, 1]$ with $t_0 > t_1 > t_2 > t_3$. Routine calculation gives that μ is an IF-ideal of BCK-algebra X .

Proposition 3.4.3. Every IF-ideal of an BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is order reversing.

Proof. Let μ be an IF-ideal of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ and let $x, y, z \in X$ be such that $x \leq z$, then $x * z = 0$ this together with $x * 0 = x$, $x * x = 0$ and $\mu(0) \geq \mu(z)$. Put $y = 0$ in (IF_1) $\mu(x) \geq \min \{ \mu((x * y) * x * z), \mu(z) \}$, let $y = x$, then

$$\mu(x) \geq \min \{ \mu((x * x) * x * z), \mu(z) \}$$

$$\mu(x) \geq \min \{ \mu(x * z), \mu(z) \} = \min \{ \mu(0), \mu(z) \} = \mu(z).$$

Proposition 3.4.4. Let μ be an IF-ideal of an BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, if the inequality $x * y \leq z$ hold in X , Then $\mu(x) \geq \min \{ \mu(y), \mu(z) \}$.

Proof. Let μ be an IF-ideal of X and let $x, y, z \in X$ be such that $x * y \leq z$, then $(x * y) * z = 0$ or $(x * z) * y = 0$, i.e., $x * z \leq y$, we get $\mu(x * z) \geq \mu(y)$ --- (3).

By (SIF_2) $\mu((x * y) * x) \geq \min \{ \mu(z * ((x * y) * x)), \mu(z) \}$, let $y = x$, then

$$\mu((x * x) * x) \geq \min \{ \mu(z * ((x * x) * x)), \mu(z) \} = \min \{ \mu(z * x), \mu(z) \}. \text{ i.e.,}$$

$$\mu(x) \geq \min \{ \mu(z * x), \mu(z) \} \geq \min \{ \mu(y), \mu(z) \}, \text{ by (3).}$$

Proposition 3.4.5. If $(X; *, 0)$ is implicative BCK-algebra, then every fuzzy ideal of X is an IF-ideal of X .

Proof. Let μ be a fuzzy ideal of X , then by Definition (3.2.1(2)), for all $y, z \in X$, $\mu(y) \geq \min\{\mu(y * z), \mu(z)\}$. Substituting $(x * y) * x$ for y in Definition (3.2.1(2)), $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(((x * y) * x) * z), \mu(z)\}$, but BCK-algebra is implicative, i.e., $(x) = (x * y) * (y * x^2)$, hence

$$\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(((x * y) * x) * z), \mu(z)\} = \min\{\mu(((x * y) * x) * z), \mu(z)\}.$$

Which shows that μ is an IF-ideal of X .

Theorem 3.4.6. Every IF-ideal is a fuzzy ideal, but the converse does not hold.

Proof. Let μ be an IF-ideal of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$; put $x = y$ in (IF_2) , we get

$\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(((x * x) * x) * z), \mu(z)\}$, then $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(x * z), \mu(z)\}$, for all $x, z \in X$. Hence μ is a fuzzy ideal of X .

The following example shows that the converse of Theorem (3.4.6) may not be true.

Example 3.4.7. Let $X = \{0, a, b, c, d\}$ in which the operation $*$ is given by:

*	0	a	b	c	d
0	0	0	0	0	0
a	a	0	0	0	0
b	b	a	0	0	0
c	c	c	c	0	0
d	d	d	d	d	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra. Define a fuzzy subset $\mu: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ by $\mu(0) = 0.7$, $\mu(a) = \mu(b) = \mu(c) = \mu(d) = 0.2$, we get for $z = 0$, $x = a$ and $y = b$. Then $\mu((a * c) * b) = \mu(a) = 0.2 \leq 0.7 = \min\{\mu(c * (a * c) * b), \mu(0)\} = \mu(0)$

Proposition 3.4.8. The intersection of any set of implicative fuzzy ideals of BCK-algebra X is also implicative fuzzy ideal.

Proof. Let $\{\mu_i : i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of implicative fuzzy ideals of BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, then for any $x, y, z \in X$, $(\cap_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(0) = \inf\{\mu_i(0)\} \geq \inf\{\mu_i(x)\} = (\cap_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(x)$ and

$$(\cap_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(x) = \inf\{\mu_i(x)\}$$

$$\geq \inf\{\min\{\mu_i(((x * y) * x) * z), \mu_i(z)\}\}$$

$$= \min\{\inf\{\mu_i(((x * y) * x) * z), \inf\{\mu_i(z)\}\}$$

$$= \min\{(\cap_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)((x * y) * x) * z, (\cap_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i(z))\}. \text{ This completes the proof.}$$

Proposition 3.4.9. Let $\{\mu_i : i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of implicative fuzzy ideals of an BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ where $\mu_i \subseteq \mu_{i+1}$, for all $i \in \Lambda$. Then $\cup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i$ is implicative fuzzy ideal of X .

Proof. Let $\{\mu_i : i \in \Lambda\}$ be a family of implicative fuzzy ideals of X . We will show that $\cup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i$ is an ideal of X . , $(\cup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(0) = \sup\{\mu_i(0)\} \geq \sup\{\mu_i(x)\} = (\cup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(x)$. Let

$x, y, z \in \cup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i$.

$$\text{and } (\cup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(x) = \sup\{\mu_i(x)\}$$

$$\geq \sup\{\min\{\mu_i(((x * y) * x) * z), \mu_i(z)\}\}$$

$$\geq \min \{ \sup (\mu_i ((x * y) * x) * z), \sup (\mu_i (z)) \}$$

$$= \min \{ (\cup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i) ((x * y) * x) * z, (\cup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i(z)) \}. \text{ This completes the proof.}$$

Theorem 3.4.10. A fuzzy subset μ of an BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is an implicative fuzzy ideal of X if and only if $\mu_t \neq \emptyset$ is an implicative ideal of X .

Proof: Suppose that μ is an implicative fuzzy ideal of X and $\mu_t \neq \emptyset$, for any $t \in (0,1]$, there exists $x \in \mu_t$ so that $\mu(x) \geq t$. It follows from (IF_1) that

$$\mu(0) \geq \mu(x) \geq t \text{ so that } 0 \in \mu_t . \text{ Let } x, y, z \in X \text{ be such that}$$

$$((x * y) * x) * z \in \mu_t \text{ and } z \in \mu_t . \text{ Using Definition (3.4.1(2)), we know that}$$

$$\mu(x) \geq \min \{ \mu(((x * y) * x) * z), \mu(z) \} \geq \min \{ t, t \} = t, \text{ thus } x \in \mu_t . \text{ Hence } \mu_t \text{ is an implicative ideal of } X .$$

Conversely, suppose that $\mu_t \neq \emptyset$ is an implicative ideal of X , for every $t \in (0,1]$, and any $x \in X$, let $\mu(x) = t$. Then $x \in \mu_t$. Since $0 \in \mu_t$, it follows that $\mu(0) \geq t = \mu(x)$, so that $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$.

Now, we need to show that μ satisfies Definition (3.4.1(2)). If not, then there exist $a, b, c \in X$ such that $\mu(a) \leq \min \{ \mu((a * b) * a) * c, \mu(c) \}$. Taking $t = 1/2 (\mu(a) + \min \{ \mu((a * b) * a) * c, \mu(c) \})$, then we have $\mu(a) < t < \min \{ \mu((a * b) * a) * c, \mu(c) \}$.

Hence

$((a * b) * a) * c \in \mu_t$ and $c \in \mu_t$, but $a \notin \mu_t$ which means that μ_t is not an implicative ideal of X . this is contradiction. Therefore μ is an implicative fuzzy ideal of X .

CHAPTER THREE

SECTION FIVE

3.5. Positive Implicative Fuzzy Ideals of BCK-algebras

In this section, we discuss the notion of sub-implicative ideals, and we give some characterizations of this concept.

Definition 3.5.1. A nonempty subset μ of an BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is called a **Positive implicative fuzzy ideal** (briefly PIF-ideal) of X , if for all $x, y, z \in X$,

$$(PIF_1) \mu(0) \geq \mu(x) ,$$

$$(PIF_2) \mu(x * z) \geq \min \{ \mu((x * (y * z))), \mu(y * z) \} .$$

Example 3.5.2. Let $X = \{0,1,2,3,4\}$ in which the operation $*$ is given by:

*	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0	0
2	2	1	0	0	0

3	3	1	1	0	0
4	4	3	2	1	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra. Define a fuzzy subset $\mu: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ by $\mu(0) = t_0$, $\mu(1) = \mu(2) = t_1$, $\mu(3) = \mu(4) = t_2$, where $t_0, t_1, t_2 \in [0,1]$ with $t_0 > t_1 > t_2$. Routine calculation gives that μ is a PIF-ideal of BCK-algebra X .

Proposition 3.5.3. Every PIF-ideal of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is order reversing.

Proof. Let μ be PIF-ideal of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ and let $x, y, z \in X$ be such that $x \leq y$, then $x * y = 0$ and by (PIF_1)

$$\mu(x * z) \geq \min\{\mu((x * (y * z)), \mu(y * z)), \text{ let } z = 0, \text{ then}$$

$$\mu(x * 0) \geq \min\{\mu(x * (y * 0)), \mu(y * 0)\}$$

$$\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(x * y), \mu(y)\} = \min\{\mu(0), \mu(y)\} = \mu(y).$$

Theorem 3.5.4. Let μ be a PIF-ideal of BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. μ is a PIF-ideal of X if and only if, for every $t \in [0,1]$, μ_t is positive implicative ideal of X .

Proof. Assume that μ is a PIF-ideal of X , by Definition (3.5.1(1)), we have $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ for all $x \in X$ therefore $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x) \geq t$ for $x \in \mu_t$ and so $0 \in \mu_t$.

Let $x, y, z \in X$ be such that $(x * (y * z)) \in \mu_t$ and $y * z \in \mu_t$, then $\mu(x * (y * z)) \geq t$ and $\mu(y * z) \geq t$, since μ is a PIF-ideal, it follows that $\mu(x * z) \geq \min\{\mu(x * (y * z)), \mu(y * z)\} \geq t$ and we have that $x * z \in \mu_t$. Hence μ_t is positive implicative ideal of X .

Conversely, we only need to show that (1) and (2) in Definition (3.5.1) are true. If (1) is false, then there exist $x' \in X$ such that $\mu(0) < \mu(x')$. If we take $t' = (\mu(x') + \mu(0))/2$, then $\mu(0) < t'$ and $0 \leq t' < \mu(x') \leq 1$, then $x' \in \mu$ and $\mu \neq \emptyset$. As $\mu_{t'}$ is positive implicative ideal of X , we have $0 \in \mu_{t'}$ and so $\mu(0) \geq t'$. This is a contradiction.

Now, assume (2) is not true, then there exist $x', y', z' \in X$ such that, $\mu(x' * z') < \min\{\mu(x' * (y' * z')), \mu(y' * z')\}$. Putting $t' = (\mu(x' * z') + \min\{\mu(x' * (y' * z')), \mu(y' * z')\})/2$, then $\mu(x' * z') < t'$ and $0 \leq t' < \min\{\mu(x' * (y' * z')), \mu(y' * z')\} \leq 1$, hence $\mu(x' * (y' * z')) > t'$ and $\mu(y' * z') > t'$, which imply that $(x' * (y' * z')) \in \mu_{t'}$ and $(y' * z') \in \mu_{t'}$. Since $\mu_{t'}$ is positive implicative ideal, it follows that $(x' * z') \in \mu_{t'}$ and that $\mu(x' * z') \geq t'$, this is also a contradiction. Hence μ is a PIF-ideal of X . ■

Corollary 3.5.5. Let μ be a fuzzy subset of BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. If μ is a PIF-ideal, then for every $t \in \text{Im}(\mu)$, μ_t is positive implicative ideal of X , when $\mu_t \neq \emptyset$.

Proof. H.W.

Proposition 3.5.6. Any PIF-ideal of a BCK-algebra must be positive implicative ideal, but the inverse is not true.

Proof. Since μ is a PIF-ideal of BCK-algebra X , then by Theorem (3.5.4), for every $t \in [0,1]$, μ_t is positive implicative ideal of X . By Proposition (2.2.3), for every $t \in [0,1]$, μ_t is ideal of X . Hence μ is a fuzzy ideal of BCK-algebra X by Proposition (3.2.4). ■

EXAMPLE 3.5.7. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ in which $*$ is given by

*	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	1	0	1
2	2	2	0	2	0
3	3	1	3	0	3
4	4	4	4	4	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is a BCK-algebra. $\{0,2\}$ is an ideal, but not positive implicative as $(3 * 2) * 0 \in \{0, 2\}$, $2 * 0 = 2 \in \{0, 2\}$ and $3 * 0 = 3 \notin \{0,2\}$. This shows that an ideal need not be positive implicative.

Define a fuzzy subset $\mu: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ by $\mu(0) = 0.7$, $\mu(a) = \mu(b) = \mu(c) = \mu(d) = 0.2$, we get for $z = 0, x = a$ and $y = b$. Then

$$\mu((a * c) * b) = \mu(a) = 0.2 \leq 0.7 = \min\{\mu(c * (a * c) * b), \mu(0)\} = \mu(0)$$

Proposition 3.5.8. Every fuzzy ideal of positive implicative BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is a PIF-ideal of X .

Proof. Since μ is a fuzzy ideal of BCK-algebra X , then by Theorem (3.2.4), for every $t \in [0,1]$, μ_t is ideal of X . By Corollary (2.2.8), for every $t \in [0,1]$, μ_t is positive implicative of X . Hence μ is a PIF-ideal of BCK-algebra X by Proposition (3.5.4). ■

Theorem 3.5.9. Let $(X; *, 0)$ and $(Y; *, 0')$ be two BCK-algebras and $f: (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, 0')$ be a homomorphism, then

- 5) If I is a PIF-ideal of X , then $f(I)$ is a PIF-ideal of Y , where f is onto.
- 6) If J is a PIF-ideal of Y , then $f^{-1}(J)$ is a PIF-ideal of X .

Proof.

5) Let I be a PIF-ideal of X that mean $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ and

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(x * z) &\geq \min\{\mu(x * (y * z)), \mu(y * z)\}, \text{ for all } x, y, z \in X. \text{ Clearly, } 0' \in f(I), \text{ then} \\ \mu(f(0)) &\geq \mu(f(x)) \text{ for all } x \in X, \text{ and let } x, y, z \in f(I) \text{ that means } x = f(a), y = \\ &f(b), z = f(c) \text{ for some } a, b, c \in I, \text{ then} \\ \mu(x * z) &= \mu(f(a) * f(c)) = \mu(f(a * c)) \geq \min\{\mu(f(a * (b * c))), \mu(f(b * c))\} \\ &= \min\{\mu(f(a) * f(b) * f(c)), \mu(f(b) * f(c))\} \\ &= \min\{\mu((x * (y * z))), \mu(y * z)\}, \text{ for all } x, y, z \in Y. \end{aligned}$$

Hence $f(I)$ is a PIF-ideal of Y .

6) Let J be a PIF-ideal of Y that mean $\mu(f(0)) = \mu(0') \geq \mu(f(x))$ and

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(f(x * z)) &\geq \min\{\mu(f(x) * f(y) * f(z)), \mu(f(y) * f(z))\}, \text{ for all } x, y, z \in Y. \text{ Clearly, } 0' \\ &\in f(J) \text{ and let } a, b, c \in f^{-1}(J) \text{ that means } a = f^{-1}(x), b = f^{-1}(y), c = f^{-1}(z) \text{ for some } x, \\ &y, z \in J, \text{ then} \\ \mu(a * c) &= \mu(f^{-1}(x) * f^{-1}(z)) = \mu(f^{-1}(x * z)) \geq \min\{\mu(f^{-1}(x * (y * z))), \mu(f^{-1}(y * z))\} \\ &\geq \min\{\mu(f^{-1}(x) * f^{-1}(y) * f^{-1}(z)), \mu(f^{-1}(y) * f^{-1}(z))\} \\ &= \min\{\mu(a * (b * c)), \mu(b * c)\}, \text{ for all } a, b, c \in X. \text{ Hence } f^{-1}(J) \text{ is a PIF-ideal of } X. \quad \blacksquare \end{aligned}$$

CHAPTER THREE

SECTION SIX

3.6. Commutative Fuzzy Ideals of BCK-algebras

In this section, we discuss the notion of commutative ideals, and we give some characterizations of this concept.

Definition 3.6.1. A nonempty subset μ of an BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is called a **commutative fuzzy ideal** (briefly CF-ideal) of X , if for all $x, y, z \in X$,

$$(CF_1) \mu(0) \geq \mu(x),$$

$$(CF_2) \mu(x * (y * (y * x))) \geq \min \{\mu((x * y) * z), \mu(z)\}.$$

Example 3.6.2. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ in which the operation $*$ is given by:

*	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	0	0	0	0
1	1	0	0	0	0
2	2	0	0	1	0
3	3	3	3	0	0
4	4	4	4	4	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is an BCK-algebra. Define a fuzzy subset $\mu: X \rightarrow [0, 1]$ by $\mu(0) = 0.6, \mu(1) = \mu(2) = 0.5, \mu(3) = \mu(4) = 0.4$. Routine calculation gives that μ is CF-ideal of BCK-algebra X .

Proposition 3.6.3. Every CF-ideal of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is order reversing.

Proof. H.W.

Theorem 3.6.4. A fuzzy subset μ of an BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is a commutative fuzzy ideal of X if and only if $\mu_t \neq \emptyset$ is a commutative ideal of X .

Proof: Suppose that μ is a commutative fuzzy ideal of X and $\mu_t \neq \emptyset$, for any $t \in (0, 1]$, there exists $x \in \mu_t$ so that $\mu(x) \geq t$. It follows from (CF_1) that $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x) \geq t$ so that $0 \in \mu_t$. Let $x, y, z \in X$ be such that

$(x * y) * z \in \mu_t$ and $z \in \mu_t$. Using Definition (2.11(2)), we know that

$$\mu(x * (y * (y * x))) \geq \min \{\mu((x * y) * z), \mu(z)\} = \min\{t, t\} = t, \text{ thus}$$

$x * (y * (y * x)) \in \mu_t$. Hence μ_t is a commutative ideal of X .

Conversely, suppose that $\mu_t \neq \emptyset$ is a commutative ideal of X , for every $t \in (0, 1]$, and any $x \in X$, let $\mu(x) = t$. Then $x \in \mu_t$. Since $0 \in \mu_t$, it follows that

$$\mu(0) \geq t = \mu(x), \text{ so that } \mu(0) \geq \mu(x), \text{ for all } x \in X.$$

Now, we need to show that μ satisfies Definition (2.11(2)). If not, then there exist

$a, b, c \in X$ such that $\mu(a * (b * (b * a))) \leq \min \{\mu((a * b) * c), \mu(c)\}$. Taking

$t = 1/2 (\mu(a * (b * (b * a))) + \min \{\mu((a * b) * c), \mu(c)\})$, then we have

$\mu(a * (b * (b * a))) < t < \min \{\mu((a * b) * c), \mu(c)\}$. Hence

$((a * b) * c) \in \mu_t$ and $c \in \mu_t$, but $a * (b * (b * a)) \notin \mu_t$ which means that μ_t is not a commutative ideal of X . this is contradiction. Therefore μ is a commutative fuzzy ideal of X .

Proposition 3.6.5. If $(X; *, 0)$ is commutative BCK-algebra, then every fuzzy ideal of X is a CF-ideal of X .

Proof. Let μ be a fuzzy ideal of X , then by Definition (3.1.1(2)), for all $x, y, z \in X$, $\mu(y) \geq \min\{\mu(y * z), \mu(z)\}$. Substituting $x * (y * (y * x))$ for y in Definition (3.1.1(2)), $\mu(x * (y * (y * x))) \geq \min\{\mu(x * (y * (y * x)) * z), \mu(z)\}$, but BCK-algebra is commutative, i.e., $(y * x) * x = (x * y) * y$, hence $\mu(x * (y * (y * x))) \geq \min\{\mu(z * (x * y)), \mu(z)\}$

Since $((y * x) * x) * y = (y * x^2) * y^2 = ((y * x) * x) * y * (0 * y) \leq (y * x) * x$

Then, $z * ((x * y) * y) * x \geq z * ((y * x) * x)$. i.e.,

$\mu(z * ((x * y) * y) * x) \leq \mu(z * ((y * x) * x))$, by Proposition (3.6.3)

$\mu(x * (y * (y * x))) \geq \min\{\mu((x * y) * z), \mu(z)\}$. Which shows that μ is a CF-ideal of X .

Theorem 3.6.6. Let μ be a fuzzy subset of an BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ satisfying the condition (CF_2) , then μ satisfies the following inequality:

$(CF_3) \mu(x * (y * (y * x))) \geq \mu(x * y)$.

Proof. Let μ by satisfying (CF_2) . i.e.,

$\mu(x * (y * (y * x))) \geq \min\{\mu((x * y) * z), \mu(z)\}$, then by taking $z = 0$ in (CF_2) and using (CF_1) , we get $\mu(x * (y * (y * x))) \geq \min\{\mu((x * y) * 0), \mu(0)\} = \mu(x * y)$.

Theorem 3.6.7. Every CF-ideal is a fuzzy ideal, but the converse does not hold.

Proof. Let μ be CF-ideal of a BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$; put $x = y$ in (CF_2) , we get

$\mu(x * (y * (y * x))) = \mu(x * (x * (x * y))) = \mu(x * y) \geq \min\{\mu((x * y) * z), \mu(z)\}$, for all $x, y, z \in X$. Hence μ is a fuzzy ideal of X .

The following example shows that the converse of Theorem (3.6.6) may not be true.

Example 3.6.8. Let $X = \{0, a, b, c, d\}$ in which the operation $*$ is given by:

*	0	a	b	c	d
0	0	0	0	0	0
1	a	0	0	0	0
2	b	a	0	0	0
3	c	c	c	0	0
4	d	d	d	d	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is an BCK-algebra. Define a fuzzy subset $\mu: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ by $\mu(0) = 0.8$, $\mu(a) = \mu(b) = \mu(c) = \mu(d) = 0.3$, we get for $z = 0, x = a$ and $y = b$. Then $\mu(b * (0 * a)) = \mu(a) = 0.3 \leq 0.8 = \min\{\mu(0 * ((a * b) * b) * 0), \mu(0)\} = \mu(0)$

Theorem 3.6.9. Every fuzzy ideal μ of an BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ satisfying the condition (CF_3) is a CF-ideal of X .

Proof. Let μ be fuzzy ideal of X satisfying the condition (CF_3) . We get

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is an BCK-algebra. Define a fuzzy subset $\mu: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ by $\mu(0) = t_0$, $\mu(1) = \mu(2) = t_1$, $\mu(3) = \mu(4) = t_2$, where $t_0, t_1, t_2 \in [0,1]$ with $t_0 > t_1 > t_2$. Routine calculation gives that μ is a fuzzy filter of BCK-algebra X .

Proposition 3.7.3. Every fuzzy filter of an BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is order reversing.

Proof. Let μ be fuzzy filter of an BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ and let $x, y \in X$ be such that

$$\begin{aligned} x \leq y, \text{ then } x * y = 0 \text{ and by } (FF_1) \\ \mu(x) \geq \min \{ \mu((x^* * y^*)^*), \mu(y) \} = \min \{ \mu((x * y)^{**}), \mu(y) \} \\ = \min \{ \mu((0)^{**}), \mu(y) \} = \mu(y). \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 3.7.4. Let μ be a fuzzy subset of BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. μ is a fuzzy filter of X if and only if, for every $t \in [0,1]$, μ_t is BCK-filter of X .

Proof. Assume that μ is a fuzzy filter of X , by Definition (3.7.1(1)), we have $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ for all $x \in X$ therefore $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x) \geq t$ for $x \in \mu_t$ and so $0 \in \mu_t$.

Let $x, y \in X$ be such that $((x^* * y^*)^*) \in \mu_t$ and $y \in \mu_t$, then $\mu((x^* * y^*)^*) \geq t$ and $\mu(y) \geq t$, since μ is a fuzzy filter, it follows that $\mu(x) \geq \min \{ \mu((x^* * y^*)^*), \mu(y) \} \geq t$ and we have that $x \in \mu_t$. Hence μ_t is BCK-filter of X .

Conversely, we only need to show that (1) and (2) in Definition (3.7.1) are true. If (1) is false, then there exist $x' \in X$ such that $\mu(0) < \mu(x')$. If we take $t' = (\mu(x') + \mu(0))/2$, then $\mu(0) < t'$ and $0 \leq t' < \mu(x') \leq 1$, then $x' \in \mu$ and $\mu \neq \emptyset$. As $\mu_{t'}$ is BCK-filter of X , we have $0 \in \mu_{t'}$, and so $\mu(0) \geq t'$. This is a contradiction.

Now, assume (2) is not true, then there exist $x', y' \in X$ such that,
 $\mu(x') < \min \{ \mu((x'^* * y'^*)^*), \mu(y') \}$.
 Putting $t' = (\mu(x') + \min \{ \mu((x'^* * y'^*)^*), \mu(y') \})/2$, then
 $\mu(x') < t'$ and $0 \leq t' < \min \{ \mu((x'^* * y'^*)^*), \mu(y') \} \leq 1$, hence
 $\mu((x'^* * y'^*)^*) > t'$ and $\mu(y') > t'$, which imply that
 $((x'^* * y'^*)^*) \in \mu_{t'}$ and $(y') \in \mu_{t'}$. Since $\mu_{t'}$ is po BCK-filter, it follows that $(x') \in \mu_{t'}$, and that
 $\mu(x') \geq t'$, this is also a contradiction. Hence μ is a fuzzy filter of X . ■

Proposition 3.7.5. The intersection of any set of fuzzy filters of BCK-algebra X is also fuzzy filter.

Proof. Let $\{ \mu_i : i \in \Lambda \}$ be a family fuzzy filters of BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, then for any $x, y \in X$,

$$(\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(0) = \inf(\mu_i(0)) \geq \inf(\mu_i(x)) = (\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(x) \text{ and}$$

$$\begin{aligned} (\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(x) &= \inf(\mu_i(x)) \\ &\geq \inf(\min \{ \mu_i((x^* * y^*)^*), \mu_i(y) \}) \\ &= \min \{ \inf(\mu_i((x^* * y^*)^*)), \inf(\mu_i(y)) \} \\ &= \min \{ (\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)((x^* * y^*)^*), (\bigcap_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(y) \}. \end{aligned}$$

This completes the proof.

Proposition 3.7.6. Let $\{ \mu_i : i \in \Lambda \}$ be a family of fuzzy filters of an BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ where $\mu_n \subseteq \mu_{n+1}$, for all $i \in \Lambda$. Then $\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i$ is fuzzy filter of X .

Proof. Let $\{ \mu_i : i \in \Lambda \}$ be a family of ideals of X . We will show that $\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i$ is an ideal of X .

$$(\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(0) = \sup(\mu_i(0)) \geq \sup(\mu_i(x)) = (\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(x). \text{ Let } x, y \in \bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i.$$

$$\begin{aligned} \text{and } (\bigcup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i)(x) &= \sup(\mu_i(x)) \\ &\geq \sup(\min \{ \mu_i((x^* * y^*)^*), \mu_i(y) \}) \\ &\geq \min \{ \sup(\mu_i((x^* * y^*)^*)), \sup(\mu_i(y)) \} \end{aligned}$$

$= \min \{(\cup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i) ((x^* * y^*)^*), (\cup_{i \in \Lambda} \mu_i(y))\}$. This completes the proof.

Theorem 3.7.7. Let $(X; *, 0)$ and $(Y; *, 0')$ be two BCK-algebras and $f : (X; *, 0) \rightarrow (Y; *, 0')$ be a homomorphism, then

- 1) If I is a fuzzy filter of X , then $f(I)$ is a fuzzy filter of Y , where f is onto.
- 2) If J is a fuzzy filter of Y , then $f^{-1}(J)$ is a fuzzy filter of X .

Proof.

1) Let I be a fuzzy filter of X that mean $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$ and $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu((x^* * y^*)^*), \mu(y)\}$, for all $x, y \in X$. Clearly, $0' \in f(I)$, then $\mu(f(0)) \geq \mu(f(x))$ for all $x \in X$, and let $x, y \in f(I)$ that means $x = f(a)$, $y = f(b)$, for some $a, b \in I$, then

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(x) &= \mu(f(a)) \min\{\mu(f((a^* * b^*)^*)), \mu(f(b))\} \\ &= \min\{\mu(f(a^*) * f(b^*)^*), \mu(f(b))\} \\ &= \min\{\mu((x^* * y^*)^*), \mu(y)\}, \text{ for all } x, y \in Y. \end{aligned}$$

Hence $f(I)$ is a fuzzy filter of Y .

- 2) Let J be a fuzzy filter of Y that mean $\mu(f(0)) = \mu(0') \geq \mu(f(x))$ and $\mu(f(x)) \geq \min\{\mu(f(x) * f(y)^* f(z)), \mu(f(y)^* f(z))\}$, for all $x, y, z \in Y$. Clearly, $0' \in f(J)$ and let $a, b, c \in f^{-1}(J)$ that means $a = f^{-1}(x)$, $b = f^{-1}(y)$, for some $x, y \in J$, then $\mu(a) = \mu(f^{-1}(x)) \geq \min\{\mu(f^{-1}((x^* * y^*)^*)), \mu(f^{-1}(y))\} \geq \min\{\mu((f^{-1}(x^*) * f^{-1}(y^*))^*), \mu(f^{-1}(y))\} = \min\{\mu((a^* * b^*)^*), \mu(b)\}$, for all $a, b \in X$. Hence $f^{-1}(J)$ is a fuzzy filter of X . ■

CHAPTER THREE

SECTION SEVEN

3.7. Sub-implicative Fuzzy Ideals of BCK-algebras

In this section, we discuss the notion of sub-implicative ideals, and we give some characterizations of this concept.

Definition 3.7.1. A nonempty subset μ of an BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is called a **sub-implicative fuzzy ideal** (briefly SIF-ideal) of X , if for all $x, y, z \in X$,

$$(SIF_1) \mu(0) \geq \mu(x),$$

$$(SIF_2) \mu(x * y^2) \geq \min\{\mu(z * ((x * y) * (y * x^2))), \mu(z)\}.$$

Example 3.7.2. Let $X = \{0, 1, 2, 3, 4\}$ in which the operation $*$ is given by:

*	0	1	2	3	4
0	0	1	2	3	4
1	0	0	1	3	4
2	0	0	0	3	4
3	0	0	0	0	4
4	0	0	0	0	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is an BCK-algebra. Define a fuzzy subset $\mu: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ by $\mu(0) = t_0$, $\mu(1) = \mu(2) = t_1$, $\mu(3) = \mu(4) = t_2$, where $t_0, t_1, t_2 \in [0,1]$ with $t_0 > t_1 > t_2$. Routine calculation gives that μ is a SIF-ideal of BCK-algebra X .

Proposition 3.7.3. Every SIF-ideal of an BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is order reversing.

Proof. Let μ be SIF-ideal of an BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ and let $x, y, z \in X$ be such that $x \leq z$, then $z * x = 0$ and by (SIF_1)

$$\mu(x * y^2) \geq \min\{\mu(z * ((x * y) * (y * x^2))), \mu(z)\}, \text{ let } y = x, \text{ then}$$

$$\mu(x * x^2) \geq \min\{\mu(z * ((x * x) * (x * x^2))), \mu(z)\}$$

$$\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(z * x), \mu(z)\} = \min\{\mu(0), \mu(z)\} = \mu(z).$$

Proposition 3.7.4. Let μ be SIF-ideal of an BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, if the inequality $y * x \leq z$ hold in X , Then $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(y), \mu(z)\}$.

Proof. Let μ be a SIF-ideal of X and let $x, y, z \in X$ be such that $y * x \leq z$, then $z * (y * x) = 0$ or $y * (z * x) = 0$,

i.e., $z * x \leq y$, we get $\mu(z * x) \geq \mu(y)$ --- (4).

$$\begin{aligned} \text{By } (SIF_2) \mu(x * y^2) &\geq \min\{\mu(z * ((x * y) * (y * x^2))), \mu(z)\}, \text{ let } y = x, \text{ then } \mu(x * \\ x^2) &\geq \min\{\mu(z * ((x * x) * (x * x^2))), \mu(z)\} \\ &= \min\{\mu(z * x), \mu(z)\}. \text{ i.e.,} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(z * x), \mu(z)\} \geq \min\{\mu(y), \mu(z)\}, \text{ by (4).}$$

Proposition 3.7.5. If $(X; *, 0)$ is implicative BCK-algebra, then every fuzzy ideal of X is an SIF-ideal of X .

Proof. Let μ be an fuzzy ideal of X , then by Definition (2.11(2)), for all $y, z \in X$, $\mu(y) \geq \min\{\mu(z * y), \mu(z)\}$. Substituting $x * y^2$ for y in Definition (2.11(2)),

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(x * y^2) &\geq \min\{\mu(z * (x * y^2)), \mu(z)\}, \text{ but BCK-algebra is implicative, i.e.,} \\ (x * y^2) &= (x * y) * (y * x^2), \text{ hence} \\ \mu(x * y^2) &\geq \min\{\mu(z * (x * y^2)), \mu(z)\} \\ &= \min\{\mu(z * (x * y) * (y * x^2)), \mu(z)\}. \end{aligned}$$

Which shows that μ is SIF-ideal of X .

Theorem 3.7.6. Let μ be a fuzzy subset of an BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ satisfying the condition (SIF_2) , then μ satisfies the following inequality:

$$(SIF_3) \mu(x * y^2) \geq \mu((x * y) * (x * y^2)).$$

Proof. Let μ by satisfying (SIF_2) . i.e.,

$\mu(x * y^2) \geq \min\{\mu(z * ((x * y) * (y * x^2))), \mu(z)\}$, then by taking $z = 0$ in (SIF_2) and using (SIF_1) and Proposition (2.2(d)), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(x * y^2) &\geq \min\{\mu(0 * ((x * y) * (y * x^2))), \mu(0)\} \\ &= \mu((x * y) * (y * x^2)). \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 3.7.7. Every SIF-ideal is a fuzzy ideal, but the converse does not hold.

Proof. Let μ be SIF-ideal of an BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$; put $x = y$ in (SIF_2) , we get

$\mu(x * x^2) \geq \min \{ \mu(z * ((x * x) * (x * x^2))), \mu(z) \}$, then

$\mu(x) \geq \min \{ \mu(z * x), \mu(z) \}$, for all $x, z \in X$. Hence μ is a fuzzy ideal of X .

The following example shows that the converse of Theorem (6.7) may not be true.

Example 3.7.8. Let $X = \{0, a, b, c, d\}$ in which the operation $*$ is given by:

*	0	a	b	c	d
0	0	a	b	c	d
a	0	0	a	c	d
b	0	0	0	c	d
c	0	0	0	0	d
d	0	0	0	0	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is an BCK-algebra. Define a fuzzy subset $\mu: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ by $\mu(0) = 0.7$, $\mu(a) = \mu(b) = \mu(c) = \mu(d) = 0.2$, we get for $z = 0, x = a$ and $y = b$. Then $\mu((a * b) * b) = \mu(a) = 0.2 \leq 0.7 = \min \{ \mu(0 * (a * b) * ((b * a) * a)), \mu(0) \} = \mu(0)$

Theorem 3.7.9. Every fuzzy ideal μ of an BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ satisfying the condition (SIF_3) is a SIF-ideal of X .

Proof. Let μ be fuzzy ideal of X satisfying the condition (SIF_3) . We get

$$\mu(x * y^2) \geq \mu((x * y) * (y * x^2)) \text{ and}$$

$$\mu(x * y^2) \geq \min \{ \mu(z * ((x * y) * (y * x^2))), \mu(z) \}$$

By Definition (2.11(2)), hence

$$\mu(x * y^2) \geq \mu((x * y) * (y * x^2)) \geq \min \{ \mu(z * ((x * y) * (y * x^2))), \mu(z) \}, \text{ which proves the condition } (SIF_2). \text{ This completes the proof.}$$

Theorem 3.7.10. Let μ be a fuzzy ideal of an BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. Then the following are equivalent

- (i) μ is a SIF-ideal of X ,
- (ii) $\mu(x * y^2) \geq \mu((x * y) * (y * x^2))$
- (iii) $\mu(x * y^2) = \mu((x * y) * (y * x^2))$.

Proof. (i) \Rightarrow (ii) Suppose that μ is a SIF-ideal of X . By (SIF_2) and (SIF_1) we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(x * y^2) &\geq \min \{ \mu(0 * ((x * y) * (y * x^2))), \mu(0) \} \\ &= \mu(0 * ((x * y) * (y * x^2))) = \mu((x * y) * (y * x^2)), \text{ i.e.,} \end{aligned}$$

$$\mu(x * y^2) \geq \mu((x * y) * (y * x^2)).$$

(ii) \Rightarrow (iii) Since $(x * y) * (y * x^2) \leq (x * y^2)$, by Proposition (6.3), we obtain,

$$\mu(x * y^2) \geq \mu((x * y) * (y * x^2)) \text{ Combining (ii) we have}$$

$$\mu(x * y^2) = \mu((x * y) * (y * x^2)).$$

(iii) \Rightarrow (i) Since

$$(z * ((x * y) * (y * x^2))) * ((x * y) * (y * x^2))$$

$$= ((x * y) * (z * (y * x^2))) * ((x * y) * (y * x^2))$$

$$\leq (z * (y * x^2)) * (y * x^2) = (z * (y * x^2)) * (0 * (y * x^2)) \leq 0 * z = z,$$

by Proposition (6.5). we obtain $\mu((x * y) * (y * x^2)) \geq \min \{\mu((x * y) * (y * x^2)), \mu(z)\}$. From (iii), we have

$\mu(x * y^2) \geq \min \{\mu(z * ((x * y) * (y * x^2))), \mu(z)\}$. Hence μ is SIF-ideal of X .

Theorem 3.7.11. A fuzzy subset μ of an BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is a sub-implicative fuzzy ideal of X if and only if $\mu_t \neq \emptyset$ is a sub-implicative ideal of X .

Proof: Suppose that μ is a sub-implicative fuzzy ideal of X and $\mu_t \neq \emptyset$, for any $t \in (0,1]$, there exists $x \in \mu_t$ so that $\mu(x) \geq t$. It follows from (SIF_1) that $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x) \geq t$ so that $0 \in \mu_t$. Let $x, y, z \in X$ be such that $z * ((x * y) * (y * x)) \in \mu_t$ and $z \in \mu_t$. Using Definition (2.11(2)), we know that

$$\mu(x * y^2) \geq \min \{\mu(z * (x * y) * ((y * x^2))), \mu(z)\} = \min\{t, t\} = t, \text{ thus}$$

$$x * y^2 \in \mu_t. \text{ Hence } \mu_t \text{ is a sub-implicative ideal of } X.$$

Conversely, suppose that $\mu_t \neq \emptyset$ is a sub-implicative ideal of X , for every $t \in (0,1]$, and any $x \in X$, let $\mu(x) = t$. Then $x \in \mu_t$. Since $0 \in \mu_t$, it follows that $\mu(0) \geq t = \mu(x)$, so that $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$.

Now, we need to show that μ satisfies Definition (2.11(2)). If not, then there exist $a, b, c \in X$ such that $\mu(a * b^2) \leq \min \{\mu(c * (a * b) * ((b * a^2))), \mu(c)\}$. Taking $t = 1/2 (\mu(a * b^2) + \min \{\mu(c * (a * b) * ((b * a^2))), \mu(c)\})$, then we have $\mu(a * b^2) < t < \min \{\mu(c * (a * b) * ((b * a^2))), \mu(c)\}$. Hence $c * ((a * b) * (b * a^2)) \in \mu_t$ and $c \in \mu_t$, but $a * b^2 \notin \mu_t$ which means that μ_t is not a sub-implicative ideal of X . this is contradiction.

Therefore μ is a sub-implicative fuzzy ideal of X .

CHAPTER THREE

SECTION FIVE

3.8. Sub-commutative Fuzzy Ideals of BCK-algebras

In this section, we discuss the notion of sub-commutative ideals, and we give some characterizations of this concept.

Definition 3.8.1. A nonempty subset μ of an BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is called a **sub-commutative fuzzy ideal** (briefly SCF-ideal) of X , if for all $x, y, z \in X$,

$$(SCF_1) \mu(0) \geq \mu(x),$$

$$(SCF_2) \mu(y * x^2) \geq \min \{\mu(((y * x^2) * y^2) * z), \mu(z)\}.$$

Example 3.8.2. Let $X = \{0,1,2,3,4\}$ in which the operation $*$ is given by:

*	0	1	2	3	4
---	---	---	---	---	---

0	0	1	2	3	4
1	0	0	0	3	4
2	0	0	0	3	4
3	0	0	1	0	4
4	0	0	0	0	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is an BCK-algebra. Define a fuzzy subset $\mu: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ by $\mu(0) = 0.6$, $\mu(1) = \mu(2) = 0.5$, $\mu(3) = \mu(4) = 0.4$. Routine calculation gives that μ is SCF-ideal of BCK-algebra X .

Proposition 3.8.3. Every SCF-ideal of an BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is order reversing.

Proof. Let μ be SCF-ideal of an BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ and let $x, y, z \in X$ be such that $x \leq z$, then $z * x = 0$ and by (SCF_1)

$$\mu(y * x^2) \geq \min\{\mu(z * (y * x^2) * y^2), \mu(z)\}, \text{ let } y = x, \text{ then}$$

$$\mu(x * x^2) \geq \min\{\mu(z * ((x * x^2) * x^2), \mu(z)\}$$

$$\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(z * ((x * x^2) * x^2), \mu(z)\}$$

$$= \min\{\mu(z * x), \mu(z)\} = \min\{\mu(0), \mu(z)\} = \mu(z).$$

Proposition 3.8.4. Let μ be SCF-ideal of an BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$, if the inequality $y * x \leq z$ hold in X , Then $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(y), \mu(z)\}$.

Proof. Let μ be SCF-ideal of X and let $x, y, z \in X$ be such that $y * x \leq z$, then $z * (y * x) = 0$ or $y * (z * x) = 0$,

i.e., $z * x \leq y$, we get $\mu(z * x) \geq \mu(y)$ --- (2).

By (SCF_2) $\mu(y * x^2) \geq \min\{\mu(z * ((y * x^2) * y^2), \mu(z)\}$, let $y = x$, then $\mu(x * x^2) \geq \min\{\mu(z * ((x * x^2) * x^2), \mu(z)\} = \min\{\mu(z * x), \mu(z)\}$. i.e., $\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(z * x), \mu(z)\} \geq \min\{\mu(y), \mu(z)\}$, by (2).

Proposition 3.8.5. If $(X; *, 0)$ is commutative BCK-algebra, then every fuzzy ideal of X is an SCF-ideal of X .

Proof. Let μ be an fuzzy ideal of X , then by Definition (2.11(2)), for all $y, z \in X$, $\mu(y) \geq \min\{\mu(z * y), \mu(z)\}$. Substituting $y * x^2$ for y in Definition (2.11(2)),

$\mu(y * x^2) \geq \min\{\mu(z * (y * x^2)), \mu(z)\}$, but BCK-algebra is commutative, i.e., $(y * x) * x = (x * y) * y$, hence

$$\mu(y * x^2) \geq \min\left\{\mu\left(z * \left((y * x^2) * y^2\right)\right), \mu(z)\right\}$$

Since $(y * x^2) * y^2 = ((y * x) * x) * y * y = ((y * x) * x) * y * (0 * y) \leq (y * x) * x$

Then, $z * ((y * x^2) * y^2) \geq z * ((y * x) * x)$. i.e.,

$$\mu(z * ((y * x^2) * y^2)) \leq \mu(z * (y * x^2)), \text{ by Proposition (3.7.3)}$$

$$\mu(y * x^2) \geq \min\{\mu(z * (y * x^2)), \mu(z)\} \geq \min\{\mu(z * (y * x^2) * y^2), \mu(z)\}.$$

Which shows that μ is SCF-ideal of X .

Theorem 3.8.6. Let μ be a fuzzy subset of an BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ satisfying the condition (SCF_2) , then μ satisfies the following inequality:

$$(SCF_3) \quad \mu(y * x^2) \geq \mu((y * x^2) * y^2).$$

Proof. Let μ be satisfying (SCF_2) . i.e.,

$\mu(y * x^2) \geq \min\{\mu(z * ((y * x^2) * y^2)), \mu(z)\}$, then by taking $z = 0$ in (SCF_2) and using (SCF_1) and Proposition (2.2(d)), we get

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(y * x^2) &\geq \min\{\mu(0 * ((y * x^2) * y^2)), \mu(0)\} \\ &= \mu((y * x^2) * y^2). \end{aligned}$$

Theorem 3.8.7. Every SCF-ideal is a fuzzy ideal, but the converse does not hold. **Proof.** Let μ be SCF-ideal of an BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$; put $x = y$ in (SCF_2) , we get

$$\mu(x * x^2) \geq \min\{\mu(z * ((x * x^2) * x^2)), \mu(z)\}, \text{ then}$$

$$\mu(x) \geq \min\{\mu(z * x), \mu(z)\}, \text{ for all } x, z \in X. \text{ Hence } \mu \text{ is a fuzzy ideal of } X.$$

The following example shows that the converse of Theorem (3.7) may not be true.

Example 3.8.8. Let $X = \{0, a, b, c, d\}$ in which the operation $*$ is given by:

*	0	a	b	c	d
0	0	a	b	c	d
a	0	0	a	c	d
b	0	0	0	c	d
c	0	0	0	0	d
d	0	0	0	0	0

Then $(X; *, 0)$ is an BCK-algebra. Define a fuzzy subset $\mu: X \rightarrow [0,1]$ by $\mu(0) = 0.8, \mu(a) = \mu(b) = \mu(c) = \mu(d) = 0.3$, we get for $z = 0, x = a$ and $y = b$. Then $\mu((c * a) * a) = \mu(a) = 0.3 \leq 0.8 = \min\{\mu(0 * (c * a) * a) * c), \mu(0)\} = \mu(0)$

Theorem 3.8.9. Every fuzzy ideal μ of an BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ satisfying the condition (SCF_3) is a SCF-ideal of X .

Proof. Let μ be fuzzy ideal of X satisfying the condition (SCF_3) . We get

$$\mu(y * x^2) \geq \mu((y * x^2) * y^2) \text{ and by Definition (2.11(2)),}$$

$$\mu(y * x^2) \geq \mu((y * x^2) * y^2) \geq \min\{\mu(z * (y * x^2) * y^2), \mu(z)\}$$

By (SCF_3) , which proves the condition (SCF_2) . This completes the proof.

Theorem 3.8.10. Let μ be a fuzzy ideal of an BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$. Then the following are equivalent

- (i) μ is a SCF-ideal of X ,
- (ii) $\mu(y * x^2) \geq \mu((y * x^2) * y^2)$
- (iii) $\mu(y * x^2) = \mu((y * x^2) * y^2)$.

Proof. (i) \Rightarrow (ii) Suppose that μ is a SCF-ideal of X . By (SCF_2) and (SCF_1) we have

$$\begin{aligned} \mu(y * x^2) &\geq \min\{\mu(z * (y * x^2) * y^2), \mu(z)\} \\ &= \mu(0 * ((y * x^2) * y^2)) = \mu((y * x^2) * y^2), \text{ i.e.,} \end{aligned}$$

(ii) \Rightarrow (iii) Since $(y * x^2) * y^2 \leq (y * x^2)$, by Proposition (4.3), we obtain,

$$\mu(y * x^2) \geq \mu((y * x^2) * y^2) \text{ Combining (ii) we have}$$

$$\mu(y * x^2) = \mu((y * x^2) * y^2).$$

(iii) \Rightarrow (i) Since

$$\left(z * \left((y * x^2) * y^2 \right) \right) * \left((y * x^2) * y^2 \right) * \left(0 * \left((y * x^2) * y^2 \right) \right) * \left((y * x^2) * y^2 \right) \leq 0 * z = z$$

by Proposition (3.8.5). we $\mu(y * x^2) \geq \min\{\mu(z * (y * x^2) * y^2), \mu(z)\}$. Hence μ is SCF-ideal of X .

Theorem 3.8.11. A fuzzy subset μ of an BCK-algebra $(X; *, 0)$ is a sub-commutative fuzzy ideal of X if and only if $\mu_t \neq \emptyset$ is a sub-commutative ideal of X .

Proof: Suppose that μ is a sub-commutative fuzzy ideal of X and $\mu_t \neq \emptyset$, for any $t \in (0,1]$, there exists $x \in \mu_t$ so that $\mu(x) \geq t$. It follows from (SCF_1) that

$\mu(0) \geq \mu(x) \geq t$ so that $0 \in \mu_t$. Let $x, y, z \in X$ be such that $z * (y * x^2) * y^2 \in \mu_t$ and $z \in \mu_t$. Using Definition (2.11(2)), we know that $\mu(y * x^2) \geq \min\{\mu(z * (y * x^2) * y^2), \mu(z)\} = \min\{t, t\} = t$, thus $y * x^2 \in \mu_t$. Hence μ_t is a sub-commutative ideal of X .

Conversely, suppose that $\mu_t \neq \emptyset$ is a sub-commutative ideal of X , for every $t \in (0,1]$, and any $x \in X$, let $\mu(x) = t$. Then $x \in \mu_t$. Since $0 \in \mu_t$, it follows that $\mu(0) \geq t = \mu(x)$, so that $\mu(0) \geq \mu(x)$, for all $x \in X$.

Now, we need to show that μ satisfies Definition (2.11(2)). If not, then there exist $a, b, c \in X$ such that $\mu(b * a^2) \leq \min\{\mu(c * ((b * a^2) * b^2)), \mu(c)\}$. Taking $t = 1/2 (\mu(b * a^2) + \min\{\mu(c * ((b * a^2) * b^2)), \mu(c)\})$, then we have $\mu(b * a^2) < t < \min\{\mu(c * ((b * a^2) * b^2)), \mu(c)\}$. Hence $c * ((b * a^2) * b^2) \in \mu_t$ and $c \in \mu_t$, but $b * a^2 \notin \mu_t$ which means that μ_t is not a sub-commutative ideal of X . this is contradiction. Therefore μ is a sub-commutative fuzzy ideal of X .